

Agricultural Research in India - A profile based on *CAB Abstracts* 1990-1994

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Abstract

India's contribution to research in agriculture and related fields is assessed from an analysis of publications indexed in *CAB Abstracts*. *CAB Abstracts* indexed 51,761 papers, including about 48,300 journal articles, from more than 3,330 addresses in over 800 locations, spread over 30 states/ union territories of India, in the five years 1990-1994. *CAB Abstracts* has classified these papers into 22 major research areas and about 250 subfields. Plants of economic importance is the leading area of research in India, followed by Animal science. The largest number of papers published are in the three subfields, viz. Pests, pathogens and biogenic diseases of plants (8,898 papers), Plant breeding and genetics (5,675 papers) and Plant production (5,231 papers). A little over 63% of these papers were published by academic institutions. Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, and the Haryana Agricultural University, Hissar, have contributed more than 2370 papers each, not including papers published from other centres of these universities. Agricultural universities have published 16,555 papers and general universities 9,933. The Indian Council of Agricultural Research has accounted for 7,856 papers. Indian researchers have used more than 1950 journals from over 65 countries. About 77% of all journal articles were published in 483 Indian journals. In no other field did Indian researchers publish such a large percent of papers in Indian journals. Unlike in physics and materials science, Indian agricultural scientists have used letters journals only infrequently. Delhi, Ludhiana, Hissar and Bangalore are the leading centres of agricultural research, while Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Haryana and Karnataka are the states accounting for the largest number of papers.

Introduction

India is essentially an agricultural country with over three-fourths of the population living in rural areas and dependent on agriculture-related occupations. Pre-Independent India was badly hurt by frequent famines and drought. The eminent economist Amartya Sen owes his major works on hunger to the devastations of the great Bengal famine which had made deep impressions on him when he was still a child. If India today is self sufficient in food, it is in no small measure due to indigenous agricultural research. Of course, India still has a long way to go. The population is increasing; the land area under cultivation is decreasing; and excessive use of chemical fertilisers, pesticides and insecticides are adversely affecting the environment. Far more needs to be produced than now, and produced in a much safer way. These are enough challenges to keep our agricultural research establishment busy.

This paper attempts to map agricultural research in India and tries to answer questions such as which institutions are carrying out the research, in which journals does Indian research get published, in what subfields India is strong, and so on. It aims not only to inventory agricultural research in India but also to provide an appreciation of endogenous research capacity in this crucial field.

This paper is a part of a larger study of mapping science in India in which I am looking at India's contribution to the literature of the world in different fields, based on an analysis of major international databases. In an earlier part of this study I looked at medical research carried out in India and its relevance to the country's healthcare concerns. Based on data collected from seven years of *Medline*, the analysis revealed that there is scope for rethinking on India's research priorities.¹ This study has received considerable attention both within India and abroad.²⁻¹¹ In other studies I and my colleagues have looked at India's contribution to the literatures of mathematics and related areas (based on *Mathsci*),¹² physics (based on *INSPEC-Physics*),¹³ and materials science (based on *Materials Science Citation Index*).¹⁴ I have also made an analysis of medical research in India based on *Science Citation Index* 1981-1985.¹⁵

Methodology

For this macroscopic study on agricultural research in India, I identified all papers from India indexed in the CD-ROM edition of *CAB Abstracts* 1992, which uses SPIRS, the proprietary software of SilverPlatter. Merely giving 'India' as the search term in the address field was not enough as *CAB Abstracts*, unlike *Science Citation Index* or *INSPEC-Physics*, does not invariably give country names. I developed a search strategy in which I gave the names of all Indian cities and towns where there is an institution that could have carried out agricultural or related research. Names of such cities and towns were collected from many sources, such as the *Universities Handbook*,¹⁶ DST's *Directory of R&D Institutions*¹⁷ and INSDOC's *Directory of Scientific Institutions*,¹⁸ and our earlier studies on mapping Indian science.^{1,12-15} Some publications from countries like USA, Japan and Italy also showed up in the data thus downloaded, as names of some cities/towns in my list are found in these countries as well. For example, Salem is in Tamil Nadu, India, and Winston-Salem is in the USA; and Kochi is both in Kerala and in Japan. I carefully removed non-Indian entries. The data needed considerable amount of cleaning up. Names of many institutions had several variants. For example, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Vishwavidyalaya is also referred to as B C Agriculture University and BCKV. In some entries Vishwavidyalaya is spelt as two words: Vishwa Vidyalaya. These were standardised. There were also some errors, such as Dhaka, Karachi and Bangladesh being given as belonging to India. Such entries were removed.

The elements downloaded are: AD: Address; SO: Source (journal title, volume, pages); PY: Publication year; PT: Publication type; and CC: Classification codes. To the data downloaded from *CAB Abstracts* I added country of publication of the journals as seen from *CAB International Serials Checklist* (1995 edition), *Serial Sources for the BIOSIS Previews Database* (1993 edition), *SCI Guide* (1994) and *Ulrich Plus* (1997). The data were converted into a database file and analysed using Foxpro. Unlike in the earlier studies in this series, I did not bother to add impact factor values from *Journal Citation Reports*, for two reasons: (1) Agricultural research is mostly published in low-impact journals. Unlike journals in new biology, agricultural journals are usually of very low impact. (2) Agriculture is not well covered in *Science Citation Index*. Most journals

in which Indian agricultural scientists publish are not indexed in *Science Citation Index*, and therefore they will not be listed in *Journal Citation Reports*.

Analysis

There were 51,761 publications from India in *CAB Abstracts* in the five years 1990-1994. As seen from Table 1, the largest number of papers were published in the four years 1988-1992. About 30% of the papers had a publication date of 1989 or earlier. I am not sure if this delay in coverage by *CAB Abstracts* is largely confined to Indian and other developing country publications or if even mainstream country publications suffer the same extent of delay. Surely, CABI should take some steps to bring down the delay in covering the literature. Other international S&T databases such as *Science Citation Index*, *Chemical Abstracts* and *INSPEC-Physics* cover whatever they cover much quicker. Besides, physicists get to know the latest developments through the Los Alamos archive, which systematically makes available preprints of papers long before they appear in print.

Indian researchers had published about 48,300 articles in about 1,950 journals, as seen from *CAB Abstracts* 1990-1994. In Table 2 I list these journals along with the country of publication of the journals and the number of Indian papers in each one of the journals. For 24 journals, I am unable to assign the countries of publication at the time of writing. It is possible that some of these may not be journals at all. Also, I am not certain that all the non-journal items are classified correctly. There were also 600 book chapters/books and over 1,600 conference papers. Indian agricultural scientists had published 1,560 articles in 61 letters journals/ newsletters (Table 3). Letters journals and books/book chapters (often equivalent to review articles) and even conferences (those which are indexed by CABI) are used by Indian agricultural scientists only to a limited extent. Probably they should examine their publication strategy and make appropriate choices to increase their visibility.

Unlike in most other fields, in agriculture Indian researchers use Indian journals to a very large extent -- close to 77% of all journal articles were published in Indian journals. They have published their work in journals from more than 65 countries, mainly India, UK, USA and the Netherlands (Table 4). Corresponding figures for different fields are:

Physics (as seen from <i>INSPEC-Physics</i> 1992)	- 18.3% [Ref. 13]
Medicine (as seen from <i>Medline</i> 1988- 1994)	- 33.5% [Ref. 1]
Mathematics (as seen from <i>Mathsci</i> 1988-1995)	- 35.2% [Ref. 12]
Materials science (<i>Materials Science Citation Index</i> 1991-1994)	- 9.5% [Ref.14]
Biology (as seen from <i>Biosis</i> 1992)	- 52.3% [Unpublished]
Agriculture (<i>CAB Abstracts</i> 1990-1994)	- 74.6%

This is to be expected. In developing countries, there is some misconception about publishing in home-country journals. Often, articles in foreign journals are given much higher weightage than articles in national journals, not realising that not all foreign journals are uniformly good. Besides, as neurosurgeon Sunil Pandya of KEM Hospital, Mumbai, points out, even the mediocre journals published in the home country may occasionally publish some high quality papers [private communication]. Communication habits vary from field to field.¹⁹ In physics and materials science which are far more 'universal', scientists prefer to publish in international journals, which are often prohibitively costly, to maximise their chances of reaching out to a worldwide audience. But in agriculture, which is far more rooted in the soil and locale specific, it is only to be expected that a large part of the work will be published in national journals which will be easily accessible to other researchers in the country (or region), extension workers and the end users. Indian journals indexed in *CAB Abstracts* 1990-1994 are listed in Table 5. Forty-eight of the more than 480 Indian journals used have published at least 200 Indian papers in the five years, and 107 journals have published 100 or more Indian papers.

Use of foreign and national journals has remained a point of debate for a long time in India. While most Indian journals suffer from poor circulation and poor editing, indifferent peer review and low production values, there have been some efforts to bring out journals of quality. About 25 years ago, the Indian Academy of Sciences, Bangalore, consulted members of the Indian Physics Association and the Fellows of the Academy and took the decision to launch *Pramana*, the Academy's physics journal. I played an important role in this initiative and I also had the privilege of steering the journal in its early days as the journal's first executive editor. Subsequently, the Academy reorganised

its journals. More recently, Samiran Nundy and colleagues at the All India Institute of Medical Sciences launched the *National Medical Journal of India*. It must be remembered that publishing indigenous journals of quality is an essential component of any healthy scientific enterprise.

The Indian papers indexed in *CAB Abstracts* 1990-1994 are classified into subfields in Table 6. *CAB Abstracts* assigns more than one subclassification code to each paper, usually three or four. I have taken into account only the first of these. 'Pests, pathogens and plant diseases' is the subfield accounting for the largest number of papers from India. It is followed by 'Plant breeding and genetics' and 'Plant production'. In all, India has published in 250 subfields, with more than 500 papers in 16 subfields. At the other extreme, in 58 subfields Indian researchers have published less than 10 papers in the five years. These include History and biography (subfield BB500), eight papers; Aquaculture equipment (NN410), nine papers; Communication (UU360), four papers; and Documentation (CC310), two papers.

The number of papers contributed by different Indian institutions is given in Table 7. There are more than 3,300 addresses, including some residential addresses. Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana; Haryana Agricultural University, Hissar; and the Indian Agricultural Research Institute are the three most prolific publishing institutions. Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, is the only other institution to have published more than 1,000 papers in the five years. Most agriculture universities have laboratories/field centres in more than one location. For example, Punjab Agricultural University has its headquarters at Ludhiana, but papers are also published from eight other centres. In this table, each centre is listed. Not surprisingly, the top nine in the list are 'agricultural' universities (including institutions devoted to dairy and veterinary sciences). Banaras Hindu University and Aligarh Muslim Universities are the only two general universities (not exclusively devoted to agriculture and related fields such as horticulture) in the top 25 institutions listed in Table 7. Delhi University, which has excellent departments of botany and zoology, is ranked 26th.

Academic institutions -- universities and colleges -- are the leading performers of agricultural research and they account for about 63% of all papers from India. ICAR laboratories are responsible for about 11.3% of Indian publications (Table 8). The

contributions made by different states and cities/towns are given in Tables 9 and 10 respectively. Uttar Pradesh leads the states with over 8,300 publications, followed by Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Haryana and Karnataka. Delhi, Ludhiana, Hissar and Bangalore are the leading publishing cities. In all, papers have been published from about 830 cities/towns. Unlike institutions engaged in research in physics and materials science, institutions carrying out agricultural research are located in smaller towns and in remote locations. This is inevitable, as much of agricultural research is field based.

Discussion

This is essentially a macroscopic study, looking at agricultural research in India as a whole. I have used *CAB Abstracts* as the source of information. There are two other international databases, viz. *AGRIS* and *AGRICOLA*, which could have also been used. I chose *CAB Abstracts* for the following reasons. *AGRIS* depends entirely on national input centres for gathering information, and I found that, for reasons I will not go into here, the job was not being done well. *AGRICOLA* does not cover Indian work as comprehensively as *CAB Abstracts*. This study based on *CAB Abstracts* 1990-1994 shows that a substantial number of papers are being published by Indian agricultural scientists, and that a very large proportion of these papers are in the area of pests, pathogens and plant diseases; plant breeding and genetics; and plant production. There were only 231 papers in the area of "biotechnology", showing that India is slow in catching up in the rather important area of agriculture-oriented biotechnology. In the past two decades many schools of new biology have emerged, e.g. at the Indian Institute of Science, Madurai Kamaraj University and M S University of Baroda. Conscious efforts to bring scientists in these schools and centres of agricultural research to work together may prove profitable.

Meeting the domestic food requirements has been the foremost social priority before India since Independence. Importance was given to food production all along, especially in the sixties and thereafter. A clear policy framework coupled with sound planning and implementation backed by generous research and development investments ensured sustained production of foodgrains and other agricultural commodities, says Dr Paroda, Director General of the Indian Council of Agricultural Research. Foodgrain production rose from 51 million tonnes in 1950-51 to 191.09 million tonnes in 1994-95.

Even thirty years ago, India had to supplement internal production of foodgrains with imports. Today the country is able to export a variety of agricultural products including foodgrains. Says Mr M R Srinivasan,²⁰ Member of India's Planning Commission, that three factors were responsible for this transformation: (1) the steadfast application of science at the field level by scientists of the ICAR, which now has 46 central research institutes (including four national institutes) and 26 national research centres, and the 29 agricultural universities set up with the assistance of the ICAR. (2) The Indian farmers, for their part, readily accepted new varieties, adopted new farm practices and worked hard. (3) Imaginative political and administrative leadership in the sixties played a vital catalytic role.

The goals were clear. The political will and administrative support were there. And the scientists rose to the challenge under an able and visionary leader. And above all, the Indian farmer was not found wanting. Similar situations were to repeat subsequently in some of the projects of the Defence and Space Departments, and a technologist who had played a significant role in the successes of both these departments was honoured with the country's highest award, viz. Bharat Ratna.

A comparison of agricultural and medical research in India will be instructive. Both agriculture and medicine are, in a sense, extensions of applied biology. Both have had a hoary past in India, albeit in their traditional forms. However, while agricultural research in Independent India has by and large delivered the goods, medical research, I am afraid, has not. My own scientometric studies have shown that in terms of both the volume of work carried out and the relevance to the healthcare needs of the country medical research in India could do a lot better.^{1,21} Significantly, medical researchers, educators and editors such as Valiathan,^{3,22} Pandya,²³ Kartha²⁴ and Nundy,²⁵ with the insight of insiders, hold similar views. The inevitable question is: why have not the medical research establishment and the doctors in India achieved the same level of success as the agricultural establishment and the farmers?

It is necessary to point out that agricultural research can not rest on its laurels and be complacent. Newer challenges have emerged and they have to be met with visionary leadership, planning, goal setting, dedicated work in the lab and the field, innovative methods of extension and so on. It is an unending journey.

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TABLES

**Table 1: Indian research papers classified by
publication year as seen from *CAB Abstracts 1990 - 94***

Sl No.	Publication year	Number of papers
1	1982	2
2	1983	23
3	1984	43
4	1985	7
5	1986	215
6	1987	906
7	1988	4752
8	1989	9366
9	1990	10503
10	1991	9987
11	1992	8620
12	1993	5817
13	1994	1517
14	1995	3
	Total	51761

**Table 2: Indian research papers classified by
journals as seen from CAB Abstracts 1990 - 94
(Arranged by number of papers)**

SI No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
1	Indian-Veterinary-Journal	India	1336
2	Indian-Journal-of-Animal-Sciences	India	1287
3	Indian-Journal-of-Agricultural-Sciences	India	959
4	Indian-Journal-of-Agronomy	India	951
5	Indian-Phytopathology	India	831
6	Journal-of-the-Indian-Society-of-Soil-Science	India	784
7	Journal-of-Maharashtra-Agricultural-Universities	India	754
8	Madras-Agricultural-Journal	India	751
9	Indian-Forester	India	717
10	Indian-Journal-of-Dairy-Science	India	682
11	Environment-and-Ecology	India	604
12	Current-Science	India	580
13	South-Indian-Horticulture	India	491
14	Indian-Journal-of-Experimental-Biology	India	434
15	Indian-Journal-of-Entomology	India	429
16	Indian-Journal-of-Mycology-and-Plant-Pathology	India	415
17	Indian-Journal-of-Forestry	India	392
18	Indian-Journal-of-Genetics-and-Plant-Breeding	India	364
19	Annals-of-Agricultural-Research	India	361
20	Current-Research-University-of-Agricultural-Sciences	India	360
21	International-Rice-Research-Newsletter	Philippines	352
22	Indian-Journal-of-Plant-Physiology	India	349
23	Indian-Journal-of-Horticulture	India	320
24	Plant-Disease-Research	India	307
25	Indian-Journal-of-Animal-Nutrition	India	303
26	Indian-Journal-of-Nematology	India	290
27	Crop-Research-Hisar	India	287
28	Indian-Journal-of-Plant-Protection	India	281
29	Journal-of-Insect-Science	India	281
30	Fertiliser-News	India	268
31	Indian-Dairyman	India	264
32	Indian-Farming	India	262
33	Mysore-Journal-of-Agricultural-Science	India	242
34	Indian-Journal-of-Animal-Reproduction	India	241
35	National-Academy-of-Science-Letters	India	240
36	Oryza	India	236
37	Phytochemistry	UK	236
38	Haryana-Journal-of-Horticultural-Sciences	India	234
39	Advances-in-Plant-Sciences	India	231
40	Journal-of-Research,-Punjab-Agricultural-University	India	228

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
41	Indian-Journal-of-Weed-Science	India	225
42	Progressive-Horticulture	India	225
43	Entomon	India	224
44	Crop-Improvement	India	221
45	Indian-Journal-of-Poultry-Science	India	220
46	Agricultural-Situation-in-India	India	217
47	PKV-Research-Journal	India	214
48	Fitoterapia	Italy	212
49	Indian-Veterinary-Medical-Journal	India	203
50	Journal-of-Oilseeds-Research	India	202
51	Haryana-Journal-of-Agronomy	India	200
52	Karnataka-Journal-of-Agricultural-Sciences	India	194
53	Cheiron	India	192
54	Acta-Botanica-Indica	India	190
55	Agricultural-Science-Digest-Karnal	India	187
56	Orissa-Journal-of-Agricultural-Research	India	186
57	Cytologia	Japan	185
58	Annals-of-Plant-Physiology	India	183
59	Haryana-Agricultural-University-Journal-of-Research	India	176
60	Indian-Sugar	India	176
61	Journal-of-Entomological-Research	India	176
62	Livestock-Adviser	India	176
63	Acta-Horticulturae	Belgium	171
64	Indian-Agriculturist	India	171
65	Research-and-Development-Reporter	India	170
66	Indian-Journal-of-Pulses-Research	India	169
67	Vegetable-Science	India	169
68	Current-Nematology	India	167
69	International-Journal-of-Tropical-Agriculture	India	164
70	Indian-Journal-of-Agricultural-Economics	India	160
71	Indian-Journal-of-Medical-Research	India	159
72	Gujarat-Agricultural-University-Research-Journal	India	157
73	Indian-Perfumer	India	157
74	Van-Vigyan	India	156
75	Journal-of-Plantation-Crops	India	151
76	Legume-Research	India	150
77	Indian-Journal-of-Parasitology	India	145
78	Indian-Journal-of-Sericulture	India	144
79	Pesticides	India	144
80	Journal-of-Veterinary-Parasitology	India	143
81	Indian-Journal-of-Veterinary-Medicine	India	142
82	Journal-of-Nuclear-Agriculture-and-Biology	India	142
83	Proceedings-of-the-Indian-National-Science-Academy	India	142
84	Indian-Journal-of-Animal-Health	India	139
85	Indian-Journal-of-Animal-Production-and-Management	India	139

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
86	Indian-Journal-of-Helminthology	India	138
87	Indian-Cocoa,-Areca-nut-and-Spices-Journal	India	136
88	Journal-of-Potassium-Research	India	136
89	Indian-Journal-of-Virology	India	132
90	Revista-di-Parassitologia	Italy	132
91	Poultry-Advisor	India	131
92	Journal-of-Communicable-Diseases	India	130
93	Journal-of-Food-Science-and-Technology-Mysore	India	130
94	Plant-Protection-Bulletin-Faridabad	India	130
95	Bulletin-of-Entomology-New-Delhi	India	129
96	Indian-Journal-of-Plant-Pathology	India	127
97	International-Chickpea-Newsletter	India	126
98	New-Agriculturist	India	123
99	Pesticide-Research-Journal	India	122
100	Cooperative-Sugar	India	120
101	Journal-of-Research,-Andhra-Pradesh-Agricultural-University	India	120
102	Journal-of-the-Indian-Society-for-Cotton-Improvement	India	118
103	Journal-of-Rural-Development-Hyderabad	India	117
104	Indian-Journal-of-Agricultural-Research	India	116
105	Seed-Research	India	115
106	Annals-of-Arid-Zone	India	112
107	Indian-Journal-of-Malariaology	India	109
108	Bulletin-of-Environmental-Contamination-and-Toxicology	USA	107
109	Journal-of-Soils-and-Crops	India	106
110	Journal-of-Environmental-Biology	India	104
111	Indian-Bee-Journal	India	103
112	Narendra-Deva-Journal-of-Agricultural-Research	India	103
113	Uttar-Pradesh-Journal-of-Zoology	India	102
114	Myforest	India	100
115	Journal-of-Biological-Control	India	99
116	Indian-Pediatrics	India	98
117	Indian-Coconut-Journal-Cochin	India	97
118	Proceedings-of-the-Indian-Academy-of-Sciences,-Plant-Sciences	India	97
119	Himachal-Journal-of-Agricultural-Research	India	96
120	Journal-of-the-Indian-Potato-Association	India	96
121	Tropical-Pest-Management	UK	96
122	Bharatiya-Sugar	India	95
123	Bioved	India	95
124	SISSTA-Sugar-Journal	India	93
125	Tobacco-Research	India	91
126	International-Pigeonpea-Newsletter	India	90
127	International-Nematology-Network-Newsletter	USA	90
128	Tropical-Agriculture-Guildford	Trinidad & Tobago	90
129	Indian-Journal-of-Ecology	India	89
130	Journal-of-Root-Crops	India	89

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
131	Indian-Journal-of-Hill-Farming	India	88
132	Proceedings-of-the-Indian-Academy-of-Sciences,-Animal-Sciences	India	88
133	Phytomorphology	India	87
134	Indian-Cooperative-Review	India	86
135	Journal-of-Coffee-Research	India	86
136	Plant-Physiology-and-Biochemistry-New-Delhi	India	86
137	Journal-of-the-Timber-Development-Association-of-India	India	85
138	Asian-Journal-of-Dairy-Research	India	84
139	Plant-Cell-Reports	Germany	83
140	Indian-Journal-of-Agricultural-Marketing	India	83
141	Indian-Journal-of-Animal-Research	India	82
142	Insect-Science-and-its-Application	Kenya	82
143	Agricultural-Research-Journal-of-Kerala	India	81
144	Journal-of-the-Andaman-Science-Association	India	81
145	Journal-of-Mycopathological-Research	India	80
146	Journal-of-Research,-Birsa-Agricultural-University	India	80
147	Annals-of-Biology-Ludhiana	India	79
148	Annals-of-Entomology	India	79
149	Indian-Journal-of-Nutrition-and-Dietetics	India	79
150	Euphytica	Netherlands	79
151	Bharatiya-Krishi-Anusandhana-Patrika	India	78
152	Indian-Journal-of-Applied-and-Pure-Biology	India	78
153	Journal-of-Tropical-Forestry	India	78
154	Farming-Systems	India	77
155	Indian-Journal-of-Microbiology	India	77
156	International-Journal-of-Tropical-Plant-Diseases	India	77
157	Pestology	India	77
158	Photosynthetica	Czech Republic	76
159	Journal-of-Agronomy-and-Crop-Science	Germany	76
160	Nematologia-Mediterranea	Italy	76
161	Economic-Affairs-Calcutta	India	74
162	Medical-Science-Research	UK	73
163	Indian-Journal-of-Pharmaceutical-Sciences	India	71
164	Two-and-a-Bud	India	71
165	Horticultural-Journal	India	69
166	Tropical-Ecology	India	69
167	Farm-Science-Journal	India	68
168	Indian-Botanical-Reporter	India	68
169	International-Rice-Research-Notes	Philippines	67
170	Buffalo-Journal	Thailand	67
171	Indian-Journal-of-Biochemistry-and-Biophysics	India	66
172	Plant-Cell,-Tissue-and-Organ-Culture	Netherlands	66
173	International-Journal-of-Animal-Sciences	India	65
174	Journal-of-the-Indian-Academy-of-Wood-Science	India	64
175	Research-Bulletin-of-the-Punjab-University	India	64

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
176	Comparative-Physiology-and-Ecology	India	63
177	Agricultural-Reviews-Karnal	India	62
178	Groundnut-News	India	62
179	Indian-Horticulture	India	62
180	Seeds-and-Farms	India	62
181	Journal-of-Advanced-Zoology	India	61
182	Journal-of-Aphidology	India	61
183	Journal-of-the-Oil-Technologists'-Association-of-India	India	61
184	World-Journal-of-Microbiology-and-Biotechnology	UK	61
185	Biochemistry-International	Australia	60
186	Range-Management-and-Agroforestry	India	60
187	Biovigyanam	India	59
188	Indian-Journal-of-Comparative-Microbiology,-Immunology-and-Infectious-Diseases	India	59
189	Journal-of-Ethnopharmacology	Ireland	59
190	Journal-of-the-Science-of-Food-and-Agriculture	UK	59
191	Journal-of-Phytological-Research	India	57
192	Journal-of-the-Bombay-Natural-History-Society	India	57
193	Plant-Science-Limerick	Ireland	57
194	Mycopathologia	Netherlands	57
195	Biology-and-Fertility-of-Soils	Germany	55
196	Seed-Science-and-Technology	Switzerland	55
197	Fertilizer-Research	Netherlands	54
198	Agricultural-Marketing	India	53
199	Journal-of-Plant-Physiology	Germany	51
200	Current-Agriculture	India	51
201	Punjab-Horticultural-Journal	India	51
202	Agricultural-Mechanization-in-Asia,-Africa-and-Latin-America	Japan	51
203	International-Journal-of-Pharmacognosy	Netherlands	51
204	Leucaena-Research-Reports	Taiwan	51
205	Indian-Journal-of-Veterinary-Pathology	India	50
206	Bioresource-Technology	UK	50
207	Theoretical-and-Applied-Genetics	Germany	49
208	Capsicum-Newsletter	Italy	49
209	Plant-and-Soil	Netherlands	49
210	International-Journal-of-Remote-Sensing	UK	49
211	Sugar-Cane	UK	48
212	Journal-of-Natural-Products	USA	48
213	Journal-of-Biosciences	India	47
214	Orissa-Journal-of-Horticulture	India	47
215	Indian-Journal-of-Agricultural-Engineering	India	46
216	Cruciferae-Newsletter	UK	46
217	Maize-Genetics-Cooperation-News-Letter	USA	46
218	Indian-Journal-of-Medical-Research.-Section-A,-Infectious-Diseases	India	45
219	International-Arachis-Newsletter	India	45
220	Wheat-Information-Service	Japan	45

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
221	Plant-Foods-for-Human-Nutrition	Netherlands	44
222	Annals-of-Applied-Biology	UK	44
223	Journal-of-Veterinary-and-Animal-Sciences	India	43
224	Journal-of-Genetics-and-Breeding	Italy	43
225	Agroforestry-Systems	Netherlands	43
226	Food-Chemistry	UK	43
227	Plant-Pathology-Newsletter	UK	43
228	Journal-of-Agriculture-and-Food-Chemistry	USA	43
229	Indian-Journal-of-Natural-Rubber-Research	India	42
230	Journal-of-Ecobiology	India	42
231	Nucleus-Calcutta	India	42
232	Annals-of-Botany	UK	42
233	Arid-Soil-Research-and-Rehabilitation	UK	42
234	Journal-of-the-Orchid-Society-of-India	India	41
235	Zentralblatt-fur-Mikrobiologie	Germany	40
236	Social-Change-New-Delhi	India	40
237	Journal-of-Agricultural-Science	UK	40
238	Crop-Science	USA	40
239	Plant-Breeding	Germany	39
240	Journal-of-Ecotoxicology-and-Environmental-Monitoring	India	39
241	NBSS-Publication	India	39
242	Enzyme-and-Microbial-Technology	USA	39
243	Journal-of-Essential-Oil-Research	USA	39
244	Annals-of-Plant-Protection-Sciences	India	38
245	International-Journal-of-Ecology-and-Environmental-Sciences	India	38
246	Plant-Cell-Incompatibility-Newsletter	USA	38
247	Zeitschrift-fur-Pflanzenkrankheiten-und-Pflanzenschutz	Germany	37
248	Centaur-Mylapore	India	36
249	Geobios-New-Reports	India	36
250	Journal-of-Aquaculture-in-the-Tropics	India	36
251	Phytotherapy-Research	UK	36
252	Advances-in-horticulture:-fruit-crops	India	35
253	Clay-Research	India	35
254	Mycological-Research	UK	35
255	Bihar-Journal-of-Agricultural-Marketing	India	34
256	Experimental-Genetics	India	34
257	Proceedings-of-the-Indian-National-Science-Academy.-Part-B.-Biological-Sciences	India	34
258	Rubber-Board-Bulletin	India	34
259	Small-Ruminant-Research	Netherlands	34
260	Veterinary-Parasitology	Netherlands	34
261	Theriogenology	USA	34
262	Indian-Coffee	India	33
263	Indian-Journal-of-Public-Health	India	33
264	Pashudhan	India	33

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
265	Biotechnology-Letters	UK	33
266	Environmental-Pollution	UK	33
267	Soil-Biology-and-Biochemistry	UK	33
268	Oriental-Insects	USA	33
269	Virus-Information-Exchange-Newsletter-for-South-East-Asia-and-the-Western-Pacific	Australia	32
270	Journal-of-Bengal-Natural-History-Society	India	32
271	Journal-of-the-Indian-Society-of-Coastal-Agricultural-Research	India	32
272	Nitrogen-Fixing-Tree-Research-Reports	Thailand	32
273	Biological-Wastes	UK	32
274	Tropical-Science	UK	32
275	Nutrition-Research	USA	32
276	Journal-of-Dairying,-Foods-and-Home-Sciences	India	31
277	Oleagineux-Paris	France	30
278	Indian-Journal-of-Environmental-Health	India	30
279	Journal-of-Spices-and-Aromatic-Crops	India	30
280	Pesticide-Science	UK	30
281	Veterinary-Record	UK	30
282	Biochemie-und-Physiologie-der-Pflanzen	Germany	29
283	Indian-Journal-of-Regional-Science	India	29
284	Lens	Ireland	29
285	Pakistan-Journal-of-Nematology	Pakistan	29
286	Asian-Environment	Philippines	29
287	Mutation-Breeding-Newsletter	Austria	28
288	Feddes-Repertorium	Germany	28
289	Mycoses	Germany	28
290	Planta-Medica	Germany	28
291	Indian-Journal-of-Indigenous-Medicines	India	28
292	Indian-Review-of-Life-Sciences	India	28
293	Vaniki-Sandesh	India	28
294	Journal-of-Tropical-Forest-Science	Malaysia	28
295	Animal-Feed-Science-and-Technology	Netherlands	28
296	FEMS-Microbiology-Letters	Netherlands	28
297	Journal-of-Environmental-Science-and-Health	USA	28
298	Journal-of-Irrigation-and-Drainage-Engineering	USA	28
299	Acta-Agronomica-Hungarica	Hungary	27
300	Cereal-Research-Communications	Hungary	27
301	Advances-in-management-and-conservation-of-soil-fauna	India	27
302	Agricultural-Engineering-Today	India	27
303	Indian-Journal-of-Helminthology-New-Series	India	27
304	Indian-Journal-of-Mycological-Research	India	27
305	Journal-of-Research-Assam-Agricultural-University	India	27
306	Journal-of-the-Assam-Science-Society	India	27
307	Journal-of-the-Assam-Veterinary-Council	India	27
308	Jute-Development-Journal	India	27
309	Maharashtra-Journal-of-Horticulture	India	27

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
310	Agricultural-Water-Management	Netherlands	27
311	Letters-in-Applied-Microbiology	UK	27
312	Biochemical-and-Biophysical-Research-Communications	USA	27
313	Fluoride	USA	27
314	Hindustan-Antibiotics-Bulletin	India	26
315	Journal-of-Agricultural-Engineering	India	26
316	Field-Crops-Research	Netherlands	26
317	Journal-of-Horticultural-Science	UK	26
318	Ecotoxicology-and-Environmental-Safety	USA	26
319	Folia-Microbiologica	Czech Republic	25
320	Microbiologie,-Aliments,-Nutrition	France	25
321	Plant-Physiology-and-Biochemistry(France)	France	25
322	Annals-of-Forestry	India	25
323	Journal-of-Scientific-and-Industrial-Research	India	25
324	Journal-of-Veterinary-Physiology-and-Allied-Sciences	India	25
325	Wool-and-Woolfens-of-India	India	25
326	Agrochimica	Italy	25
327	Aquaculture	Netherlands	25
328	International-Journal-of-Crude-Drug-Research	Netherlands	25
329	Journal-of-Tree-Sciences	India	24
330	Phytophaga	India	24
331	Acta-Parasitologica-Polonica	Poland	24
332	Buffalo-Bulletin	Thailand	24
333	International-Journal-for-Parasitology	UK	24
334	Current-Microbiology	USA	24
335	Afro-Asian-Journal-of-Nematology	India	23
336	Indian-Journal-of-Dryland-Agricultural-Research-and-Development	India	23
337	FAO-Plant-Protection-Bulletin	Italy	23
338	Plant-Genetic-Resources-Newsletter	Italy	23
339	Nematologica	Netherlands	23
340	Scientia-Horticulturae	Netherlands	23
341	Analyst	UK	23
342	Crop-Protection	UK	23
343	Experimental-Agriculture	UK	23
344	International-Journal-of-Environmental-Studies	UK	23
345	Plant-Disease	USA	23
346	Beitrage-zur-Tropischen-Landwirtschaft-und-Veterinarmedizin	Germany	22
347	Evergreen-Trichur	India	22
348	Indian-Geographical-Journal	India	22
349	Journal-of-Genetics	India	22
350	Veterinary-Research-Communications	Netherlands	22
351	Nutrition-Reports-International	USA	22
352	Applied-Microbiology-and-Biotechnology	Germany	21
353	Biometrical-Journal	Germany	21
354	Journal-of-Applied-Entomology	Germany	21

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
355	Cashew-Bulletin	India	21
356	National-Bank-News-Review-Bombay	India	21
357	Forest-Ecology-and-Management	Netherlands	21
358	Acta-Cytologica	USA	21
359	Soil-Science	USA	21
360	Biologia-Plantarum	Czech Republic	20
361	Journal-of-Applied-Rabbit-Research	France	20
362	Acta-Veterinaria-Hungarica	Hungary	20
363	Fertiliser-Marketing-News	India	20
364	Rachis	Syria	20
365	Journal-of-Arid-Environments	UK	20
366	Journal-of-Stored-Products-Research	UK	20
367	Economic-Botany	USA	20
368	Entomophaga	France	19
369	Gartenbauwissenschaft	Germany	19
370	Indian-Journal-of-Agricultural-Chemistry	India	19
371	Journal-of-Bombay-Veterinary-College	India	19
372	Journal-of-Microbial-Biotechnology	India	19
373	Journal-of-Rural-Reconstruction	India	19
374	Transactions-of-Indian-Society-of-Desert-Technology	India	19
375	Helminthologia	Slovakia	19
376	FABIS-Newsletter	Syria	19
377	Journal-of-Experimental-Botany	UK	19
378	Plant-Pathology	UK	19
379	Tests-of-Agrochemicals-and-Cultivars	UK	19
380	Transactions-of-the-Royal-Society-of-Tropical-Medicine-and-Hygiene	UK	19
381	Cultured-Dairy-Products-Journal	USA	19
382	Journal-of-Plant-Nutrition	USA	19
383	Journal-of-the-American-Oil-Chemists'-Society	USA	19
384	Mycotaxon	USA	19
385	Veterinary-and-Human-Toxicology	USA	19
386	Fundamental-and-Applied-Nematology	France	18
387	Kerala-Journal-of-Veterinary-Science	India	18
388	Agriculture,-Ecosystems-and-Environment	Netherlands	18
389	Journal-of-Hydrology-Amsterdam	Netherlands	18
390	Plant-Physiology	USA	18
391	Soybean-Genetics-Newsletter	USA	18
392	Genome	Canada	17
393	Physiologia-Plantarum	Denmark	17
394	Nahrung	Germany	17
395	Zoologische-Jahrbucher,-Abteilung-fur-Allgemeine-Zoologie-und-Physiologie-der-Tiere	Germany	17
396	Journal-of-Research-Rajendra-Agricultural-University	India	17
397	Journal-of-the-Indian-Medical-Association	India	17
398	Mushroom-Research	India	17

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
399	New-Botanist	India	17
400	Cereal-Rusts-and-Powdery-Mildews-Bulletin	Netherlands	17
401	Biological-Agriculture-and-Horticulture	UK	17
402	International-Sugar-Journal	UK	17
403	International-Tree-Crops-Journal	UK	17
404	Journal-of-Helminthology	UK	17
405	Pesticide-Biochemistry-and-Physiology	USA	17
406	Journal-of-Phytopathology	Germany	16
407	Agropedology	India	16
408	Indian-Drugs	India	16
409	Indian-Journal-of-Marine-Sciences	India	16
410	Indian-Standard	India	16
411	JNKVV-Research-Journal	India	16
412	Mausam	India	16
413	Moving-Technology	India	16
414	Newsletter-Associated-Agricultural-Development-Foundation	India	16
415	Journal-of-General-and-Applied-Microbiology	Japan	16
416	Animal-Reproduction-Science	Netherlands	16
417	Soil-and-Tillage-Research	Netherlands	16
418	Acta-Protozoologica	Poland	16
419	International-Journal-of-Pest-Management	UK	16
420	Process-Biochemistry	UK	16
421	Research-in-Veterinary-Science	UK	16
422	Biochemistry-and-Molecular-Biology-International	Australia	15
423	Canadian-Journal-of-Botany	Canada	15
424	Zeitschrift-fur-Angewandte-Zoologie	Germany	15
425	Advances-in-Forestry-Research-in-India	India	15
426	Advances-in-Himalayan-ecology	India	15
427	Indian-Textile-Journal	India	15
428	Proceedings-of-the-Nutrition-Society-of-India	India	15
429	Social-Action-New-Delhi	India	15
430	Plant-Growth-Regulation	Netherlands	15
431	Annals-of-Nutrition-and-Metabolism	Switzerland	15
432	Cytobios	UK	15
433	European-Journal-of-Clinical-Nutrition	UK	15
434	Water-Research-Oxford	UK	15
435	Special-Publication-International-Fertilizer-Development-Center	USA	15
436	Australian-Journal-of-Dairy-Technology	Australia	14
437	Archiv-fur-Experimentelle-Veterinarmedizin	Germany	14
438	Beitrage-zur-Biologie-der-Pflanzen	Germany	14
439	Annals-of-the-National-Association-of-Geographers	India	14
440	Chemical-Engineering-World	India	14
441	KFRI-Research-Report	India	14
442	Plant-Material-Description	India	14
443	Poultry-Today-and-Tomorrow	India	14

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
444	Food-and-Nutrition-Bulletin	Japan	14
445	Agroforestry-Today	Kenya	14
446	Sorghum-Newsletter	South Africa	14
447	Ambio	Sweden	14
448	Experientia	Switzerland	14
449	Energy-Conversion-and-Management	UK	14
450	Biomedical-and-Environmental-Sciences	USA	14
451	Communications-in-Soil-Science-and-Plant-Analysis	USA	14
452	Journal-of-Chemical-Ecology	USA	14
453	Folia-Parasitologica	Czechoslovakia	13
454	Apidologie	France	13
455	European-Journal-of-Forest-Pathology	Germany	13
456	Indian-Journal-of-Veterinary-Anatomy	India	13
457	Journal-of-the-Indian-Institute-of-Science	India	13
458	Phytoparasitica	Israel	13
459	Journal-of-Fermentation-and-Bioengineering	Japan	13
460	Journal-of-Japanese-Botany	Japan	13
461	Pyrethrum-Post	Kenya	13
462	RIC-Bulletin	Malaysia	13
463	Veterinary-Immunology-and-Immunopathology	Netherlands	13
464	Veterinary-Microbiology	Netherlands	13
465	Proceedings-of-Parasitology	Pakistan	13
466	British-Veterinary-Journal	UK	13
467	International-Journal-of-Food-Science-and-Technology	UK	13
468	Journal-of-Toxicology,-Toxin-Reviews	USA	13
469	Acta-Veterinaria-Beograd	Yugoslavia	13
470	Egyptian-Journal-of-Dairy-Science	Egypt	12
471	Silvae-Genetica	Germany	12
472	Financing-Agriculture	India	12
473	Gujvet	India	12
474	Indian-Journal-of-Dermatology	India	12
475	Tropical-Biomedicine	Malaysia	12
476	Science-of-the-Total-Environment	Netherlands	12
477	British-Poultry-Science	UK	12
478	International-Journal-of-Food-Science-and-Nutrition	UK	12
479	International-Journal-of-Water-Resources-Development	UK	12
480	International-Pest-Control	UK	12
481	Journal-of-Apicultural-Research	UK	12
482	Lancet-British-edition	UK	12
483	Tropical-Animal-Health-and-Production	UK	12
484	Journal-of-Food-Science	USA	12
485	Journal-of-Invertebrate-Pathology	USA	12
486	Journal-of-the-American-Mosquito-Control-Association	USA	12
487	Canadian-Journal-of-Microbiology	Canada	11
488	Annals-of-Agricultural-Science-Cairo	Egypt	11
489	Mitteilungen-aus-dem-Zoologischen-Museum-in-Berlin	Germany	11

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
490	Bulletin-United-Planters'-Association-of-Southern-India	India	11
491	Indian-Journal-of-Landscape-Systems-and-Ecological-Studies	India	11
492	Journal-of-Applied-Animal-Research	India	11
493	Journal-of-Association-of-Physicians-of-India	India	11
494	Journal-of-the-Maharashtra-Agricultural-Universities	India	11
495	Kavaka	India	11
496	Sharkara-Kanpur	India	11
497	Japanese-Journal-of-Dairy-and-Food-Science	Japan	11
498	Journal-of-Veterinary-Medicine	Japan	11
499	Korean-Journal-of-Apiculture	Korea	11
500	Planter	Malaysia	11
501	Acta-Tropica	Netherlands	11
502	Entomologia-Experimentalis-et-Applicata	Netherlands	11
503	Genetica	Netherlands	11
504	Photosynthesis-Research	Netherlands	11
505	Acta-Physiologiae-Plantarum	Poland	11
506	Environmental-Conservation	Switzerland	11
507	International-Journal-for-Vitamin-and-Nutrition-Research	Switzerland	11
508	Comparative-Immunology,-Microbiology-and-Infectious-Diseases	UK	11
509	Hydrological-Sciences-Journal	UK	11
510	International-Journal-of-Environmental-Analytical-Chemistry	UK	11
511	Journal-of-Tropical-Pediatrics	UK	11
512	Report-Cucurbit-Genetics-Cooperative	USA	11
513	Acta-Entomologica-Bohemoslovaca	Czechoslovakia	10
514	Acta-Veterinaria-Brno	Czechoslovakia	10
515	Biologisches-Zentralblatt	Germany	10
516	Fresenius'-Journal-of-Analytical-Chemistry	Germany	10
517	Zoologischer-Anzeiger	Germany	10
518	Asian-Profile	Hong Kong	10
519	Afro-Asian-Nematology-Network	India	10
520	Cecidologia-Internationale	India	10
521	Indian-Journal-of-Economics	India	10
522	Indian-Journal-of-Environmental-Protection	India	10
523	Indian-Journal-of-Mushrooms	India	10
524	Indian-Journal-of-Veterinary-Surgery	India	10
525	Orissa-Veterinary-Journal	India	10
526	Planters'-Chronicle	India	10
527	State-Bank-of-India-Monthly-Review	India	10
528	VET-Mhow	India	10
529	World-Review-of-Animal-Production	Italy	10
530	Mutation-Research,-Genetic-Toxicology-Testing	Netherlands	10
531	Water,-Air,-and-Soil-Pollution	Netherlands	10
532	Botanical-Bulletin-of-Academia-Sinica	Taiwan	10

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533	Southeast-Asian-Journal-of-Tropical-Medicine-and-Public-Health	Thailand	10
534	Agricultural-Systems	UK	10
535	Aquaculture-and-Fisheries-Management	UK	10
536	Biochemical-Pharmacology	UK	10
537	Food-and-Chemical-Toxicology	UK	10
538	Nutrition-Burbank	UK	10
539	Water-Science-and-Technology	UK	10
540	Biotechnology-and-Bioengineering	USA	10
541	Plant-Systematics-and-Evolution	Austria	9
542	Naturalia-Sao-Paulo	Brazil	9
543	Revue-de-Nematologie	France	9
544	Acta-Hydrochimica-et-Hydrobiologica	Germany	9
545	Milchwissenschaft	Germany	9
546	Pharmazie	Germany	9
547	Herba-Hungarica	Hungary	9
548	Artha-Vijnana	India	9
549	Haryana-Veterinarian	India	9
550	Indian-Economic-Review	India	9
551	Indian-Journal-of-Labour-Economics	India	9
552	Journal-of-Parasitology-and-Applied-Animal-Biology	India	9
553	Journal-of-the-Agricultural-Science-Society-of-North-East-India	India	9
554	Journal-of-the-Indian-School-of-Political-Economy	India	9
555	Journal-of-the-National-Botanical-Society	India	9
556	Margin	India	9
557	Caryologia	Italy	9
558	Plant-and-Cell-Physiology	Japan	9
559	Journal-of-Chromatography	Netherlands	9
560	Potato-Research	Netherlands	9
561	Toxicology-Letters	Netherlands	9
562	Tropical-and-Geographical-Medicine	Netherlands	9
563	Vegetatio	Netherlands	9
564	Acta-Paediatrica-Scandinavica	Norway	9
565	Pakistan-Journal-of-Zoology	Pakistan	9
566	Philippine-Journal-of-Science	Philippines	9
567	Acta-Virologica	Slovakia	9
568	Biotechnology-and-Applied-Biochemistry	UK	9
569	British-Journal-of-Nutrition	UK	9
570	Chemosphere	UK	9
571	Ecology-of-Food-and-Nutrition	UK	9
572	Environmental-and-Experimental-Botany	UK	9
573	Journal-of-Applied-Bacteriology	UK	9
574	Lebensmittel-Wissenschaft-and-Technologie	UK	9
575	Microbios-Letters	UK	9
576	MIRCEN-Journal-of-Applied-Microbiology-and-Biotechnology	UK	9

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
577	Outlook-on-Agriculture	UK	9
578	Talanta-Oxford	UK	9
579	Agronomy-Journal	USA	9
580	Journal-of-Nutritional-Biochemistry	USA	9
581	Mosquito-Systematics	USA	9
582	Nutrition-and-Cancer	USA	9
583	European-Archives-of-Biology	Belgium	8
584	Beitrag-zur-Entomologie	Germany	8
585	Cryptogamic-Botany	Germany	8
586	International-Journal-of-Biometeorology	Germany	8
587	Journal-of-Basic-Microbiology	Germany	8
588	Mycotoxin-Research	Germany	8
589	Advances-in-Forestry-Research-in-India,-Volume-V	India	8
590	Biology-Education	India	8
591	Indian-Journal-of-Medical-Research.-Section-B,-Biomedical-Research-other-than-Infectious-Diseases	India	8
592	Journal-of-Ravishankar-University	India	8
593	Journal-of-Social-Research-Ranchi	India	8
594	Journal-of-the-Marine-Biological-Association-of-India	India	8
595	Magazine,-College-of-Agriculture	India	8
596	Science-and-Culture	India	8
597	Zoology,-Journal-of-Pure-and-Applied-Zoology	India	8
598	Toxicology	Ireland	8
599	Japanese-Journal-of-Parasitology	Japan	8
600	FEBS-Letters	Netherlands	8
601	Geoderma	Netherlands	8
602	IBPGR-Newsletter-for-Asia,-the-Pacific-and-Oceania	Netherlands	8
603	Journal-of-Development-Economics	Netherlands	8
604	Grana	Sweden	8
605	Quarterly-Newsletter-Asia-and-Pacific-Plant-Protection-Commission	Thailand	8
606	Energy-Oxford	UK	8
607	Food-Additives-and-Contaminants	UK	8
608	International-Biodeterioration	UK	8
609	Journal-of-Medical-and-Veterinary-Mycology	UK	8
610	Parasitology	UK	8
611	Vaccine	UK	8
612	Applied-Biochemistry-and-Biotechnology	USA	8
613	Biological-Trace-Element-Research	USA	8
614	Journal-of-Geotechnical-Engineering	USA	8
615	Toxicological-and-Environmental-Chemistry	USA	8
616	Genetika-Beograd	Yugoslavia	8
617	Canadian-Journal-of-Forest-Research	Canada	7
618	International-Journal-of-Dermatology	Canada	7
619	Veterinarski-Arhiv	Croatia	7
620	Acta-Ophthalmologica	Denmark	7

SI No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
621	Lait-Lyon	France	7
622	Irrigation-Science	Germany	7
623	Pedobiologia	Germany	7
624	Acta-Phytopathologica-et-Entomologica-Hungarica	Hungary	7
625	Allelopathy-Journal	India	7
626	Conserving-Indian-environment	India	7
627	Cotton-Development	India	7
628	Current-Research-Reporter,-Mahatma-Phule-Agricultural-University	India	7
629	ICID-Bulletin	India	7
630	Indian-Cashew-Journal	India	7
631	Indian-Journal-of-Heredity	India	7
632	IPPTA	India	7
633	Journal-of-Economic-and-Taxonomic-Botany	India	7
634	Neo-Botanica	India	7
635	Plant-Breeding-News-Letter	India	7
636	Sugarcane-Breeding-Institute-News-Letter	India	7
637	Giornale-Italiano-di-Entomologia	Italy	7
638	Agricultural-and-Forest-Meteorology	Netherlands	7
639	Plant-Molecular-Biology	Netherlands	7
640	Systematic-Parasitology	Netherlands	7
641	Pakistan-Journal-of-Scientific-and-Industrial-Research	Pakistan	7
642	Polish-Journal-of-Soil-Science	Poland	7
643	Helia	Romania	7
644	Fagopyrum	Slovenia	7
645	Fresenius-Environmental-Bulletin	Switzerland	7
646	Journal-of-Radioanalytical-and-Nuclear-Chemistry,-Letters	Switzerland	7
647	Mosquito-Borne-Diseases-Bulletin	Thailand	7
648	Journal-of-Turkish-Phytopathology	Turkey	7
649	Atmospheric-Environment	UK	7
650	Biotechnology-Techniques	UK	7
651	Flavour-and-Fragrance-Journal	UK	7
652	Journal-of-Applied-Toxicology	UK	7
653	Journal-of-Tropical-Medicine-and-Hygiene	UK	7
654	Medical-and-Veterinary-Entomology	UK	7
655	Nucleic-Acids-Research	UK	7
656	Onion-Newsletter-for-the-Tropics	UK	7
657	Postgraduate-Medical-Journal	UK	7
658	Soil-Use-and-Management	UK	7
659	American-Journal-of-Gastroenterology	USA	7
660	Applied-and-Environmental-Microbiology	USA	7
661	Biochemical-Archives	USA	7
662	Biochemical-Genetics	USA	7
663	Biotechnic-and-Histochemistry	USA	7
664	Cereal-Chemistry	USA	7
665	Environmental-Geology-and-Water-Sciences	USA	7

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
666	Journal-of-Food-Composition-and-Analysis	USA	7
667	Journal-of-Heredity	USA	7
668	Journal-of-Nematology	USA	7
669	Lipids	USA	7
670	Transactions-of-the-ASAE	USA	7
671	Australian-Journal-of-Plant-Physiology	Australia	6
672	Bacterial-Wilt-Newsletter	Australia	6
673	Journal-of-Diarrhoeal-Diseases-Research	Bangladesh	6
674	Archives-Internationales-de-Physiologie-et-de-Biochimie	Belgium	6
675	World-Leisure-and-Recreation	Canada	6
676	Boletin-Chileno-de-Parasitologia	Chile	6
677	Nordic-Journal-of-Botany	Denmark	6
678	Acarologia	France	6
679	Coton-et-Fibres-Tropicales	France	6
680	Archiv-fur-Hydrobiologie	Germany	6
681	Bioprocess-Engineering	Germany	6
682	International-Journal-of-Mycology-and-Lichenology	Germany	6
683	Acta-Physiologica-Hungarica	Hungary	6
684	Calcutta-Medical-Journal	India	6
685	Changing-Villages	India	6
686	Indian-Food-Industry	India	6
687	Indian-Journal-of-Veterinary-Research	India	6
688	Journal-of-Animal-Morphology-and-Physiology	India	6
689	Journal-of-Extension-Systems	India	6
690	Journal-of-Research-and-Education-in-Indian-Medicine	India	6
691	Man-in-India	India	6
692	National-Medical-Journal-of-India	India	6
693	Newsletter-Central-Sericultural-Research-and-Training-Institute,-Mysore	India	6
694	Newsletter-Sugarcane-Breeding-Institute	India	6
695	Proceedings-of-the-Indian-National-Science-Academy,-Part-B,-Biological-Sciences	India	6
696	Proceedings-of-the-National-Academy-of-Sciences,-India	India	6
697	SARAS-Journal-of-Livestock-and-Poultry-Production	India	6
698	South-Asian-Anthropologist	India	6
699	Sustainable-development-of-the-Indian-arid-zone:-a-research-perspective	India	6
700	Invertebrate-Reproduction-and-Development	Israel	6
701	Maydica	Italy	6
702	Analytica-Chimica-Acta	Netherlands	6
703	Molecular-and-Cellular-Biochemistry	Netherlands	6
704	Resources,-Conservation-and-Recycling	Netherlands	6
705	Revista-Iberoamericana-de-Micologia	Spain	6
706	Animal-Production	UK	6
707	Annals-of-Tropical-Medicine-and-Parasitology	UK	6
708	Biomass-and-Bioenergy	UK	6
709	Commonwealth-Forestry-Review	UK	6

SI No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
710	Epidemiology-and-Infection	UK	6
711	International-Journal-of-Insect-Morphology-and-Embryology	UK	6
712	Journal-of-Agricultural-Engineering-Research	UK	6
713	Journal-of-General-Microbiology	UK	6
714	Journal-of-Laryngology-and-Otology	UK	6
715	Journal-of-Medical-Microbiology	UK	6
716	Medical-and-veterinary-dipterology	UK	6
717	Plant-Breeding-Abstracts	UK	6
718	Archives-of-Biochemistry-and-Biophysics	USA	6
719	Biochemical-Medicine-and-Metabolic-Biology	USA	6
720	General-and-Comparative-Endocrinology	USA	6
721	HortScience	USA	6
722	Journal-of-Biological-Chemistry	USA	6
723	Journal-of-Economic-Entomology	USA	6
724	Journal-of-Environmental-Engineering-New-York	USA	6
725	Journal-of-Medical-and-Applied-Malacology	USA	6
726	Journal-of-Parasitology	USA	6
727	Journal-of-Pediatric-Gastroenterology-and-Nutrition	USA	6
728	Journal-of-Protozoology	USA	6
729	Journal-of-the-Lepidopterists'-Society	USA	6
730	Molecular-Reproduction-and-Development	USA	6
731	Peanut-Science	USA	6
732	Australian-Journal-of-Soil-Research	Australia	5
733	Phyton-Horn	Austria	5
734	Bangladesh-Journal-of-Agricultural-Research	Bangladesh	5
735	Bangladesh-Journal-of-Zoology	Bangladesh	5
736	Plasticulture	France	5
737	Revue-d'Ecologie-et-de-Biologie-du-Sol	France	5
738	Angewandte-Parasitologie	Germany	5
739	Archives-of-Microbiology	Germany	5
740	Fett-Wissenschaft-Technologie	Germany	5
741	Holzforschung	Germany	5
742	Material-und-Organismen	Germany	5
743	Mycorrhiza	Germany	5
744	Pediatric-Surgery-International	Germany	5
745	Starch-Starke	Germany	5
746	Trace-Elements-in-Medicine	Germany	5
747	VITIS	Germany	5
748	Allelopathy;-basic-and-applied-aspects	India	5
749	Anvesak	India	5
750	Chemical-Age-of-India	India	5
751	CIMAP-Newsletter	India	5
752	Indian-Journal-of-Public-Administration	India	5
753	Indian-Journal-of-Rubber-Research	India	5
754	Indian-Journal-of-Technology	India	5
755	Journal-of-Living-World	India	5

SI No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
756	Journal-of-the-Indian-Chemical-Society	India	5
757	Working-Paper -Indian-Institute-of-Management,-Ahmedabad	India	5
758	Cancer-Letters	Ireland	5
759	Israeli-Journal-of-Aquaculture	Israel	5
760	Animal-Genetic-Resources-Information	Italy	5
761	Japanese-Journal-of-Medical-Science-and-Biology	Japan	5
762	Journal-of-Nutritional-Science-and-Vitaminology	Japan	5
763	Journal-of-Pesticide-Science	Japan	5
764	Soil-Science-and-Plant-Nutrition	Japan	5
765	Antonie-van-Leeuwenhoek	Netherlands	5
766	Carbohydrate-Research	Netherlands	5
767	International-Journal-of-Mineral-Processing	Netherlands	5
768	Journal-of-Biotechnology	Netherlands	5
769	Journal-of-Controlled-Release	Netherlands	5
770	Soil-Technology	Netherlands	5
771	Acta-Microbiologica-Polonica	Poland	5
772	Chemia-Analityczna	Poland	5
773	Archiva-Veterinaria-Bucuresti	Romania	5
774	Sri-Lanka-Journal-of-Tea-Science	Sri Lanka	5
775	Asian-Pacific-Journal-of-Allergy-and-Immunology	Thailand	5
776	Journal-of-the-Asian-Farming-Systems-Association	Thailand	5
777	SABRAO-Journal	Thailand	5
778	Agricultural-Zoology-Reviews	UK	5
779	Bee-World	UK	5
780	Biochemical-Systematics-and-Ecology	UK	5
781	Biotechnology-Advances	UK	5
782	British-Medical-Journal-Clinical-Research-Edition	UK	5
783	Evolutionary-Trends-in-Plants	UK	5
784	Human-and-Experimental-Toxicology	UK	5
785	IAHS-Publication	UK	5
786	International-Biodeterioration-and-Biodegradation	UK	5
787	International-Journal-of-Experimental-Pathology	UK	5
788	Journal-of-Cereal-Science	UK	5
789	Journal-of-Comparative-Pathology	UK	5
790	Journal-of-Environmental-Management	UK	5
791	Journal-of-Fish-Biology	UK	5
792	Journal-of-Insect-Physiology	UK	5
793	Journal-of-Molecular-Biology	UK	5
794	Microbios	UK	5
795	Tropical-Doctor	UK	5
796	World-Development-Oxford	UK	5
797	Advances-in-Applied-Microbiology	USA	5
798	American-Journal-of-Clinical-Nutrition	USA	5
799	Analytical-Letters	USA	5
800	Annals-of-Allergy	USA	5

SI No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
801	Archives-of-Environmental-Contamination-and-Toxicology	USA	5
802	Journal -Association-of-Official-Analytical-Chemists	USA	5
803	Journal-of-Dairy-Science	USA	5
804	Journal-of-Research-on-the-Lepidoptera	USA	5
805	Journal-of-Solid-State-Chemistry	USA	5
806	Life-Sciences	USA	5
807	Microchemical-Journal	USA	5
808	Mountain-Research-and-Development	USA	5
809	Nematropica	USA	5
810	Physiology-and-Behavior	USA	5
811	Soil-Science-Society-of-America-Journal	USA	5
812	Wood-and-Fiber-Science	USA	5
813	Journal-of-Gastroenterology-and-Hepatology	Australia	4
814	Bangladesh-Journal-of-Agricultural-Sciences	Bangladesh	4
815	Memorias-do-Instituto-Oswaldo-Cruz	Brazil	4
816	Summa-Phytopathologica	Brazil	4
817	Oikos	Denmark	4
818	Acta-Oecologica	France	4
819	Fruits-Paris	France	4
820	Archiv-fur-Protistenkunde	Germany	4
821	European-Journal-of-Biochemistry	Germany	4
822	Flora-Jena	Germany	4
823	Hormone-and-Metabolic-Research	Germany	4
824	Journal-of-Applied-Ichthyology	Germany	4
825	Molecular-and-General-Genetics	Germany	4
826	Reichenbachia	Germany	4
827	Zeitschrift-fur-Naturforschung	Germany	4
828	Zeitschrift-fur-Pflanzenernahrung-und-Bodenkunde	Germany	4
829	Better-Farming-in-Salt-Affected-Soils	India	4
830	Bulletin-of-the-Botanical-Society-of-Bengal	India	4
831	Discussion-Paper -Indira-Gandhi-Institute-of-Development-Research	India	4
832	IHR-News	India	4
833	Indian-Biologist	India	4
834	Indian-Chemical-Engineer	India	4
835	Indian-Economic-Journal	India	4
836	Indian-Journal-of-Adult-Education	India	4
837	Indian-Journal-of-Animal-Production	India	4
838	Indian-Journal-of-Medical-Sciences	India	4
839	Indian-Journal-of-Pediatrics	India	4
840	Journal-of-Farming-Systems	India	4
841	Journal-of-Nature-Conservation	India	4
842	Journal-of-Plant-Biochemistry-and-Biotechnology	India	4
843	Journal-of-the-Geological-Society-of-India	India	4
844	Journal-of-the-Indian-Society-of-Cotton-Improvement	India	4
845	Journal-of-the-Institution-of-Chemists,-Calcutta	India	4

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
846	Lal-Baugh	India	4
847	Medical-Journal-Armed-Forces-India	India	4
848	National-Geographical-Journal-of-India	India	4
849	NBRI-Newsletter	India	4
850	New farmers' movements in India	India	4
851	Newsletter-National-Horticultural-Research-and-Development-Foundation	India	4
852	NFI-Bulletin	India	4
853	Pacific-and-Asian-Journal-of-Energy	India	4
854	Poultry-Guide	India	4
855	Tourism-Recreation-Research	India	4
856	Urja	India	4
857	Wastelands-News	India	4
858	Aerobiologia	Italy	4
859	Capsicum-and-Eggplant-Newsletter	Italy	4
860	Phytopathologia-Mediterranea	Italy	4
861	Desertification-Control-Bulletin	Kenya	4
862	Economic-Journal-of-Nepal	Nepal	4
863	Applied-Animal-Behaviour-Science	Netherlands	4
864	Biochimica-et-Biophysica-Acta,-Biomembranes	Netherlands	4
865	Biochimica-et-Biophysica-Acta,-Protein-Structure-and-Molecular-Enzymology	Netherlands	4
866	Diabetes-Research-and-Clinical-Practice	Netherlands	4
867	Ecological-Modelling	Netherlands	4
868	Environmental-Monitoring-and-Assessment	Netherlands	4
869	Gene	Netherlands	4
870	International-Journal-of-Food-Microbiology	Netherlands	4
871	International-Journal-of-Industrial-Ergonomics	Netherlands	4
872	Journal-of-Microbiological-Methods	Netherlands	4
873	Molecular-and-Biochemical-Parasitology	Netherlands	4
874	Preventive-Veterinary-Medicine	Netherlands	4
875	Tropical-Grain-Legume-Bulletin	Nigeria	4
876	Pakistan-Veterinary-Journal	Pakistan	4
877	Acta-Societatis-Botanicorum-Poloniae	Poland	4
878	Singapore-Journal-of-Primary-Industries	Singapore	4
879	Cocos	Sri Lanka	4
880	World-Health-Forum	Switzerland	4
881	Avian-Pathology	UK	4
882	Biology-of-Metals	UK	4
883	Biomedical-Letters	UK	4
884	BioMetals	UK	4
885	Biometals	UK	4
886	Botanical-Journal-of-the-Linnean-Society	UK	4
887	Bulletin-of-Entomological-Research	UK	4
888	Chemistry-and-Industry-London	UK	4
889	Environmentalist	UK	4
890	Insect-Biochemistry-and-Molecular-Biology	UK	4

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
891	International-Dairy-Journal	UK	4
892	International-Journal-of-Climatology	UK	4
893	International-Journal-of-Radiation-Applications-and-Instrumentation	UK	4
894	International-Journal-of-Radiation-Applications-and-Instrumentation.-Part-A,-Applied-Radiation-and-Isotopes	UK	4
895	Journal-of-Applied-Ecology	UK	4
896	Journal-of-Dairy-Research	UK	4
897	Journal-of-Endocrinology	UK	4
898	Journal-of-Hospital-Infection	UK	4
899	Journal-of-Nutritional-Medicine	UK	4
900	Journal-of-Soil-Science	UK	4
901	Journal-of-Veterinary-Pharmacology-and-Therapeutics	UK	4
902	Mutagenesis	UK	4
903	Weed-Research-Oxford	UK	4
904	Advances-in-Soil-Science	USA	4
905	Agricultural-Engineering-Journal	USA	4
906	American-Journal-of-Tropical-Medicine-and-Hygiene	USA	4
907	Annals-of-the-Entomological-Society-of-America	USA	4
908	Applied-Agricultural-Research	USA	4
909	Cactus-and-Succulent-Journal	USA	4
910	Chest	USA	4
911	Corrosion-Houston	USA	4
912	Critical-Reviews-in-Food-Science-and-Nutrition	USA	4
913	Drying-Technology	USA	4
914	Environmental-Entomology	USA	4
915	Experimental-and-Molecular-Pathology	USA	4
916	Experimental-Parasitology	USA	4
917	International-Journal-of-Acarology	USA	4
918	Journal-of-Food-Process-Engineering	USA	4
919	Journal-of-Food-Processing-and-Preservation	USA	4
920	Journal-of-Plant-Growth-Regulation	USA	4
921	Phytopathology	USA	4
922	Proceedings-of-the-National-Academy-of-Sciences-of-the-United-States-of-America	USA	4
923	Resistant-Pest-Management	USA	4
924	Water-Resources-Research	USA	4
925	Weed-Science	USA	4
926	Asian-Australasian-Journal-of-Animal-Sciences	Australia	3
927	Australian-Veterinary-Journal	Australia	3
928	Plant-Protection-Quarterly	Australia	3
929	Tropical-Grasslands	Australia	3
930	Bangladesh-Horticulture	Bangladesh	3
931	Bangladesh-Journal-of-Botany	Bangladesh	3
932	Bulletin-of-the-International-Dairy-Federation	Belgium	3
933	Tsenden	Bhutan	3

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
934	Biochemistry-and-Cell-Biology	Canada	3
935	Canadian-Journal-of-Plant-Science	Canada	3
936	Allergy-Copenhagen	Denmark	3
937	Pharmacology-and-Toxicology	Denmark	3
938	Agronomie	France	3
939	Etudes-et-Syntheses-de-l'EMVT	France	3
940	IFA-Publication	France	3
941	Mammalia	France	3
942	Anzeiger-fur-Schadlingskunde,-Pflanzenschutz,-Umweltschutz	Germany	3
943	Archiv-fur-Phytopathologie-und-Pflanzenschutz	Germany	3
944	Archiv-fur-Tierzucht	Germany	3
945	Botanica-Marina	Germany	3
946	Chemie-Mikrobiologie-Technologie-der-Lebensmittel	Germany	3
947	Chromatographia	Germany	3
948	Entomologia-Generalis	Germany	3
949	Erkrankungen der Zootiere	Germany	3
950	Infection	Germany	3
951	Journal-of-Veterinary-Medicine.-Series-A	Germany	3
952	Medical-Microbiology-and-Immunology	Germany	3
953	Oecologia	Germany	3
954	Sexual-Plant-Reproduction	Germany	3
955	Wood-Science-and-Technology	Germany	3
956	Zentralblatt-fur-Bakteriologie	Germany	3
957	Geocarto-International	Hong Kong	3
958	Acta-Botanica-Hungarica	Hungary	3
959	Acta-Microbiologica-Hungarica	Hungary	3
960	Agrokemia-es-Talajtan	Hungary	3
961	Annals-of-Medical-Entomology	India	3
962	Bulletin-of-Grain-Technology	India	3
963	Geophytology	India	3
964	Gujarat-Agricultural-Research-Journal	India	3
965	Himachal-Journal-of-Environmental-Zoology	India	3
966	Indian Society for Parasitology	India	3
967	Indian-Heart-Journal	India	3
968	Indian-Journal-of-Experimental-Botany	India	3
969	Indian-Journal-of-Industrial-Relations	India	3
970	Indian-Veterinary-Reporter	India	3
971	ISCI-Journal,-Indian-Society-for-Cotton-Improvement	India	3
972	Journal-of-Industrial-Pollution-Control	India	3
973	Journal-of-the-Indian-Society-of-Agricultural-Statistics	India	3
974	Journal-of-the-Institution-of-Engineers-India	India	3
975	Manpower-Journal	India	3
976	Proceeding-of-the-Indian-Academy-of-Sciences,-Earth-and-Planetary-Sciences	India	3

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
977	Proceedings-of-the-Indian-Academy-of-Sciences,-Chemical-Sciences	India	3
978	Recent-Researches-in-Ecology,-Environment-and-Pollution	India	3
979	Research-and-Industry-New-Delhi	India	3
980	TISGLOW	India	3
981	Working-Paper-Series -Sustainable-Forest-Management,-Ford-Foundation	India	3
982	Atherosclerosis	Ireland	3
983	Journal-of-Reproductive-Immunology	Ireland	3
984	Advances-in-Horticultural-Science	Italy	3
985	World-Animal-Review	Italy	3
986	Applied-Entomology-and-Zoology	Japan	3
987	Japanese-Journal-of-Experimental-Medicine	Japan	3
988	Journal-of-the-Faculty-of-Agriculture,-Hokkaido-University	Japan	3
989	Journal-of-Plant-Protection-in-the-Tropics	Malaysia	3
990	Malaysian-Forester	Malaysia	3
991	Archives-of-Medical-Research	Mexico	3
992	Aquatic-Toxicology	Netherlands	3
993	Hydrobiologia	Netherlands	3
994	IAWA-Bulletin	Netherlands	3
995	ITC-Journal	Netherlands	3
996	Journal-of-Virological-Methods	Netherlands	3
997	Mutation-Research,-Mutation-Research-Letters	Netherlands	3
998	Sarhad-Journal-of-Agriculture	Pakistan	3
999	Philippine-Journal-of-Veterinary-Medicine	Philippines	3
1000	Acta-Mycologica	Poland	3
1001	International-Agrophysics	Poland	3
1002	Polskie-Pismo-Entomologiczne	Poland	3
1003	Revista-Iberica-de-Parasitologia	Spain	3
1004	Nephron	Switzerland	3
1005	Lens-Newsletter	Syria	3
1006	Bulletin-of-Institute-of-Zoology,-Academia-Sinica	Taiwan	3
1007	Asian-Livestock	Thailand	3
1008	Advances-in-Space-Research	UK	3
1009	Annals-of-Tropical-Paediatrics	UK	3
1010	Applied-Ergonomics	UK	3
1011	Aquacultural-Engineering	UK	3
1012	Biochemical-Journal-London	UK	3
1013	Biocontrol-Science-and-Technology	UK	3
1014	Biologicals	UK	3
1015	Biotechnology-in-Agriculture	UK	3
1016	Comparative-Biochemistry-and-Physiology	UK	3
1017	Ecological-Entomology	UK	3
1018	Environmental-Technology	UK	3
1019	Geotechnique	UK	3
1020	Immunology-and-Infectious-Diseases	UK	3

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
1021	Insect-Biochemistry	UK	3
1022	Journal-of-Food-Engineering	UK	3
1023	Journal-of-Peasant-Studies	UK	3
1024	Journal-of-Reproduction-and-Fertility	UK	3
1025	Land-Degradation-and-Rehabilitation	UK	3
1026	Leprosy-Review	UK	3
1027	Marine-Pollution-Bulletin	UK	3
1028	Mycologist	UK	3
1029	Nature-London	UK	3
1030	New-Phytologist	UK	3
1031	ODI-Irrigation-Management-Network-Paper	UK	3
1032	Pharmacological-Research	UK	3
1033	Physiological-Entomology	UK	3
1034	Plant,-Cell-and-Environment	UK	3
1035	RRA-Notes-International-Institute-for-Environment-and-Development	UK	3
1036	Tetrahedron	UK	3
1037	Advances-in-Agronomy	USA	3
1038	American-Journal-of-Roentgenology	USA	3
1039	Ammonia-Plant-Safety-and-Related-Facilities	USA	3
1040	Annals-of-Ophthalmology	USA	3
1041	Archives-of-Insect-Biochemistry-and-Physiology	USA	3
1042	Archives-of-Ophthalmology	USA	3
1043	Botanical-Review	USA	3
1044	Coleopterists-Bulletin	USA	3
1045	Developmental-and-Comparative-Immunology	USA	3
1046	Digestive-Diseases-and-Sciences	USA	3
1047	Endocrine-Research	USA	3
1048	Environmental-Research-New-York	USA	3
1049	Food-Reviews-International	USA	3
1050	Immunological-Investigations	USA	3
1051	Industrial-and-Engineering-Chemistry-Research	USA	3
1052	Infection-and-Immunity	USA	3
1053	Journal-of-Bacteriology	USA	3
1054	Journal-of-Biochemical-Toxicology	USA	3
1055	Journal-of-Clinical-Laboratory-Analysis	USA	3
1056	Journal-of-Clinical-Microbiology	USA	3
1057	Journal-of-Environmental-Science-and-Health.-Part-A,-Environmental-Science-and-Engineering	USA	3
1058	Journal-of-Experimental-Zoology	USA	3
1059	Journal-of-Herbs,-Spices-and-Medicinal-Plants	USA	3
1060	Journal-of-Texture-Studies	USA	3
1061	Studies-in-Family-Planning	USA	3
1062	Sulphur-in-Agriculture	USA	3
1063	Teratogenesis,-Carcinogenesis,-and-Mutagenesis	USA	3
1064	Zimbabwe-Journal-of-Agricultural-Research	Zimbabwe	3

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
1065	Australian-and-New-Zealand-Journal-of-Obstetrics-and-Gynaecology	Australia	2
1066	Australian-Journal-of-Nutrition-and-Dietetics	Australia	2
1067	Archives-of-Virology	Austria	2
1068	Mikrochimica-Acta	Austria	2
1069	Sydowia	Austria	2
1070	Asia-Pacific-Journal-of-Rural-Development	Bangladesh	2
1071	Bangladesh-Journal-of-Agriculture	Bangladesh	2
1072	Bangladesh-Journal-of-Scientific-and-Industrial-Research	Bangladesh	2
1073	Bangladesh-Veterinarian	Bangladesh	2
1074	Ciencia-e-Cultura-Sao-Paulo	Brazil	2
1075	Fitopatologia-Brasileira	Brazil	2
1076	Pesquisa-Agropecuaria-Brasileira	Brazil	2
1077	Revista-Ceres	Brazil	2
1078	Canadian-Journal-of-Plant-Pathology	Canada	2
1079	Orbit	Canada	2
1080	Tree-Physiology	Canada	2
1081	Bulletin-of-Malacology,-Republic-of-China	China	2
1082	Soybean-Science	China	2
1083	Cassava-Newsletter	Colombia	2
1084	Revista-de-Biologia-Tropical	Costa Rica	2
1085	Turrialba	Costa Rica	2
1086	APMIS,-Acta-Pathologica,-Microbiologica-et-Immunologica-Scandinavica	Denmark	2
1087	European-Respiratory-Journal	Denmark	2
1088	Nordic-Hydrology	Denmark	2
1089	Egyptian-Journal-of-Botany	Egypt	2
1090	Acta-Oecologica,-Oecologia-Plantarum	France	2
1091	Annales-de-Parasitologie-Humaine-et-Comparee	France	2
1092	Bulletin-de-la-Societe-Botanique-de-France,-Actualite-Botaniques	France	2
1093	Cryptogamie,-Mycologie	France	2
1094	European-Journal-of-Medicinal-Chemistry	France	2
1095	Genetics,-Selection,-Evolution	France	2
1096	Revue-d'Elevage-et-de-Medecine-Veterinaire-des-Pays-Tropicaux	France	2
1097	Revue-Scientifique-et-Technique -Office-International-des-Epizooties	France	2
1098	World-Rabbit-Science	France	2
1099	Acceptance-of-soil-and-water-conservation-strategies-and-technologies	Germany	2
1100	Archiv-der-Pharmazie-Weinheim	Germany	2
1101	Behavioural-Ecology-and-Sociobiology	Germany	2
1102	Cell-and-Tissue-Research	Germany	2
1103	Chromosoma	Germany	2
1104	Current-Genetics	Germany	2
1105	Deutsche-Entomologische-Zeitschrift	Germany	2

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
1106	Fleischwirtschaft	Germany	2
1107	HRC,-Journal-of-High-Resolution-Chromatography	Germany	2
1108	Journal-of-Veterinary-Medicine.-Series-B	Germany	2
1109	Mitteilungen-der-Deutschen-Bodenkundlichen-Gesellsch	Germany	2
1110	Neuroradiology	Germany	2
1111	Nova-Hedwigia	Germany	2
1112	Polar-Biology	Germany	2
1113	Tropical-Medicine-and-Parasitology	Germany	2
1114	Zeitschrift-fur-Geomorphologie	Germany	2
1115	Acta-Biologica-Hungarica	Hungary	2
1116	Apiacta	Hungary	2
1117	Bulletin-of-the-Indian-Association-of-Lady-Veterinarians	India	2
1118	Bulletin-Postgraduate-Institute-of-Medical-Education-and-Research,-Chandigarh	India	2
1119	Contributions-to-Indian-Sociology	India	2
1120	Entomol.-Res.,-New-Delhi	India	2
1121	Geographical-Review-of-India	India	2
1122	Health-and-Population-Perspectives-and-Issues	India	2
1123	ICMF-Journal,-Indian-Cotton-Manufacturers-Federation	India	2
1124	Indian-Academy-of-Sciences	India	2
1125	Indian-Food-Packer	India	2
1126	Indian-Journal-of-Botany	India	2
1127	Indian-Journal-of-Power-and-River-Valley-Development	India	2
1128	Indian-Journal-of-Textile-Research	India	2
1129	Indian-Journal-Poultry-Science	India	2
1130	Irrigation-and-Power-New-Delhi	India	2
1131	Journal-of-Financial-Management-and-Analysis	India	2
1132	Journal-of-Palynology	India	2
1133	Journal-of-the-Indian-Society-of-Coastal-Research	India	2
1134	Kanpur-University-Research-Journal-Science	India	2
1135	Khadi-Gramodyog	India	2
1136	Medicinal-and-Aromatic-Plants-Abstracts	India	2
1137	Newsletter-UPASI-Tea-Research-Institute	India	2
1138	Pashudhan-Anushandhan	India	2
1139	Prajnan	India	2
1140	Proceedings-of-the-Indian-Academy-of-Sciences,-Earth-and-Planetary-Sciences	India	2
1141	Research-Bulletin-International-Crops-Research-Institute-for-the-Semi-Arid-Tropics	India	2
1142	Transactions-of-the-Bose-Research-Institute	India	2
1143	Vatika-from-the-Seed-and-Plant-People	India	2
1144	Working-Paper -Gujarat-Institute-of-Area-Planning	India	2
1145	Agrivita	Indonesia	2
1146	Forensic-Science-International	Ireland	2
1147	International-Journal-of-Cardiology	Ireland	2
1148	International-Journal-of-Gynecology-and-Obstetrics	Ireland	2

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
1149	International-Journal-of-Pediatric-Otorhinolaryngology	Ireland	2
1150	Mechanisms-of-Ageing-and-Development	Ireland	2
1151	Israel-Journal-of-Veterinary-Medicine	Israel	2
1152	Symbiosis-Rehovot	Israel	2
1153	Acta-Cardiologica	Italy	2
1154	Ceres-Rome	Italy	2
1155	FAO-Economic-and-Social-Development-Paper	Italy	2
1156	Microbiologica	Italy	2
1157	Journal-of-Antibiotics	Japan	2
1158	Transactions-of-the-Mycological-Society-of-Japan	Japan	2
1159	Tropical-Medicine-Nagasaki	Japan	2
1160	Zoological-Science	Japan	2
1161	ASEAN-Food-Journal	Malaysia	2
1162	Malaysian-Agricultural-Journal	Malaysia	2
1163	Aquatic-Botany	Netherlands	2
1164	Aquatic-Insects	Netherlands	2
1165	Biochimica-et-Biophysica-Acta,-Lipids-and-Lipid-Metabolism	Netherlands	2
1166	Biofouling	Netherlands	2
1167	Biogenic-Amines	Netherlands	2
1168	Blumea	Netherlands	2
1169	Clinica-Chimica-Acta	Netherlands	2
1170	Clinical-Neurology-and-Neurosurgery	Netherlands	2
1171	Energy-Economics	Netherlands	2
1172	Fish-Physiology-and-Biochemistry	Netherlands	2
1173	Fisheries-Research	Netherlands	2
1174	IAWA-Journal	Netherlands	2
1175	Irrigation-and-Drainage-Systems	Netherlands	2
1176	Journal-of-Immunological-Methods	Netherlands	2
1177	Netherlands-Milk-and-Dairy-Journal	Netherlands	2
1178	New-Forests	Netherlands	2
1179	Postharvest-Biology-and-Technology	Netherlands	2
1180	Quarterly-Bulletin-of-IAALD	Netherlands	2
1181	Water-Resources-Management	Netherlands	2
1182	Journal-of-Applied-Seed-Production	New Zealand	2
1183	Philippine-Agriculturist	Philippines	2
1184	Acta-Hydrobiologica	Poland	2
1185	Animal-Science-Papers-and-Reports-Polish-Academy-of-Sciences,-Institute-of-Genetics-and-Animal-Breed	Poland	2
1186	Annales-Zoologici	Poland	2
1187	Genetica-Polonica	Poland	2
1188	Cellulose-Chemistry-and-Technology	Romania	2
1189	Pochvovedenie	Russia	2
1190	Neoplasma	Slovakia	2
1191	Phytophylactica	South Africa	2
1192	Scandinavian-Journal-of-Infectious-Diseases	Sweden	2
1193	Digestion	Switzerland	2

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1194	Gerontology	Switzerland	2
1195	International-Archives-of-Allergy-and-Immunology	Switzerland	2
1196	International-Labour-Review	Switzerland	2
1197	Progress-in-Drug-Research	Switzerland	2
1198	Agro-Chemicals-News-in-Brief	Thailand	2
1199	Acta-Botanica-Neerlandica	UK	2
1200	Annals-of-Human-Biology	UK	2
1201	Asia-Pacific-Journal-of-Pharmacology	UK	2
1202	Biomass	UK	2
1203	British-Journal-of-Urology	UK	2
1204	Cambridge-Journal-of-Economics	UK	2
1205	Carcinogenesis	UK	2
1206	Chemical-Speciation-and-Bioavailability	UK	2
1207	Clinical-and-Experimental-Allergy	UK	2
1208	Clinical-and-Experimental-Immunology	UK	2
1209	Clinical-Radiology	UK	2
1210	Comparative-Biochemistry-and-Physiology.-B.-Comparative-Biochemistry	UK	2
1211	Comparative-Haematology-International	UK	2
1212	Cryo-letters	UK	2
1213	Development-and-Change	UK	2
1214	Development-in-Practice:-An-Oxfam-Journal	UK	2
1215	Ecologist	UK	2
1216	Environmental-Geochemistry-and-Health	UK	2
1217	Experimental-and-Applied-Acarology	UK	2
1218	Fertilizer-Focus	UK	2
1219	Fish-and-Shellfish-Immunology	UK	2
1220	Flavors-and-Fragrances:-a-world-perspective	UK	2
1221	Food-Policy	UK	2
1222	Genetic-Engineer-and-Biotechnologist	UK	2
1223	Genetical-Research	UK	2
1224	Gut	UK	2
1225	Heredity	UK	2
1226	Hydrological-Processes	UK	2
1227	International-Industrial-Biotechnology	UK	2
1228	International-Journal-of-Biochemistry	UK	2
1229	International-Journal-of-Epidemiology	UK	2
1230	International-Journal-of-Immunopharmacology	UK	2
1231	Journal-of-Agricultural-Economics	UK	2
1232	Journal-of-Clinical-Pathology	UK	2
1233	Journal-of-General-Virology	UK	2
1234	Journal-of-Human-Nutrition-and-Dietetics	UK	2
1235	Journal-of-Infection	UK	2
1236	Journal-of-Pharmacy-and-Pharmacology	UK	2
1237	Journal-of-Terramechanics	UK	2
1238	Journal-of-the-Society-of-Dairy-Technology	UK	2

SI No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
1239	Journal-of-Thermal-Biology	UK	2
1240	Journal-of-Veterinary-Anaesthesia	UK	2
1241	Kew-Bulletin	UK	2
1242	Meat-Science	UK	2
1243	Mushroom-Science-XIII	UK	2
1244	Natural-Resources-Forum	UK	2
1245	Nephrology-Dialysis-Transplantation	UK	2
1246	Parasitology-Today	UK	2
1247	Phosphorus-and-Potassium	UK	2
1248	Physiological-and-Molecular-Plant-Pathology	UK	2
1249	Plant-Varieties-and-Seeds	UK	2
1250	Proceedings-of-the-Nutrition-Society	UK	2
1251	Project-Appraisal	UK	2
1252	Respiratory-Medicine	UK	2
1253	Shell-Agriculture	UK	2
1254	Subcellular-Biochemistry	UK	2
1255	Tetrahedron-Letters	UK	2
1256	Veterinary-Bulletin	UK	2
1257	World's-Poultry-Science-Journal	UK	2
1258	Advances-in-Environmental-Science-and-Technology	USA	2
1259	American-Journal-of-Agricultural-Economics	USA	2
1260	American-Journal-of-Alternative-Agriculture	USA	2
1261	American-Orchid-Society-Bulletin	USA	2
1262	Analytical-Biochemistry	USA	2
1263	Analytical-Chemistry-Washington	USA	2
1264	Asian-Survey	USA	2
1265	Bio-Technology	USA	2
1266	Bulletin-of-the-Torrey-Botanical-Club	USA	2
1267	Chronobiology-International	USA	2
1268	Contraception-Stoneham	USA	2
1269	CRC-Critical-Reviews-in-Food-Science-and-Nutrition	USA	2
1270	Diagnostic-Cytopathology	USA	2
1271	Diversity	USA	2
1272	Drug-and-Chemical-Toxicology	USA	2
1273	Environment-International	USA	2
1274	Environmental-Geology	USA	2
1275	Environmental-Management	USA	2
1276	Environmental-Toxicology-and-Water-Quality	USA	2
1277	Experimental-Cell-Research	USA	2
1278	Forest-Products-Journal	USA	2
1279	Forest-Science	USA	2
1280	Fruit-Varieties-Journal	USA	2
1281	Functional-and-Developmental-Morphology	USA	2
1282	Health-Physics	USA	2
1283	Journal-for-Farming-Systems-Research-Extension	USA	2
1284	Journal-of-Allergy-and-Clinical-Immunology	USA	2
1285	Journal-of-Applied-Polymer-Science	USA	2

SI No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
1286	Journal-of-Aquatic-Animal-Health	USA	2
1287	Journal-of-Clinical-Ultrasound	USA	2
1288	Journal-of-Comparative-Physiology	USA	2
1289	Journal-of-Computer-Assisted-Tomography	USA	2
1290	Journal-of-Environmental-Hydrology	USA	2
1291	Journal-of-Environmental-Pathology,-Toxicology-and-Oncology	USA	2
1292	Journal-of-Environmental-Science-and-Health.-Part-B,-Pesticides,-Food-Contaminants,-and-Agricultural-Wastes	USA	2
1293	Journal-of-Food-Protection	USA	2
1294	Journal-of-Nutrition	USA	2
1295	Journal-of-Protein-Chemistry	USA	2
1296	Journal-of-Soil-and-Water-Conservation	USA	2
1297	Journal-of-Sustainable-Agriculture	USA	2
1298	Journal-of-the-American-College-of-Nutrition	USA	2
1299	Journal-of-the-Helminthological-Society-of-Washington	USA	2
1300	Journal-of-Zoo-and-Wildlife-Medicine	USA	2
1301	Lindleyana	USA	2
1302	Lymphology	USA	2
1303	Malacological-Review	USA	2
1304	Medicinal-Research-Reviews	USA	2
1305	Metabolism,-Clinical-and-Experimental	USA	2
1306	Microelectronics-and-Reliability	USA	2
1307	Minerals-and-Metallurgical-Processing	USA	2
1308	Mycologia	USA	2
1309	Photochemistry-and-Photobiology	USA	2
1310	Principes	USA	2
1311	Proceedings-of-the-Society-for-Experimental-Biology-and-Medicine	USA	2
1312	Progressive-Fish-Culturist	USA	2
1313	Rat-News-Letter	USA	2
1314	Reviews-of-Infectious-Diseases	USA	2
1315	Stain-Technology	USA	2
1316	Steroids	USA	2
1317	Transplantation-Proceedings	USA	2
1318	Geo-Eco-Trop	Zaire	2
1319	Phyton-Buenos-Aires	Argentina	1
1320	ACIAR-Food-Legume-Newsletter	Australia	1
1321	ACIAR-Proceedings-Series	Australia	1
1322	Appita-Journal	Australia	1
1323	Australasian-Biotechnology	Australia	1
1324	Australasian-Journal-of-Dermatology	Australia	1
1325	Australian-and-New-Zealand-Journal-of-Ophthalmology	Australia	1
1326	Australian-Journal-of-Biotechnology	Australia	1
1327	Australian-Journal-of-Botany	Australia	1
1328	Australian-Journal-of-Ecology	Australia	1

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
1329	Australian-Journal-of-Medical-Herbalism	Australia	1
1330	Australian-Journal-of-Soil-and-Water-Conservation	Australia	1
1331	Australian-Journal-of-Soil-Science	Australia	1
1332	Clinical-and-Experimental-Pharmacology-and-Physiology	Australia	1
1333	Genetic-Engineering-and-Biotechnology-Monitor	Austria	1
1334	Bango-Biggyan-Patrika	Bangladesh	1
1335	Journal-of-Rural-Development	Bangladesh	1
1336	Belgian-Journal-of-Botany	Belgium	1
1337	Bulletin-de-l'Institut-Royal-des-Sciences-Naturelles-de-Belgique,-Entomologie	Belgium	1
1338	International-Dairy-Federation-Special-Issue	Belgium	1
1339	Mededelingen-van-de-Faculteit-Landbouwwetenschappen,-Rijksuniversiteit-Gent	Belgium	1
1340	Pedologie	Belgium	1
1341	Arquivos-de-Biologia-e-Tecnologia	Brazil	1
1342	Brazilian-Journal-of-Medical-and-Biological-Research	Brazil	1
1343	Naturalia-Sao-Jose-do-Rio-Preto	Brazil	1
1344	Revista-Brasileira-de-Biologia	Brazil	1
1345	Revista-do-Instituto-de-Medicina-Tropical-de-Sao-Paulo	Brazil	1
1346	Canadian-Journal-of-Chemical-Engineering	Canada	1
1347	Canadian-Journal-of-Ophthalmology	Canada	1
1348	Canadian-Journal-of-Soil-Science	Canada	1
1349	Canadian-Journal-of-Zoology	Canada	1
1350	Convergence-Toronto	Canada	1
1351	Ecodecision	Canada	1
1352	Journal-of-Distance-Education	Canada	1
1353	Journal-of-Engineering-for-International-Development	Canada	1
1354	Land Use Planning Application	Canada	1
1355	Revue-Canadienne-d'Etudes-du-Developpement	Canada	1
1356	Water-Pollution-Research-Journal-of-Canada	Canada	1
1357	Water-Quality-Bulletin	Canada	1
1358	Acta-Pharmacologica-Sinica	China	1
1359	Chemistry-and-Industry-of-Forest-Products	China	1
1360	Genetic-Manipulation-in-Plants	China	1
1361	Evolucion-Biologica	Colombia	1
1362	Collection-of-Czechoslovak-Chemical-Communications	Czech Republic	1
1363	European-Journal-of-Entomology	Czech Republic	1
1364	Acta-Societatis-Zoologicae-Bohemoslovacae	Czechoslovakia	1
1365	Folia-Geobotanica-et-Phytotaxonomica	Czechoslovakia	1
1366	Journal-of-Hygiene,-Epidemiology,-Microbiology-and-Immunology	Czechoslovakia	1
1367	Vestnik-Ceskoslovenske-Spolecnosti-Zoologicke	Czechoslovakia	1
1368	Allergy	Denmark	1
1369	Contact-Dermatitis	Denmark	1
1370	Entomologia-Scandinavica	Denmark	1

SI No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
1371	International-Journal-of-Oral-and-Maxillofacial-Surgery	Denmark	1
1372	International-Journal-of-Peptide-and-Protein-Research	Denmark	1
1373	Journal-of-Cutaneous-Pathology	Denmark	1
1374	Physiological-Zoology	Denmark	1
1375	Alexandria-Journal-of-Agricultural-Research	Egypt	1
1376	Egyptian-Journal-of-Soil-Science	Egypt	1
1377	Journal-of-the-Egyptian-Society-of-Parasitology	Egypt	1
1378	Livestock-Research-for-Rural-Development	Ethiopia	1
1379	Acta-Oecologica,-Oecologia-Applicata	France	1
1380	Annales-de-la-Societe-Entomologique-de-France	France	1
1381	Annales-de-Recherches-Veterinaires	France	1
1382	Annales-de-Sciences-Naturelles,-Botanique-et-Biologie-Vegatale	France	1
1383	Aquatic-Living-Resources	France	1
1384	Biology-of-Behaviour	France	1
1385	Cahiers-ORSTOM,-Serie-Pedologie	France	1
1386	European-Journal-of-Soil-Biology	France	1
1387	Infomusa	France	1
1388	International-Social-Science-Journal	France	1
1389	Journal-de-Mycologie-Medicale	France	1
1390	Medicographia	France	1
1391	Plantes-Medicinales-et-Phytotherapie	France	1
1392	Revue-de-Chirurgie-Orthopedique-et-Reparatrice-de-l'Appareil-Moteur	France	1
1393	Acta-Neuropathologica	Germany	1
1394	Archives-of-Toxicology	Germany	1
1395	Arzneimittel-Forschung	Germany	1
1396	Blut	Germany	1
1397	Chemical-Engineering-and-Technology	Germany	1
1398	Chemie-ingenieur-technik	Germany	1
1399	Diseases-of-Aquatic-Organisms	Germany	1
1400	Endoscopy	Germany	1
1401	Entomologische-Abhandlungen	Germany	1
1402	European-Journal-of-Clinical-Microbiology-and-Infectious-Diseases	Germany	1
1403	Holz-als-Roh-und-Werkstoff	Germany	1
1404	IFLA-Journal	Germany	1
1405	Internationale-Revue-der-Gesamten-Hydrobiologie	Germany	1
1406	Journal-of-Animal-Breeding-and-Genetics	Germany	1
1407	Journal-of-Planar-Chromatography	Germany	1
1408	Journal-of-Trace-Elements-and-Electrolytes-in-Health-and-Disease	Germany	1
1409	Liebigs-Annalen-der-Chemie	Germany	1
1410	Mitteilungen-der-Osterreichischen-Gesellschaft-fur-Tropenmedizin-und-Parasitologie	Germany	1
1411	Mycotoxin-prevention-and-control-in-foodgrains	Germany	1

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
1412	Naturwissenschaften	Germany	1
1413	Parasitology-Research	Germany	1
1414	Pediatric-Radiology	Germany	1
1415	Pediatric-Surgery	Germany	1
1416	Quarterly-Journal-of-International-Agriculture	Germany	1
1417	Systematic-and-Applied-Microbiology	Germany	1
1418	Willdenowia	Germany	1
1419	Zeitschrift-fur-Lebensmittel-Untersuchung-und -Forschung	Germany	1
1420	Zeitschrift-fur-Naturforschung.-Section-C,-Biosciences	Germany	1
1421	Zeitschrift-fur-Zoologie	Germany	1
1422	Zeitschrift-fur-Zoologische-Systematik-und-Evolutionsforschung	Germany	1
1423	Zoologische-Jahrbucher,-Abteilung-fur-Anatomie-und-Ontogenie-der-Tiere	Germany	1
1424	Zoologische-Jahrbucher,-Abteilung-fur-Systematik,-Okologie-und-Geographie-der-Tiere	Germany	1
1425	Entomologia-Hellenica	Greece	1
1426	Asia-Pacific-Journal-of-Public-Health	Hong Kong	1
1427	Mushroom-Journal-for-the-Tropics	Hong Kong	1
1428	Acta-Alimentaria-Budapest	Hungary	1
1429	Journal-of-Thermal-Analysis	Hungary	1
1430	Parasitologia-Hungarica	Hungary	1
1431	Administrator	India	1
1432	Advances-in-Biosciences-Muzaffarnagar	India	1
1433	Agricultural-Science-Digest-Karnal	India	1
1434	Alternative-Appropriate-Technologies-in-Agriculture	India	1
1435	Ancient-Science-of-Life	India	1
1436	Applied-Botany-Abstracts	India	1
1437	Asian-Journal-of-Plant-Science	India	1
1438	Bay-of-Bengal-News	India	1
1439	Bio-Science-Research-Bulletin	India	1
1440	Bulletin-of-Electrochemistry	India	1
1441	China-Report-New-Delhi	India	1
1442	CSIR-News	India	1
1443	Eastern-Anthropologist	India	1
1444	Economics-and-Social-Science-Review	India	1
1445	Electrical-India	India	1
1446	Everyman's-Science	India	1
1447	Future-New-Delhi	India	1
1448	Geophysical-Research-Bulletin	India	1
1449	ICRISAT-Information-Bulletin	India	1
1450	ICSSR-Newsletter	India	1
1451	Indian-Journal-of-Chemistry.-Section-A,-Inorganic,-Bio-inorganic,-Physical,-Theoretical-and-Analytical-Chemistry	India	1
1452	Indian-Journal-of-Earth-Sciences	India	1
1453	Indian-Journal-of-Gastroenterology	India	1

SI No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
1454	Indian-Journal-of-Pure-and-Applied-Biology	India	1
1455	Indian-Journal-of-Quantitative-Economics	India	1
1456	Indian-Journal-of-Social-Science	India	1
1457	Indian-Journal-of-Tuberculosis	India	1
1458	Indian-perfumer	India	1
1459	International-Journal-of-Development-Planning-Literature	India	1
1460	Irrigation-and-Power-Journal	India	1
1461	Journal-of-Biosocial-Science	India	1
1462	Journal-of-Feed-Science-and-Technology-Mysore	India	1
1463	Journal-of-Recent-Advances-in-Applied-Sciences	India	1
1464	Journal-of-the-Electrochemical-Society-of-India	India	1
1465	Journal-of-the-Indian-Botanical-Society	India	1
1466	Journal-of-the-Indian-Society-of-Coastal-Aquacultural-Research	India	1
1467	Journal-Oilseeds-Research	India	1
1468	KFRI-Information-Bulletin	India	1
1469	Memoirs-Geological-Society-of-India	India	1
1470	Memoirs-of-the-Entomological-Society-of-India	India	1
1471	Mendel	India	1
1472	MFP-News	India	1
1473	National-Bank-News-Bombay	India	1
1474	Paintindia	India	1
1475	Photonirvachak-Dehra-Dun	India	1
1476	Proceedings-of-the-Academy-of-Sciences,-Earth-and-Planetary-Sciences	India	1
1477	Proceedings-of-the-Annual-Convention-of-the-Sugar-Technologists-Association-of-India	India	1
1478	Proceedings-of-the-Indian-Academy-of-Parasitology	India	1
1479	Proceedings-of-the-Indian-Academy-of-Science	India	1
1480	Proceedings-of-the-Indian-National-Science-Academy.-Part-A,-Physical-Sciences	India	1
1481	Progress-Report-Economics-Group,-Resource-Management-Program-ICRISAT	India	1
1482	Progressive-Farming-Ludhiana	India	1
1483	Records-of-the-Zoological-Survey-of-India	India	1
1484	Regional-Journal-of-Energy,-Heat-and-Mass-Transfer	India	1
1485	Research-and-Industry	India	1
1486	Research-Bulletin-Central-Research-Institute-for-Dryland-Agriculture	India	1
1487	Research-Paper-Institute-of-Rural-Management,Anand	India	1
1488	Research-Publication -Mahatma-Phule-Krishi-Vidyapeeth	India	1
1489	Science-Age	India	1
1490	Science-and-Environment	India	1
1491	Southern-Economist	India	1
1492	Sugarcane-Breeding-Institute-Quarterly	India	1
1493	Technical-Bulletin-Project-Directorate-of-Biological-Control,-ICAR	India	1

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
1494	Tool-and-Alloy-Steels	India	1
1495	Toxin-related-diseases	India	1
1496	Working-Paper -Institute-of-Rural-Management-Anand	India	1
1497	Iranian-Journal-of-Agricultural-Sciences	Iran	1
1498	Chemico-Biological-Interactions	Ireland	1
1499	Irish-Journal-of-Food-Science-and-Technology	Ireland	1
1500	Israel-Journal-of-Botany	Israel	1
1501	Agricoltura-Mediterranea	Italy	1
1502	Annali-di-Chimica	Italy	1
1503	Annali-di-Microbiologia-ed-Enzimologia	Italy	1
1504	Bollettino-del-Laboratorio-di-Entomologia-Agraria-Filippo-Silvestri	Italy	1
1505	Bollettino-di-Zoologia	Italy	1
1506	Bollettino-Malacologico	Italy	1
1507	Ethology,-Ecology-and-Evolution	Italy	1
1508	FAO-Animal-Production-and-Health-Paper	Italy	1
1509	FAO-Aquaculture-Newsletter	Italy	1
1510	FAO-Fisheries-Technical-Paper	Italy	1
1511	International-Rice-Commission-Newsletter	Italy	1
1512	International-Surgery	Italy	1
1513	Journal-of-Submicroscopic-Cytology-and-Pathology	Italy	1
1514	Monitore-Zoologico-Italiano	Italy	1
1515	Parassitologia-Roma	Italy	1
1516	Revista-di-Agricoltura-Subtropicale-e-Tropicale	Italy	1
1517	Rivista-di-Ingegneria-Agraria	Italy	1
1518	Rivista-di-Patologia-Vegetale	Italy	1
1519	Savings-and-Development	Italy	1
1520	Tropical-Zoology	Italy	1
1521	Women-in-agriculture	Italy	1
1522	Annals-of-the-Phytopathological-Society-of-Japan	Japan	1
1523	APO-Productivity-Journal	Japan	1
1524	Asian-Economies	Japan	1
1525	Biotronics	Japan	1
1526	Clay-Science	Japan	1
1527	Endocrinologica-Japonica	Japan	1
1528	Japanese-Journal-of-Breeding	Japan	1
1529	Japanese-Journal-of-Pharmacology	Japan	1
1530	Journal-of-Clinical-Biochemistry-and-Nutrition	Japan	1
1531	Nippon-Kingakukai-Kaiho	Japan	1
1532	Primates	Japan	1
1533	Proceedings-of-the-Japanese-Association-of-Mycotoxicology	Japan	1
1534	Rice-Genome	Japan	1
1535	Tropical-Agriculture-Research-Series	Japan	1
1536	Dirasat	Jordan	1
1537	East-African-Agricultural-and-Forestry-Journal	Kenya	1
1538	Tea	Kenya	1

Sl No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
1539	Korean-Journal-of-Mycology	Korea	1
1540	Arab-Journal-of-Plant-Protection	Lebanon	1
1541	Elaeis	Malaysia	1
1542	Jurnal-Veterinar-Malaysia	Malaysia	1
1543	Anales-del-Instituto-de-Biologia	Mexico	1
1544	Atmosfera	Mexico	1
1545	Revista-Mexicana-de-Fitopatologia	Mexico	1
1546	Dinteria	Namibia	1
1547	Banko-Janakari	Nepal	1
1548	Journal-of-the-Institute-of-Agriculture-and-Animal-Science	Nepal	1
1549	Acta-Leidensia	Netherlands	1
1550	Agricultural-Economics	Netherlands	1
1551	Beltsville-Symposia-in-Agricultural-Research	Netherlands	1
1552	Biochimica-et-Biophysica-Acta	Netherlands	1
1553	Biochimica-et-Biophysica-Acta,-General-Subjects	Netherlands	1
1554	Biochimica-et-Biophysica-Acta,-Molecular-Basis-of-Disease	Netherlands	1
1555	Biochimica-et-Biophysica-Acta-G,-General-Subjects	Netherlands	1
1556	Biodegradation	Netherlands	1
1557	Chemical-Geology,-Isotope-Geoscience-Section	Netherlands	1
1558	Chemistry-and-Ecology	Netherlands	1
1559	Crustaceana	Netherlands	1
1560	Developments-in-Soil-Science	Netherlands	1
1561	Earth-and-Planetary-Science-Letters	Netherlands	1
1562	Environmental-and-Resource-Economics	Netherlands	1
1563	Environmental-Studies	Netherlands	1
1564	European-Journal-of-Radiology	Netherlands	1
1565	Geojournal	Netherlands	1
1566	Higher-Education	Netherlands	1
1567	Immunology-Letters	Netherlands	1
1568	International-Journal-of-Production-Economics	Netherlands	1
1569	Journal-of-Chromatography,-Biomedical-Applications	Netherlands	1
1570	Journal-of-Crystal-Growth	Netherlands	1
1571	Journal-of-Molecular-Catalysis	Netherlands	1
1572	Journal-of-the-Neurological-Sciences	Netherlands	1
1573	Journal-of-World-Trade	Netherlands	1
1574	Landscape-and-Urban-Planning	Netherlands	1
1575	Livestock-Production-Science	Netherlands	1
1576	Misset-World-Poultry	Netherlands	1
1577	Pigs	Netherlands	1
1578	Prophyta	Netherlands	1
1579	Review-of-Palaeobotany-and-Palynology	Netherlands	1
1580	Social-Indicators-Research	Netherlands	1
1581	Tijdschrift-voor-Entomologie	Netherlands	1
1582	World-animal-science-C,-production-system-approach-6:-Buffalo-production	Netherlands	1
1583	Asparagus-Research-Newsletter	New Zealand	1

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1584	Clinical-Pharmacokinetics	New Zealand	1
1585	Journal-of-Hydrology,-New-Zealand	New Zealand	1
1586	New-Zealand-Veterinary-Journal	New Zealand	1
1587	Newsletter -International-Herbage-Seed-Production-Research-Group	New Zealand	1
1588	Acta-Endocrinologia	Norway	1
1589	Scandinavian-Journal-of-Gastroenterology	Norway	1
1590	Biologia,-Lahore	Pakistan	1
1591	Journal-of-Agricultural-Research-Lahore	Pakistan	1
1592	Journal-of-Behavioural-Sciences	Pakistan	1
1593	Pakistan-Journal-of-Biochemistry	Pakistan	1
1594	Pakistan-Journal-of-Botany	Pakistan	1
1595	Pakistan-Journal-of-Forestry	Pakistan	1
1596	Pakistan-Sugar-Journal	Pakistan	1
1597	Proceedings-of-the-Annual-Convention -Pakistan-Society-of-Sugar-Technologists	Pakistan	1
1598	Asian-Development-Review	Philippines	1
1599	Canopy-International	Philippines	1
1600	Journal-of-Contemporary-Asia	Philippines	1
1601	Naga	Philippines	1
1602	Philippine-Journal-of-Crop-Science	Philippines	1
1603	Solidarity	Philippines	1
1604	Acta-Biologica-Cracoviensia	Poland	1
1605	Bulletin-of-the-Polish-Academy-of-Sciences,-Biological-Sciences	Poland	1
1606	Fragmenta-Floristica-et-Geobotanica	Poland	1
1607	Fruit-Science-Reports	Poland	1
1608	Geographica-Polonica	Poland	1
1609	Cytology	Russia	1
1610	Soviet-Journal-of-Ecology	Russia	1
1611	Asean-Journal-of-Clinical-Sciences	Singapore	1
1612	Raffles-Bulletin-of-Zoology	Singapore	1
1613	Singapore-Veterinary-Journal	Singapore	1
1614	Bothalia	South Africa	1
1615	Progress-in-Food-and-Nutrition-Science	South Africa	1
1616	South-African-Journal-of-Botany	South Africa	1
1617	Southern-Journal-of-Agricultural-Economics	South Africa	1
1618	Elytron	Spain	1
1619	Investigacion-Agraria,-Produccion-y-Proteccion-Vegetales	Spain	1
1620	Marga	Sri Lanka	1
1621	Sri-Lanka-Forester	Sri Lanka	1
1622	Tropical-Agriculturist	Sri Lanka	1
1623	Journal-of-Oman-Studies	Sultanate Of Oman	1
1624	Acta-Agriculturae-Scandinavica	Sweden	1
1625	Acta-Dermato-Venereologica	Sweden	1

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1626	European-Journal-of-Endocrinology	Sweden	1
1627	Food-Laboratory-News	Sweden	1
1628	Hereditas-Landskrona	Sweden	1
1629	Scandinavian-Journal-of-Development-Alternatives	Sweden	1
1630	Biology-of-the-Neonate	Switzerland	1
1631	Cardiology	Switzerland	1
1632	Dermatologica	Switzerland	1
1633	E+D,-Entwicklung-+-Developpement	Switzerland	1
1634	Human-Heredit	Switzerland	1
1635	International-Journal-of-Clinical-Pharmacology-Research	Switzerland	1
1636	International-Journal-of-Environment-and-Pollution	Switzerland	1
1637	Intervirolgy	Switzerland	1
1638	IUCN-Forest-Conservation-Programme-Newsletter	Switzerland	1
1639	Pediatric-Neurosurgery	Switzerland	1
1640	Potash-Review	Switzerland	1
1641	Research-Series -International-Institute-for-Labour-Studies	Switzerland	1
1642	Urologia-Internationalis	Switzerland	1
1643	Camel-Newsletter	Syria	1
1644	Journal-of-Taiwan-Museum	Taiwan	1
1645	Mushroom-Science	Taiwan	1
1646	Taiwan-Sugar	Taiwan	1
1647	Taiwania	Taiwan	1
1648	Economic-Bulletin-for-Asia-and-the-Pacific	Thailand	1
1649	Field-Documnt -FAO-Regional-Office-for-Asia-and-the-Pacific	Thailand	1
1650	RAPA-Publication	Thailand	1
1651	Tigerpaper	Thailand	1
1652	Acta-Physiologica-Scandinavica	UK	1
1653	Advances-in-Biosciences	UK	1
1654	Animal-Behaviour	UK	1
1655	Animal-Genetics	UK	1
1656	Animal-Technology	UK	1
1657	Archives-of-Disease-in-Childhood	UK	1
1658	Atmospheric-Environment.-Part-A,-General-Topics	UK	1
1659	Atmospheric-Environment.-Part-B,-Urban-Atmosphere	UK	1
1660	Biochemical-Society-Transactions	UK	1
1661	BioFactors-Oxford	UK	1
1662	Biological-Conservation	UK	1
1663	Biological-Journal-of-the-Linnean-Society	UK	1
1664	Biomedical-Chromatography	UK	1
1665	Bioorganic-and-Medicinal-Chemistry-Letters	UK	1
1666	Biosensors-and-Bioelectronics	UK	1
1667	Biotechnology-Education	UK	1
1668	Botanic-Gardens-Micropropagation-News	UK	1
1669	British-Corrosion-Journal	UK	1
1670	British-Journal-of-Industrial-Medicine	UK	1
1671	British-Journal-of-Neurosurgery	UK	1

SI No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
1672	British-Journal-of-Ophthalmology	UK	1
1673	British-Journal-of-Surgery	UK	1
1674	Cell-Biology-International-Reports	UK	1
1675	Cellular-and-Molecular-Biology-Research	UK	1
1676	Cement-and-Concrete-Research	UK	1
1677	Chemistry-International	UK	1
1678	Clinical-Nutrition	UK	1
1679	Computer-Applications-in-the-Biosciences	UK	1
1680	Current-Medical-Research-and-Opinion	UK	1
1681	Current-Opinion-in-Biotechnology	UK	1
1682	Development-Cambridge	UK	1
1683	Disasters	UK	1
1684	Earth-Surface-Processes-and-Landforms	UK	1
1685	Edinburgh-Journal-of-Botany	UK	1
1686	Energy-Policy	UK	1
1687	Energy-Sources	UK	1
1688	Entomologie-et-Phytopathologie-Appiquees	UK	1
1689	Entomologist	UK	1
1690	Environment-and-Urbanization	UK	1
1691	Environment-Update-Leamington-Spa	UK	1
1692	Far-Eastern-Agriculture	UK	1
1693	Fish-Farmer	UK	1
1694	Food-Microbiology	UK	1
1695	Food-Quality-and-Preference	UK	1
1696	Food-Sciences-and-Nutrition	UK	1
1697	Genitourinary-Medicine	UK	1
1698	Geomicrobiology-Journal	UK	1
1699	GRID,-IPTRID-Network-Magazine	UK	1
1700	Helminthological-Abstracts	UK	1
1701	Human-Toxicology	UK	1
1702	Immunology	UK	1
1703	Impact-of-Science-on-Society	UK	1
1704	International-Journal-of-Andrology	UK	1
1705	International-Journal-of-Biological-Macromolecules	UK	1
1706	International-Journal-of-Climatology	UK	1
1707	International-Journal-of-Energy-Research	UK	1
1708	International-Journal-of-Environmental-Health-Research	UK	1
1709	International-Journal-of-Hospitality-Management	UK	1
1710	International-Journal-of-Obesity	UK	1
1711	International-Journal-of-Radiation-Biology	UK	1
1712	International-Milling,-Flour-and-Feed	UK	1
1713	Journal-of-Antimicrobial-Chemotherapy	UK	1
1714	Journal-of-Biogeography	UK	1
1715	Journal-of-Chemical-Technology-and-Biotechnology	UK	1
1716	Journal-of-Chemical-Thermodynamics	UK	1
1717	Journal-of-Development-Studies	UK	1

SI No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
1718	Journal-of-Ecology-Oxford	UK	1
1719	Journal-of-Experimental-Biology	UK	1
1720	Journal-of-Fish-Diseases	UK	1
1721	Journal-of-Industrial-Microbiology	UK	1
1722	Journal-of-International-Development	UK	1
1723	Journal-of-Materials-Science	UK	1
1724	Journal-of-Materials-Science-Letters	UK	1
1725	Journal-of-Natural-History	UK	1
1726	Journal-of-the-Chemical-Society,-Faraday-Transactions	UK	1
1727	Journal-of-the-Institute-of-Wood-Science	UK	1
1728	Journal-of-the-Textile-Association	UK	1
1729	Journal-of-Toxicology-and-Environmental-Health	UK	1
1730	Journal-of-Tropical-Ecology	UK	1
1731	Journal-of-Wilderness-Medicine	UK	1
1732	Journal-of-Zoology	UK	1
1733	Land-Use-Policy	UK	1
1734	Medical-Education	UK	1
1735	Medical-History	UK	1
1736	Medical-Hypotheses	UK	1
1737	Medical-Laboratory-Sciences	UK	1
1738	Medicine-International	UK	1
1739	Microbial-Pathogenesis	UK	1
1740	Molecular-Immunology	UK	1
1741	Nematological-Abstracts	UK	1
1742	Nitrogen	UK	1
1743	Nuclear-Geophysics	UK	1
1744	Nutrition-and-Health	UK	1
1745	Nutrition-Research-Reviews	UK	1
1746	Occasional-Publication-British-Society-of-Animal-Production	UK	1
1747	Oxford-Economic-Papers	UK	1
1748	Parasite-Immunology	UK	1
1749	Perkin-Transactions-I	UK	1
1750	Philosophical-Transactions-of-the-Royal-Society-of-London	UK	1
1751	Philosophical-Transactions-of-the-Royal-Society-of-London,-B	UK	1
1752	Plantsman	UK	1
1753	Proceedings-of-the-Royal-College-of-Physicians-of-Edinburgh	UK	1
1754	Research-and-Development-in-Agriculture	UK	1
1755	Review-of-Plant-Pathology	UK	1
1756	Science-and-Public-Affairs-London	UK	1
1757	Science-Progress	UK	1
1758	Seed-Science-Research	UK	1
1759	Sheep-Dairy-News	UK	1
1760	Small-Enterprise-Development	UK	1
1761	Social-Science-and-Medicine	UK	1
1762	Soil-Survey-and-Land-Evaluation	UK	1

SI No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
1763	Thorax	UK	1
1764	Tissue-and-Cell	UK	1
1765	Toxicon-Oxford	UK	1
1766	Trends-in-Ecology-and-Evolution	UK	1
1767	Trends-in-Food-Science-and-Technology	UK	1
1768	Trends-in-Genetics	UK	1
1769	Tropical-Diseases-Bulletin	UK	1
1770	Waterlines	UK	1
1771	World-Agriculture-London	UK	1
1772	Zoologica-Scripta	UK	1
1773	Abdominal-Imaging	USA	1
1774	Agribusiness-New-York	USA	1
1775	AICHE-Journal	USA	1
1776	American-Bee-Journal	USA	1
1777	American-Journal-of-Botany	USA	1
1778	American-Journal-of-Human-Biology	USA	1
1779	American-Journal-of-Industrial-Medicine	USA	1
1780	American-Journal-of-Kidney-Diseases	USA	1
1781	American-Journal-of-Neuroradiology	USA	1
1782	American-Journal-of-Reproductive-Immunology	USA	1
1783	American-Potato-Journal	USA	1
1784	Annals-of-Internal-Medicine	USA	1
1785	Annals-of-the-Missouri-Botanical-Garden	USA	1
1786	Annals-of-the-New-York-Academy-of-Sciences	USA	1
1787	Annual-Review-of-Phytopathology	USA	1
1788	Annual-Review-of-Plant-Physiology-and-Plant-Molecular-Biology	USA	1
1789	Applied-Engineering-in-Agriculture	USA	1
1790	Atomic-Spectroscopy	USA	1
1791	Avian-Diseases	USA	1
1792	Biochemistry-Washington	USA	1
1793	Biological-Control	USA	1
1794	Biology-of-Reproduction	USA	1
1795	Biometrics	USA	1
1796	Bioscience-Reports	USA	1
1797	Calcified-Tissue-International	USA	1
1798	Cancer	USA	1
1799	Cancer-Research-Baltimore	USA	1
1800	Canine-Practice	USA	1
1801	Clays-and-Clay-Minerals	USA	1
1802	Clinical-Pediatrics	USA	1
1803	Clinical-Toxicology	USA	1
1804	Clinics-in-Dermatology	USA	1
1805	Compost-Science-and-Utilization	USA	1
1806	Contraception	USA	1
1807	Cooperation-South	USA	1

SI No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
1808	Critical-Reviews-in-Biotechnology	USA	1
1809	Critical-Reviews-in-Environmental-Control	USA	1
1810	Critical-Reviews-in-Microbiology	USA	1
1811	Critical-Reviews-in-Plant-Sciences	USA	1
1812	Developmental-Biology	USA	1
1813	Diabetes-Care	USA	1
1814	Diagnostic-Microbiology-and-Infectious-Disease	USA	1
1815	Diseases-of-the-Colon-and-Rectum	USA	1
1816	Doklady,-Botanical-Sciences	USA	1
1817	Drug-Development-Research	USA	1
1818	Ecology	USA	1
1819	Endocrinology-Philadelphia	USA	1
1820	Environment-and-development	USA	1
1821	Environmental-Progress	USA	1
1822	Environmental-Science-and-Technology	USA	1
1823	Fam-Forestry-News	USA	1
1824	Gamete-Research	USA	1
1825	Gastroenterology	USA	1
1826	Gastrointestinal-Endoscopy	USA	1
1827	Gastrointestinal-Radiology	USA	1
1828	Geotechnical-Testing-Journal	USA	1
1829	Haustorium	USA	1
1830	Head-and-Neck	USA	1
1831	IEEE-Transactions-on-Geoscience-and-Remote-Sensing	USA	1
1832	Immunopharmacology-and-Immunotoxicology	USA	1
	INFORM -International-News-on-Fats,-Oils-and-Related-	USA	1
1833	Materials		
1834	International-Aerobiology-Newsletter	USA	1
1835	International-Journal-of-Artificial-Organs	USA	1
1836	International-Journal-of-Health-Services	USA	1
1837	International-Journal-of-Systematic-Bacteriology	USA	1
1838	International-Journal-of-Wildland-Fire	USA	1
1839	International-Regional-Science-Review	USA	1
1840	International-Review-of-Cytology	USA	1
1841	IPM-Practitioner	USA	1
1842	Journal-of-Agricultural-Entomology	USA	1
1843	Journal-of-AOAC-International	USA	1
1844	Journal-of-Aquatic-Plant-Management	USA	1
1845	Journal-of-Asthma	USA	1
1846	Journal-of-Chromatographic-Science	USA	1
1847	Journal-of-Colloid-and-Interface-Science	USA	1
1848	Journal-of-Equine-Veterinary-Science	USA	1
1849	Journal-of-Eukaryotic-Microbiology	USA	1
1850	Journal-of-Food-Safety	USA	1
1851	Journal-of-Hydraulic-Engineering-New-York	USA	1
1852	Journal-of-Infectious-Diseases	USA	1

SI No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
1853	Journal-of-Inorganic-Biochemistry	USA	1
1854	Journal-of-Insect-Behavior	USA	1
1855	Journal-of-Liquid-Chromatography	USA	1
1856	Journal-of-Macroeconomics	USA	1
1857	Journal-of-Medical-Entomology	USA	1
1858	Journal-of-Medical-Virology	USA	1
1859	Journal-of-Medicinal-Chemistry	USA	1
1860	Journal-of-Molecular-Evolution	USA	1
1861	Journal-of-Morphology	USA	1
1862	Journal-of-Oral-and-Maxillofacial-Surgery	USA	1
1863	Journal-of-Organic-Chemistry	USA	1
1864	Journal-of-Pediatrics	USA	1
1865	Journal-of-Pharmaceutical-Sciences	USA	1
1866	Journal-of-Pharmacological-Methods	USA	1
1867	Journal-of-Physical-Chemistry	USA	1
1868	Journal-of-Raman-Spectroscopy	USA	1
1869	Journal-of-Range-Management	USA	1
1870	Journal-of-Sport-Management	USA	1
1871	Journal-of-Sugar-Beet-Research	USA	1
1872	Journal-of-the-World-Aquaculture-Society	USA	1
1873	Journal-of-Trace-Elements-in-Experimental-Medicine	USA	1
1874	Journal-of-Ultrasound-in-Medicine	USA	1
1875	Journal-of-Water-Resources-Planning-and-Management	USA	1
1876	Journal-of-Wildlife-Diseases	USA	1
1877	Langmuir	USA	1
1878	Magnetic-Resonance-Imaging	USA	1
1879	Marine-Biology	USA	1
1880	Microbiology-New-York	USA	1
1881	Minerals-Engineering	USA	1
1882	Mining-and-Engineering	USA	1
1883	Molecular-and-Chemical-Neuropathology	USA	1
1884	Monographs-in-Systematic-Botany-from-the-Missouri-Botanical-Garden	USA	1
1885	Nestle-Foundation-for-the-Study-of-the-Problems-of-Nutrition-in-the-World	USA	1
1886	Neurology	USA	1
1887	Neurotoxicology-and-Teratology	USA	1
1888	Nucleosides-and-Nucleotides	USA	1
1889	Ophthalmic-Surgery	USA	1
1890	Otolaryngology-Head-and-Neck-Surgery	USA	1
1891	Pancreas	USA	1
1892	Paper-American-Society-of-Agricultural-Engineers	USA	1
1893	Pediatric-Dermatology	USA	1
1894	Pediatric-Infectious-Disease-Journal	USA	1
1895	Pediatrics	USA	1
1896	Perfumer-and-Flavorist	USA	1

SI No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
1897	Pharmaceutical-Research	USA	1
1898	Plant-Breeding-Reviews	USA	1
1899	Plant-Operations-Progress	USA	1
1900	Planta	USA	1
1901	Progress-in-Clinical-and-Biological-Research	USA	1
1902	Radiology	USA	1
1903	Remote-Sensing-of-Environment	USA	1
1904	Renal-Failure	USA	1
1905	Research-Communications-in-Chemical-Pathology-and-Pharmacology	USA	1
1906	Research-Journal-of-the-Water-Pollution-Control-Federation	USA	1
1907	Science-Washington	USA	1
1908	Seminars-in-Surgical-Oncology	USA	1
1909	Sociobiology	USA	1
1910	Soil-Survey-Horizons	USA	1
1911	Solar-and-Wind-Technology	USA	1
1912	Somatic-Cell-and-Molecular-Genetics	USA	1
1913	Surgery,-Gynaecology-and-Obstetrics	USA	1
1914	Surgical-Neurology	USA	1
1915	Textile-Research-Journal	USA	1
1916	Theoretical-Population-Biology	USA	1
1917	Toxicity-Assessment	USA	1
1918	Transactions-of-the-American-Microscopical-Society	USA	1
1919	Tree-Ring-Bulletin	USA	1
1920	Tropical-Lepidoptera	USA	1
1921	Water-International	USA	1
1922	Water-Resources-Development	USA	1
1923	World-Bank-Technical-Paper	USA	1
1924	World-Journal-of-Surgery	USA	1
1925	Archivos-Latinoamericanos-de-Nutricion	Venezuela	1
1926	Revista-de-la-Facultad-de-Ciencias-Veterinarias,-Universidad-Central-de-Venezuela	Venezuela	1
1927	Acta-Entomologica-Jugoslavica	Yugoslavia	1
1928	Central-African-Journal-of-Medicine	Zimbabwe	1
			48233
1929	Journal-of-Agricultural-Issues	****	10
1930	Rice-Research-Newsletter	****	9
1931	New-dimension-in-agricultural-geography	****	8
1932	Journal-of-the-Remount-and-Veterinary-Corps	****	6
1933	Biomass gasification & congeneration in sugar complex	****	5
1934	Advances-in-tropical-acacia-research	****	3
1935	AVRDC-Publication	****	3
1936	Better-Crops-Intemational	****	3
1937	Fertilizer-Marketing	****	3
1938	Journal-of-Poultry-Science	****	2

SI No.	Journal title	Publication country	Number of papers
1939	Journal-of-Rural-Energy	****	2
1940	Tropical-tree-seed-research	****	2
1941	Avichal-Science-Foundation-Science-Series	****	1
1942	Biochemical-and-Environmental-Sciences	****	1
1943	Environmental-and-animal-Health	****	1
1944	Human-growth,-physical-fitness-and-nutrition	****	1
1945	Journal-of-Bioresources	****	1
1946	National-Resources-Forum	****	1
1947	Perspectives-in-mycological-research	****	1
1948	Pesticide-transformation-products	****	1
1949	Research-and-Development-of-Indigenous-Drugs	****	1
1950	Rickets	****	1
1951	Technical-Bulletin-National-Fertilizer-Development-Centre	****	1
1952	VSI-Bulletin	****	1
			48301
	Conference papers		1678
	Miscellaneous		966
	Book chapters and books		599
	Abstracts		82
	Standards		45
	Letters to the editor [Journal unknown]		1
	Research-on-goats:-Indian-experience		15
	Annual-reports		13
	Theses		12
	Reports		9
	Patents		2
	Unknown		38
	Total		51761

**** Journal Country Not Known

Journal countries were checked from four sources: 1. *CAB International Serials Checklist*, 1995 edition; 2. *Serial Sources for the BIOSIS Previews Database*, 1993 edition; *SCI Guide & List of Source Publications*, 1994; Ulrich CD-ROM version, 1997. Some titles were not listed in any of these sources. Also, in some cases we were not sure whether the document is a report, book, book chapter or journal article. CAB Abstracts has classified some items under the head 'Miscellaneous', and we have faithfully followed the same classification for these items. But, the error caused by this uncertainty is too small and has not affected our interpretation of the data.

Table 3: Letters journals and newsletters used by Indian agricultural researchers as seen from CAB Abstracts 1990 - 94

SI No.	Journal title	Country	Number of papers
1	International-Rice-Research-Newsletter	Philippines	352
2	National-Academy-of-Science-Letters	India	240
3	International-Chickpea-Newsletter	India	126
4	International-Nematology-Network-Newsletter	USA	90
5	International-Pigeonpea-Newsletter	India	90
6	Capsicum-Newsletter	Italy	49
7	Cruciferae-Newsletter	UK	46
8	Maize-Genetics-Cooperation-News-Letter	USA	46
9	International-Arachis-Newsletter	India	45
10	Plant-Pathology-Newsletter	UK	43
11	Plant-Cell-Incompatibility-Newsletter	USA	38
12	Biotechnology-Letters	UK	33
13	Virus-Information-Exchange-Newsletter-for-South-East-Asia-and-the-Western-Pacific	Australia	32
14	FEMS-Microbiology-Letters	Netherlands	28
15	Mutation-Breeding-Newsletter	Austria	28
16	Letters-in-Applied-Microbiology	UK	27
17	Plant-Genetic-Resources-Newsletter	Italy	23
18	FABIS-Newsletter	Syria	19
19	Soybean-Genetics-Newsletter	USA	18
20	Newsletter-Associated-Agricultural-Development-Foundation	India	16
21	Sorghum-Newsletter	South Africa	14
22	Microbios-Letters	UK	9
23	Rice-Research-Newsletter	Unknown **	9
24	Toxicology-Letters	Netherlands	9
25	FEBS-Letters	Netherlands	8
26	IBPGR-Newsletter-for-Asia,-the-Pacific-and-Oceania	Netherlands	8
27	Quarterly-Newsletter-Asia-and-Pacific-Plant-Protection-Commission	Thailand	8
28	Journal-of-Radioanalytical-and-Nuclear-Chemistry,-Letters	Switzerland	7
29	Onion-Newsletter-for-the-Tropics	UK	7
30	Plant-Breeding-News-Letter	India	7
31	Sugarcane-Breeding-Institute-News-Letter	India	7
32	Bacterial-Wilt-Newsletter	Australia	6
33	Newsletter-Central-Sericultural-Research-and-Training-Institute,-Mysore	India	6
34	Newsletter-Sugarcane-Breeding-Institute	India	6
35	Analytical-Letters	USA	5
36	Cancer-Letters	Ireland	5
37	CIMAP-Newsletter	India	5
38	Biomedical-Letters	UK	4
39	Capsicum-and-Eggplant-Newsletter	Italy	4
40	NBRI-Newsletter	India	4

SI No.	Journal title	Country	Number of papers
41	Newsletter-National-Horticultural-Research-and-Development-Foundation	India	4
42	Lens-Newsletter	Syria	3
43	Mutation-Research,-Mutation-Research-Letters	Netherlands	3
44	Cassava-Newsletter	Colombia	2
45	Cryo-letters	UK	2
46	Newsletter-UPASI-Tea-Research-Institute	India	2
47	Rat-News-Letter	USA	2
48	Tetrahedron-Letters	UK	2
49	ACIAR-Food-Legume-Newsletter	Australia	1
50	Asparagus-Research-Newsletter	New Zealand	1
51	Bioorganic-and-Medicinal-Chemistry-Letters	UK	1
52	Camel-Newsletter	Syria	1
53	Earth-and-Planetary-Science-Letters	Netherlands	1
54	FAO-Aquaculture-Newsletter	Italy	1
55	ICSSR-Newsletter	India	1
56	Immunology-Letters	Netherlands	1
57	International-Aerobiology-Newsletter	USA	1
58	International-Rice-Commission-Newsletter	Italy	1
59	IUCN-Forest-Conservation-Programme-Newsletter	Switzerland	1
60	Journal-of-Materials-Science-Letters	UK	1
61	Newsletter -International-Herbage-Seed-Production-Research-Group	New Zealand	1
Total			1560

Table 4: Country of publication of the journals used by Indian researchers as seen from *CAB Abstracts 1990 - 94* (Arranged by number of papers)

Sl No.	Publication country	Number of journals	Number of papers	% of papers in world journals
1	India	483	37178	76.96
2	UK	357	2742	5.68
3	USA	352	1888	3.91
4	Netherlands	127	1245	2.58
5	Germany	124	1100	2.28
6	Italy	43	667	1.38
7	Philippines	12	468	0.97
8	Japan	36	427	0.88
9	France	42	240	0.5
10	Belgium	9	193	
11	Ireland	14	176	
12	Thailand	15	172	
13	Australia	27	171	
14	Switzerland	27	150	
15	Czech Republic	5	123	
16	Kenya	6	115	
17	Hungary	14	112	
18	Poland	19	94	
19	Trinidad & Tobago	1	90	
20	Canada	23	87	
21	Malaysia	10	76	
22	Pakistan	14	73	
23	Taiwan	7	68	
24	Denmark	16	53	
25	Austria	7	49	
26	Syria	4	43	
27	Czechoslovakia	7	37	
28	Bangladesh	12	36	
29	Brazil	12	30	
30	Slovakia	3	30	
31	Sweden	9	30	
32	Israel	6	29	
33	Egypt	6	28	
34	Yugoslavia	3	22	
35	South Africa	6	20	
36	Hong Kong	4	15	
37	Romania	3	14	
38	Korea	2	12	
39	Sri Lanka	5	12	
40	Norway	3	11	

SI No.	Publication country	Number of journals	Number of papers	% of papers in world journal
41	Spain	4	11	
42	China	5	7	
43	Croatia	1	7	
44	New Zealand	6	7	
45	Singapore	4	7	
46	Slovenia	1	7	
47	Turkey	1	7	
48	Chile	1	6	
49	Mexico	4	6	
50	Nepal	3	6	
51	Costa Rica	2	4	
52	Nigeria	1	4	
53	Russia	3	4	
54	Zimbabwe	2	4	
55	Bhutan	1	3	
56	Colombia	2	3	
57	Indonesia	1	2	
58	Venezuela	2	2	
59	Zaire	1	2	
60	Argentina	1	1	
61	Ethiopia	1	1	
62	Greece	1	1	
63	Iran	1	1	
64	Jordan	1	1	
65	Lebanon	1	1	
66	Namibia	1	1	
67	Sultanate Of Oman	1	1	
	Unknown	24	68	
	Total	1952	48301	

**Table 5: Indian journals covered by CAB Abstracts 1990 - 94
(Arranged by number of papers)**

Sl No.	Journal title	Number of papers
1	Indian-Veterinary-Journal	1336
2	Indian-Journal-of-Animal-Sciences	1287
3	Indian-Journal-of-Agricultural-Sciences	959
4	Indian-Journal-of-Agronomy	951
5	Indian-Phytopathology	831
6	Journal-of-the-Indian-Society-of-Soil-Science	784
7	Journal-of-Maharashtra-Agricultural-Universities	754
8	Madras-Agricultural-Journal	751
9	Indian-Forester	717
10	Indian-Journal-of-Dairy-Science	682
11	Environment-and-Ecology	604
12	Current-Science	580
13	South-Indian-Horticulture	491
14	Indian-Journal-of-Experimental-Biology	434
15	Indian-Journal-of-Entomology	429
16	Indian-Journal-of-Mycology-and-Plant-Pathology	415
17	Indian-Journal-of-Forestry	392
18	Indian-Journal-of-Genetics-and-Plant-Breeding	364
19	Annals-of-Agricultural-Research	361
20	Current-Research-University-of-Agricultural-Sciences-Bangalore	360
21	Indian-Journal-of-Plant-Physiology	349
22	Indian-Journal-of-Horticulture	320
23	Plant-Disease-Research	307
24	Indian-Journal-of-Animal-Nutrition	303
25	Indian-Journal-of-Nematology	290
26	Crop-Research-Hisar	287
27	Indian-Journal-of-Plant-Protection	281
28	Journal-of-Insect-Science	281
29	Fertiliser-News	268
30	Indian-Dairyman	264
31	Indian-Farming	262
32	Mysore-Journal-of-Agricultural-Science	242
33	Indian-Journal-of-Animal-Reproduction	241
34	National-Academy-of-Science-Letters	240
35	Orysa	236
36	Haryana-Journal-of-Horticultural-Sciences	234
37	Advances-in-Plant-Sciences	231
38	Journal-of-Research,-Punjab-Agricultural-University	228
39	Indian-Journal-of-Weed-Science	225
40	Progressive-Horticulture	225

Sl No.	Journal title	Number of papers
41	Entomon	224
42	Crop-Improvement	221
43	Indian-Journal-of-Poultry-Science	220
44	Agricultural-Situation-in-India	217
45	PKV-Research-Journal	214
46	Indian-Veterinary-Medical-Journal	203
47	Journal-of-Oilseeds-Research	202
48	Haryana-Journal-of-Agronomy	200
49	Karnataka-Journal-of-Agricultural-Sciences	194
50	Cheiron	192
51	<i>Acta-Botanica-Indica</i>	190
52	Agricultural-Science-Digest-Kamal	187
53	Orissa-Journal-of-Agricultural-Research	186
54	Annals-of-Plant-Physiology	183
55	Haryana-Agricultural-University-Journal-of-Research	176
56	Indian-Sugar	176
57	Journal-of-Entomological-Research	176
58	Livestock-Adviser	176
59	Indian-Agriculturist	171
60	Research-and-Development-Reporter	170
61	Indian-Journal-of-Pulses-Research	169
62	<i>Vegetable-Science</i>	169
63	Current-Nematology	167
64	International-Journal-of-Tropical-Agriculture	164
65	Indian-Journal-of-Agricultural-Economics	160
66	Indian-Journal-of-Medical-Research	159
67	Gujarat-Agricultural-University-Research-Journal	157
68	Indian-Perfumer	157
69	Van-Vigyan	156
70	Journal-of-Plantation-Crops	151
71	Legume-Research	150
72	Indian-Journal-of-Parasitology	145
73	<i>Indian-Journal-of-Sericulture</i>	144
74	Pesticides	144
75	Journal-of-Veterinary-Parasitology	143
76	Indian-Journal-of-Veterinary-Medicine	142
77	Journal-of-Nuclear-Agriculture-and-Biology	142
78	Proceedings-of-the-Indian-National-Science-Academy	142
79	Indian-Journal-of-Animal-Health	139
80	Indian-Journal-of-Animal-Production-and-Management	139
81	Indian-Journal-of-Helminthology	138
82	Indian-Cocoa,-Areca-nut-and-Spices-Journal	136
83	Journal-of-Potassium-Research	136
84	<i>Indian-Journal-of-Virology</i>	132
85	Poultry-Advisor	131
86	Journal-of-Communicable-Diseases	130

Sl No.	Journal title	Number of papers
87	Journal-of-Food-Science-and-Technology-Mysore	130
88	Plant-Protection-Bulletin-Faridabad	130
89	Bulletin-of-Entomology-New-Delhi	129
90	Indian-Journal-of-Plant-Pathology	127
91	International-Chickpea-Newsletter	126
92	New-Agriculturist	123
93	Pesticide-Research-Journal	122
94	Cooperative-Sugar	120
95	Journal-of-Research,-Andhra-Pradesh-Agricultural-University	120
96	Journal-of-the-Indian-Society-for-Cotton-Improvement	118
97	Journal-of-Rural-Development-Hyderabad	117
98	Indian-Journal-of-Agricultural-Research	116
99	Seed-Research	115
100	Annals-of-Arid-Zone	112
101	Indian-Journal-of-Malariology	109
102	Journal-of-Soils-and-Crops	106
103	Journal-of-Environmental-Biology	104
104	Indian-Bee-Journal	103
105	Narendra-Deva-Journal-of-Agricultural-Research	103
106	Uttar-Pradesh-Journal-of-Zoology	102
107	Myforest	100
108	Journal-of-Biological-Control	99
109	Indian-Pediatrics	98
110	Indian-Coconut-Journal-Cochin	97
111	Proceedings-of-the-Indian-Academy-of-Sciences,-Plant-Sciences	97
112	Himachal-Journal-of-Agricultural-Research	96
113	Journal-of-the-Indian-Potato-Association	96
114	Bharatiya-Sugar	95
115	Bioved	95
116	SISSTA-Sugar-Journal	93
117	Tobacco-Research	91
118	International-Pigeonpea-Newsletter	90
119	Indian-Journal-of-Ecology	89
120	Journal-of-Root-Crops	89
121	Indian-Journal-of-Hill-Farming	88
122	Proceedings-of-the-Indian-Academy-of-Sciences,-Animal-Sciences	88
123	Phytomorphology	87
124	Indian-Cooperative-Review	86
125	Journal-of-Coffee-Research	86
126	Plant-Physiology-and-Biochemistry-New-Delhi	86
127	Journal-of-the-Timber-Development-Association-of-India	85
128	Asian-Journal-of-Dairy-Research	84
129	Indian-Journal-of-Agricultural-Marketing	83
130	Indian-Journal-of-Animal-Research	82
131	Agricultural-Research-Journal-of-Kerala	81
132	Journal-of-the-Andaman-Science-Association	81

Sl No.	Journal title	Number of papers
133	Journal-of-Mycopathological-Research	80
134	Journal-of-Research,-Birsa-Agricultural-University	80
135	Annals-of-Biology-Ludhiana	79
136	Annals-of-Entomology	79
137	Indian-Journal-of-Nutrition-and-Dietetics	79
138	Bharatiya-Krishi-Anusandhana-Patrika	78
139	Indian-Journal-of-Applied-and-Pure-Biology	78
140	Journal-of-Tropical-Forestry	78
141	Farming-Systems	77
142	Indian-Journal-of-Microbiology	77
143	International-Journal-of-Tropical-Plant-Diseases	77
144	Pestology	77
145	Economic-Affairs-Calcutta	74
146	Indian-Journal-of-Pharmaceutical-Sciences	71
147	Two-and-a-Bud	71
148	Horticultural-Journal	69
149	Tropical-Ecology	69
150	Farm-Science-Journal	68
151	Indian-Botanical-Reporter	68
152	Indian-Journal-of-Biochemistry-and-Biophysics	66
153	International-Journal-of-Animal-Sciences	65
154	Journal-of-the-Indian-Academy-of-Wood-Science	64
155	Research-Bulletin-of-the-Panjab-University	64
156	Comparative-Physiology-and-Ecology	63
157	Agricultural-Reviews-Karnal	62
158	Groundnut-News	62
159	Indian-Horticulture	62
160	Seeds-and-Farms	62
161	Journal-of-Advanced-Zoology	61
162	Journal-of-Aphidology	61
163	Journal-of-the-Oil-Technologists'-Association-of-India	61
164	Range-Management-and-Agroforestry	60
165	Biovigyanam	59
166	Indian-Journal-of-Comparative-Microbiology,-Immunology-and-Infectious-Diseases	59
167	Journal-of-Phytological-Research	57
168	Journal-of-the-Bombay-Natural-History-Society	57
169	Agricultural-Marketing	53
170	Current-Agriculture	51
171	Punjab-Horticultural-Journal	51
172	Indian-Journal-of-Veterinary-Pathology	50
173	Journal-of-Biosciences	47
174	Orissa-Journal-of-Horticulture	47
175	Indian-Journal-of-Agricultural-Engineering	46
176	Indian-Journal-of-Medical-Research.-Section-A,-Infectious-Diseases	45
177	International-Arachis-Newsletter	45

Sl No.	Journal title	Number of papers
178	Journal-of-Veterinary-and-Animal-Sciences	43
179	Indian-Journal-of-Natural-Rubber-Research	42
180	Journal-of-Ecobiology	42
181	Nucleus-Calcutta	42
182	Journal-of-the-Orchid-Society-of-India	41
183	Social-Change-New-Delhi	40
184	Journal-of-Ecotoxicology-and-Environmental-Monitoring	39
185	NBSS-Publication	39
186	Annals-of-Plant-Protection-Sciences	38
187	International-Journal-of-Ecology-and-Environmental-Sciences	38
188	Centaur-Mylapore	36
189	Geobios-New-Reports	36
190	Journal-of-Aquaculture-in-the-Tropics	36
191	Advances-in-horticulture:-fruit-crops	35
192	Clay-Research	35
193	Bihar-Journal-of-Agricultural-Marketing	34
194	Experimental-Genetics	34
195	Proceedings-of-the-Indian-National-Science-Academy.-Part-B,- Biological-Sciences	34
196	Rubber-Board-Bulletin	34
197	Indian-Coffee	33
198	Indian-Journal-of-Public-Health	33
199	Pashudhan	33
200	Journal-of-Bengal-Natural-History-Society	32
201	Journal-of-the-Indian-Society-of-Coastal-Agricultural-Research	32
202	Journal-of-Dairying,-Foods-and-Home-Sciences	31
203	Indian-Journal-of-Environmental-Health	30
204	Journal-of-Spices-and-Aromatic-Crops	30
205	Indian-Journal-of-Regional-Science	29
206	Indian-Journal-of-Indigenous-Medicines	28
207	Indian-Review-of-Life-Sciences	28
208	Vaniki-Sandesh	28
209	Advances-in-management-and-conservation-of-soil-fauna	27
210	Agricultural-Engineering-Today	27
211	Indian-Journal-of-Helminthology-New-Series	27
212	Indian-Journal-of-Mycological-Research	27
213	Journal-of-Research-Assam-Agricultural-University	27
214	Journal-of-the-Assam-Science-Society	27
215	Journal-of-the-Assam-Veterinary-Council	27
216	Jute-Development-Journal	27
217	Maharashtra-Journal-of-Horticulture	27
218	Hindustan-Antibiotics-Bulletin	26
219	Journal-of-Agricultural-Engineering	26
220	Annals-of-Forestry	25
221	Journal-of-Scientific-and-Industrial-Research	25
222	Journal-of-Veterinary-Physiology-and-Allied-Sciences	25

Sl No.	Journal title	Number of papers
223	Wool-and-Woolens-of-India	25
224	Journal-of-Tree-Sciences	24
225	Phytophaga	24
226	Afro-Asian-Journal-of-Nematology	23
227	Indian-Journal-of-Dryland-Agricultural-Research-and-Development	23
228	Evergreen-Trichur	22
229	Indian-Geographical-Journal	22
230	Journal-of-Genetics	22
231	Cashew-Bulletin	21
232	National-Bank-News-Review-Bombay	21
233	Fertiliser-Marketing-News	20
234	Indian-Journal-of-Agricultural-Chemistry	19
235	Journal-of-Bombay-Veterinary-College	19
236	Journal-of-Microbial-Biotechnology	19
237	Journal-of-Rural-Reconstruction	19
238	Transactions-of-Indian-Society-of-Desert-Technology	19
239	Kerala-Journal-of-Veterinary-Science	18
240	Journal-of-Research-Rajendra-Agricultural-University	17
241	Journal-of-the-Indian-Medical-Association	17
242	Mushroom-Research	17
243	New-Botanist	17
244	Agropedology	16
245	Indian-Drugs	16
246	Indian-Journal-of-Marine-Sciences	16
247	Indian-Standard	16
248	JNKVV-Research-Journal	16
249	Mausam	16
250	Moving-Technology	16
251	Newsletter-Associated-Agricultural-Development-Foundation	16
252	Advances-in-Forestry-Research-in-India	15
253	Advances-in-Himalayan-ecology	15
254	Indian-Textile-Journal	15
255	Proceedings-of-the-Nutrition-Society-of-India	15
256	Social-Action-New-Delhi	15
257	Annals-of-the-National-Association-of-Geographers	14
258	Chemical-Engineering-World	14
259	KFRI-Research-Report	14
260	Plant-Material-Description	14
261	Poultry-Today-and-Tomorrow	14
262	Indian-Journal-of-Veterinary-Anatomy	13
263	Journal-of-the-Indian-Institute-of-Science	13
264	Financing-Agriculture	12
265	Gujvet	12
266	Indian-Journal-of-Dermatology	12
267	Bulletin-United-Planters'-Association-of-Southern-India	11
268	Indian-Journal-of-Landscape-Systems-and-Ecological-Studies	11

Sl No.	Journal title	Number of papers
269	Journal-of-Applied-Animal-Research	11
270	Journal-of-Association-of-Physicians-of-India	11
271	Journal-of-the-Maharashtra-Agricultural-Universities	11
272	Kavaka	11
273	Sharkara-Kanpur	11
274	Afro-Asian-Nematology-Network	10
275	Cecidologia-Internationale	10
276	Indian-Journal-of-Economics	10
277	Indian-Journal-of-Environmental-Protection	10
278	Indian-Journal-of-Mushrooms	10
279	Indian-Journal-of-Veterinary-Surgery	10
280	Orissa-Veterinary-Journal	10
281	Planters'-Chronicle	10
282	State-Bank-of-India-Monthly-Review	10
283	VET-Mhow	10
284	Artha-Vijnana	9
285	Haryana-Veterinarian	9
286	Indian-Economic-Review	9
287	Indian-Journal-of-Labour-Economics	9
288	Journal-of-Parasitology-and-Applied-Animal-Biology	9
289	Journal-of-the-Agricultural-Science-Society-of-North-East-India	9
290	Journal-of-the-Indian-School-of-Political-Economy	9
291	Journal-of-the-National-Botanical-Society	9
292	Margin	9
293	Advances-in-Forestry-Research-in-India,-Volume-V	8
294	Biology-Education	8
295	Indian-Journal-of-Medical-Research.-Section-B,-Biomedical-Research-other-than-Infectious-Diseases	8
296	Journal-of-Ravishankar-University	8
297	Journal-of-Social-Research-Ranchi	8
298	Journal-of-the-Marine-Biological-Association-of-India	8
299	Magazine,-College-of-Agriculture	8
300	Science-and-Culture	8
301	Zoology,-Journal-of-Pure-and-Applied-Zoology	8
302	Allelopathy-Journal	7
303	Conserving-Indian-environment	7
304	Cotton-Development	7
305	Current-Research-Reporter,-Mahatma-Phule-Agricultural-University	7
306	ICID-Bulletin	7
307	Indian-Cashew-Journal	7
308	Indian-Journal-of-Heredity	7
309	IPPTA	7
310	Journal-of-Economic-and-Taxonomic-Botany	7
311	Neo-Botanica	7
312	Plant-Breeding-News-Letter	7
313	Sugarcane-Breeding-Institute-News-Letter	7

Sl No.	Journal title	Number of papers
314	Calcutta-Medical-Journal	6
315	Changing-Villages	6
316	Indian-Food-Industry	6
317	Indian-Journal-of-Veterinary-Research	6
318	Journal-of-Animal-Morphology-and-Physiology	6
319	Journal-of-Extension-Systems	6
320	Journal-of-Research-and-Education-in-Indian-Medicine	6
321	Man-in-India	6
322	National-Medical-Journal-of-India	6
323	Newsletter-Central-Sericultural-Research-and-Training-Institute,- Mysore	6
324	Newsletter-Sugarcane-Breeding-Institute	6
325	Proceedings-of-the-Indian-National-Science-Academy,-Part-B,- Biological-Sciences	6
326	Proceedings-of-the-National-Academy-of-Sciences,-India	6
327	SARAS-Journal-of-Livestock-and-Poultry-Production	6
328	South-Asian-Anthropologist	6
329	Sustainable-development-of-the-Indian-arid-zone:-a-research- perspective	6
330	Allelopathy:-basic-and-applied-aspects	5
331	Anvesak	5
332	Chemical-Age-of-India	5
333	CIMAP-Newsletter	5
334	Indian-Journal-of-Public-Administration	5
335	Indian-Journal-of-Rubber-Research	5
336	Indian-Journal-of-Technology	5
337	Journal-of-Living-World	5
338	Journal-of-the-Indian-Chemical-Society	5
339	Working-Paper -Indian-Institute-of-Management,-Ahmedabad	5
340	Better-Farming-in-Salt-Affected-Soils	4
341	Bulletin-of-the-Botanical-Society-of-Bengal	4
342	Discussion-Paper -Indira-Gandhi-Institute-of-Development- Research	4
343	IIHR-News	4
344	Indian-Biologist	4
345	Indian-Chemical-Engineer	4
346	Indian-Economic-Journal	4
347	Indian-Journal-of-Adult-Education	4
348	Indian-Journal-of-Animal-Production	4
349	Indian-Journal-of-Medical-Sciences	4
350	Indian-Journal-of-Pediatrics	4
351	Journal-of-Farming-Systems	4
352	Journal-of-Nature-Conservation	4
353	Journal-of-Plant-Biochemistry-and-Biotechnology	4
354	Journal-of-the-Geological-Society-of-India	4
355	Journal-of-the-Indian-Society-of-Cotton-Improvement	4

Sl No.	Journal title	Number of papers
356	Journal-of-the-Institution-of-Chemists,-Calcutta	4
357	Lal-Baugh	4
358	Medical-Journal-Armed-Forces-India	4
359	National-Geographical-Journal-of-India	4
360	NBRI-Newsletter	4
361	New farmers' movements in India	4
362	Newsletter-National-Horticultural-Research-and-Development-Foundation	4
363	NFI-Bulletin	4
364	Pacific-and-Asian-Journal-of-Energy	4
365	Poultry-Guide	4
366	Tourism-Recreation-Research	4
367	Urja	4
368	Wastelands-News	4
369	Annals-of-Medical-Entomology	3
370	Bulletin-of-Grain-Technology	3
371	Geophytology	3
372	Gujarat-Agricultural-Research-Journal	3
373	Himachal-Journal-of-Environmental-Zoology	3
374	Indian Society for Parasitology	3
375	Indian-Heart-Journal	3
376	Indian-Journal-of-Experimental-Botany	3
377	Indian-Journal-of-Industrial-Relations	3
378	Indian-Veterinary-Reporter	3
379	ISCI-Journal,-Indian-Society-for-Cotton-Improvement	3
380	Journal-of-Industrial-Pollution-Control	3
381	Journal-of-the-Indian-Society-of-Agricultural-Statistics	3
382	Journal-of-the-Institution-of-Engineers-India	3
383	Manpower-Journal	3
384	Proceeding-of-the-Indian-Academy-of-Sciences,-Earth-and-Planetary-Sciences	3
385	Proceedings-of-the-Indian-Academy-of-Sciences,-Chemical-Sciences	3
386	Recent-Researches-in-Ecology,-Environment-and-Pollution	3
387	Research-and-Industry-New-Delhi	3
388	TISGLOW	3
389	Working-Paper-Series -Sustainable-Forest-Management,-Ford-Foundation	3
390	Bulletin-of-the-Indian-Association-of-Lady-Veterinarians	2
391	Bulletin-Postgraduate-Institute-of-Medical-Education-and-Research,-Chandigarh	2
392	Contributions-to-Indian-Sociology	2
393	Entomol.-Res.,-New-Delhi	2
394	Geographical-Review-of-India	2
395	Health-and-Population-Perspectives-and-Issues	2

SI No.	Journal title	Number of papers
396	ICMF-Journal,-Indian-Cotton-Manufacturers-Federation	2
397	Indian-Academy-of-Sciences	2
398	Indian-Food-Packer	2
399	Indian-Journal-of-Botany	2
400	Indian-Journal-of-Power-and-River-Valley-Development	2
401	Indian-Journal-of-Textile-Research	2
402	Indian-Journal-Poultry-Science	2
403	Irrigation-and-Power-New-Delhi	2
404	Journal-of-Financial-Management-and-Analysis	2
405	Journal-of-Palynology	2
406	Journal-of-the-Indian-Society-of-Coastal-Research	2
407	Kanpur-University-Research-Journal-Science	2
408	Khadi-Gramodyog	2
409	Medicinal-and-Aromatic-Plants-Abstracts	2
410	Newsletter-UPASI-Tea-Research-Institute	2
411	Pashudhan-Anushandhan	2
412	Prajnan	2
413	Proceedings-of-the-Indian-Academy-of-Sciences,-Earth-and-Planetary-Sciences	2
414	Research-Bulletin-International-Crops-Research-Institute-for-the-Semi-Arid-Tropics	2
415	Transactions-of-the-Bose-Research-Institute	2
416	Vatika-from-the-Seed-and-Plant-People	2
417	Working-Paper -Gujarat-Institute-of-Area-Planning	2
418	Administrator	1
419	Advances-in-Biosciences-Muzaffamagar	1
420	Agricultural-Science-Digest-Karnal	1
421	Alternative-Appropriate-Technologies-in-Agriculture	1
422	Ancient-Science-of-Life	1
423	Applied-Botany-Abstracts	1
424	Asian-Journal-of-Plant-Science	1
425	Bay-of-Bengal-News	1
426	Bio-Science-Research-Bulletin	1
427	Bulletin-of-Electrochemistry	1
428	China-Report-New-Delhi	1
429	CSIR-News	1
430	Eastern-Anthropologist	1
431	Economics-and-Social-Science-Review	1
432	Electrical-India	1
433	Everyman's-Science	1
434	Future-New-Delhi	1
435	Geophysical-Research-Bulletin	1
436	ICRISAT-Information-Bulletin	1
437	ICSSR-Newsletter	1
438	Indian-Journal-of-Chemistry,-Section-A,-Inorganic,-Bio-inorganic,-Physical,-Theoretical-and-Analytical-Chemistry	1

Sl No.	Journal title	Number of papers
439	Indian-Journal-of-Earth-Sciences	1
440	Indian-Journal-of-Gastroenterology	1
441	Indian-Journal-of-Pure-and-Applied-Biology	1
442	Indian-Journal-of-Quantitative-Economics	1
443	Indian-Journal-of-Social-Science	1
444	Indian-Journal-of-Tuberculosis	1
445	Indian-perfumer	1
446	International-Journal-of-Development-Planning-Literature	1
447	Irrigation-and-Power-Journal	1
448	Journal-of-Biosocial-Science	1
449	Journal-of-Feed-Science-and-Technology-Mysore	1
450	Journal-of-Recent-Advances-in-Applied-Sciences	1
451	Journal-of-the-Electrochemical-Society-of-India	1
452	Journal-of-the-Indian-Botanical-Society	1
453	Journal-of-the-Indian-Society-of-Coastal-Aquacultural-Research	1
454	Journal-Oilseeds-Research	1
455	KFRI-Information-Bulletin	1
456	Memoirs-Geological-Society-of-India	1
457	Memoirs-of-the-Entomological-Society-of-India	1
458	Mendel	1
459	MFP-News	1
460	National-Bank-News-Bombay	1
461	Paintindia	1
462	Photonirvachak-Dehra-Dun	1
463	Proceedings-of-the-Academy-of-Sciences,-Earth-and-Planetary-Sciences	1
464	Proceedings-of-the-Annual-Convention-of-the-Sugar-Technologists-Association-of-India	1
465	Proceedings-of-the-Indian-Academy-of-Parasitology	1
466	Proceedings-of-the-Indian-Academy-of-Science	1
467	Proceedings-of-the-Indian-National-Science-Academy.-Part-A,-Physical-Sciences	1
468	Progress-Report-Economics-Group,-Resource-Management-Program-ICRISAT	1
469	Progressive-Farming-Ludhiana	1
470	Records-of-the-Zoological-Survey-of-India	1
471	Regional-Journal-of-Energy,-Heat-and-Mass-Transfer	1
472	Research-and-Industry	1
473	Research-Bulletin-Central-Research-Institute-for-Dryland-Agriculture	1
474	Research-Paper-Institute-of-Rural-Management, Anand	1
475	Research-Publication -Mahatma-Phule-Krishi-Vidyapeeth	1
476	Science-Age	1
477	Science-and-Environment	1
478	Southern-Economist	1
479	Sugarcane-Breeding-Institute-Quarterly	1
480	Technical-Bulletin-Project-Directorate-of-Biological-Control,-ICAR	1

Sl No.	Journal title	Number of papers
481	Tool-and-Alloy-Steels	1
482	Toxin-related-diseases	1
483	Working-Paper -Institute-of-Rural-Management-Anand	1
Total		37175

**Table 6: Indian research papers covered by CAB Abstracts 1990 - 94
classified by subfields (Arranged by number of papers)**

Sl Class No. code	Subfield name	Number of papers
1 FF600	Pests, Pathogens and Biogenic Diseases of Plants	8898
2 FF020	Plant Breeding and Genetics	5675
3 FF100	Plant Production	5231
4 LL820	Parasites, Vectors, Pathogens and Biogenic Diseases of Animals	2222
5 HH400	Control by Chemicals and Drugs	1465
6 FF060	Plant Physiology and Biochemistry	1335
7 VV200	Parasites, Vectors, Pathogens and Biogenic Diseases of Humans	1302
8 KK100	Forestry (General)	1102
9 JJ700	Fertilizers and other Amendments	1086
10 FF040	Plant Composition	987
11 QQ010	Milk and Dairy Produce	785
12 LL900	Animal Toxicology, Poisoning and Pharmacology	746
13 LL200	Animal Breeding and Genetics	664
14 LL210	Animal Reproduction and Development	578
15 LL520	Animal Nutrition (Production Responses)	557
16 FF000	Plants of Economic Importance (General)	547
17 JJ400	Soil Morphology, Formation and Classification	486
18 FF500	Weeds and Noxious Plants	469
19 KK110	Silviculture	464
20 FF400	Mycorrhizas and Fungi of Economic Importance; Symbiotic Nitrogen Fixation	445
21 QQ020	Sugar and Sugar Refining	423
22 FF061	Plant Nutrition	418
23 LL220	Animal Genetics	396
24 FF160	Plant Propagation	386
25 LL860	Animal Disorders (Not caused by Organisms)	365
26 HH100	Biological Control	347
27 TT300	Medical and Veterinary Entomology Records (Discontinued)	342
28 LL100	Animal Husbandry (General)	336
29 ZZ380	Taxonomy and Evolution	336
30 EE200	Farming Systems and Management	311
31 LL600	Animal Physiology and Biochemistry (Excluding Nutrition)	297
32 LL110	Animal Husbandry (Dairy)	291
33 JJ200	Soil Chemistry and Mineralogy	289
34 FF150	Plant Cropping Systems	279
35 PP600	Pollution and Degradation	271
36 ZZ900	Techniques and Methodology	267
37 FF030	Plant Morphology and Structure	263
38 LL510	Animal Nutrition (Physiology)	261

SI Class No. code	Subfield name	Number of papers
39 QQ500	Food Composition and Quality	240
40 RR300	Feed Composition and Quality	236
41 FF062	Plant-Water Relations	234
42 VV000	Biotechnology	231
43 HH000	Pathogen, Pest and Parasite Management (General)	229
44 HH600	Host Resistance and Immunity	227
45 EE130	Supply, Demand and Prices	221
46 LL020	Sericulture	203
47 VV130	Diet and Diet-related Diseases	202
48 JJ300	Soil Physics	198
49 LL010	Beekeeping and Bees	196
50 JJ100	Soil Biology	195
51 FF170	in vitro Culture of Plant Material	190
52 VV120	Physiology of Human Nutrition	182
53 KK150	Other Land Use	179
54 KK510	<i>Wood Properties and Utilization</i>	169
55 FF900	Environmental Tolerance of Plants	166
56 PP400	Erosion; Soil and Water Conservation	160
57 VV140	<i>Human Nutrition (Animal Models)</i>	160
58 JJ800	Soil Water Management	160
59 MM120	Aquaculture (Animals)	156
60 EE700	Distribution and Marketing of Products	153
61 EE120	Policy and Planning (General)	147
62 EE520	Food Industry	146
63 PP710	Biological Resources (Animal)	144
64 LL880	Animal Treatment and Diagnosis (Non Drug)	136
65 SS300	Biodeterioration (General)	136
66 XX200	Plant Wastes	129
67 QQ200	Food Contamination, Residues and Toxicology	127
68 SS210	Biodeterioration, Storage Problems and Pests of Plant Products	126
69 JJ600	Soil Fertility	122
70 QQ111	Biodeterioration, Storage Problems and Pests of Food	121
71 ZZ000	Auxiliary Disciplines	116
72 SS200	Agricultural Products (Plant)	111
73 PP720	Biological Resources (Plant)	110
74 EE800	Investment, Finance and Credit	110
75 KK120	Forest Mensuration and Management	106
76 QQ050	Crop Produce	104
77 JJ500	Soil Surveys and Land Evaluation	103
78 VV110	Diet Studies and Health	102
79 XX400	Industrial Wastes and Effluents	101
80 HH700	Other Control Measures	95
81 XX000	Wastes (General)	94
82 ZZ390	General Microbiology	93

SI Class No. code	Subfield name	Number of papers
83 EE900	<i>Labour and Employment</i>	91
84 PP500	Meteorology and Climate	91
85 PP100	Energy	87
86 VV300	Public Health and Nuisance Pests	87
87 KK600	Agroforestry	84
88 LL800	Animal Health and Hygiene (General)	84
89 EE170	Water Resources, Irrigation and Drainage Economics	80
90 LL040	Laboratory Animal Science	76
91 ZZ310	Anatomy, Morphology and Structure (General)	75
92 PP700	Biological Resources (General)	70
93 AA000	Agriculture (General)	58
94 EE145	Farm Input Utilization	56
95 VV000	Human Health and Hygiene (General)	54
96 XX700	Biodegradation Organisms	53
97 NN600	Processing Equipment and Technology	53
98 KK140	Protection Forestry	53
99 AA500	Research	51
100 LL300	Animal Behavior	50
101 HH410	Pesticide and Drug Resistance	50
102 LL500	Animal Nutrition (General)	49
103 HH300	Integrated Pest Management	49
104 NN470	Drying Equipment	48
105 RR100	Forage and Feed Processing (General)	48
106 PP210	Freshwater and Brackish Water	48
107 EE140	Input Supply Industries	47
108 PP200	Water Resources (General)	47
109 NN400	Agricultural and Forestry Equipment (General)	46
110 EE150	Environmental Economics	46
111 VV800	Human Toxicology, Poisoning and Pharmacology	43
112 EE160	Land Use and Valuation	43
113 XX600	Waste Conversion and Utilization	43
114 LL130	Animal Husbandry (Eggs)	42
115 SS230	Composition and Quality of Plant Products	42
116 KK540	Forest Products (Miscellaneous, including Minor Forest Products)	42
117 VV100	Human Nutrition (General)	41
118 NN440	<i>Irrigation and Drainage Equipment</i>	41
119 EE100	Economics (General)	40
120 EE300	Cooperatives	39
121 JJ900	Soil Cultivation	39
122 KK515	Wood Processing	39
123 QQ110	Food Storage and Preservation	38
124 EE950	Income and Poverty	38
125 FF700	Plant Disorders and Injuries (Not caused directly by Organisms)	37

SI Class No. code	Subfield name	Number of papers
126 PP300	Land Resources	36
127 EE165	Agricultural Structure and Tenure System	35
128 UU500	Women	35
129 NN453	Crop Harvesting Equipment	33
130 ZZ800	Earth Sciences (General)	33
131 UU480	Social Structure	33
132 NN450	Soil Cultivation and Handling Equipment	33
133 RR200	Feed Contamination, Residues and Toxicology	31
134 KK520	Forest Products (Wood-based Materials)	31
135 NN490	Milking and Dairy Equipment	31
136 NN461	Food and Feed Packaging Technology and Equipment	30
137 PP350	Grasslands and Rangelands	30
138 LL140	Animal Husbandry (Wool and Other Fibers)	29
139 KK530	Forest Products (Pulping and Chemical Utilization of Wood)	29
140 TT100	Medical and Veterinary Helminthology Records (Discontinued)	29
141 NN000	Engineering and Safety	27
142 TT200	Medical and Veterinary Protozoology Records (Discontinued)	27
143 NN460	Cleaning, Grading, Transport and Handling Equipment (Animal and Plant)	26
144 EE350	Industry and Enterprises	26
145 EE600	International Trade	26
146 UU300	Public Services	26
147 QQ100	Food Processing (General)	25
148 ZZ370	Genetics (General and Theoretical)	25
149 CC200	Extension and Advisory Work	24
150 ZZ200	Materials Science	24
151 NN430	Pest and Weed Control Equipment	24
152 EE110	Agricultural Economics	23
153 RR120	Microbiology of Feed Processing	23
154 UU460	Community Development	21
155 ZZ331	Plant Ecology	21
156 LL060	Draught Animals	20
157 NN300	Farm and Horticultural Structures	20
158 UU490	Social Psychology and Culture	20
159 MM300	Aquatic Biology and Ecology	19
160 UU200	Demography	19
161 CC100	Educational and Training Aids	19
162 QQ070	Other Produce	19
163 CC000	Professions, Education, Information and Training (General)	19
164 HH500	Repellents and Attractants	19
165 SS320	Biodeterioration Organisms	18
166 EE450	Development Aid, Agencies and Projects	18
167 NN700	Waste Handling and Treatment Equipment	18

SI Class No. code	Subfield name	Number of papers
168 LL120	Animal Husbandry (Meat)	17
169 NN451	Crop Sowing and Planting Equipment	16
170 EE500	Food Policy, Food Security and Food Aid	16
171 KK500	Forest Products (General)	16
172 XX300	Human Wastes and Refuse	16
173 SS310	Biodeterioration (Non-biological Products)	15
174 NN200	Farm Vehicles as Power Sources	15
175 ZZ100	Mathematics and Statistics	15
176 QQ030	Meat Produce	15
177 HH200	Environmental Pest Management	14
178 RR000	Forage and Feed Products (Non-human)	14
179 ZZ600	Chemistry	13
180 NN100	Ergonomics and Safety	13
181 RR110	Feed Storage and Preservation	12
182 QQ000	Food Science and Food Products (Human)	12
183 CC300	Information and Library Sciences	12
184 SS110	Biodeterioration, Storage Problems and Pests of Animal Products	11
185 UU350	Health Services	11
186 NN900	Other Equipment	11
187 UU100	Settlement	11
188 JJ000	Soil Science	11
189 SS100	Agricultural Products (Animal)	10
190 UU250	Human Fertility	10
191 LL070	Pets and Companion Animals	10
192 ZZ500	Physical Sciences	10
193 XX100	Animal Wastes	9
194 NN410	Aquacultural Equipment	9
195 UU700	Tourism and Travel	9
196 RR130	Feed Additives	8
197 LL050	Game Farming, Game Management and Game Utilization	8
198 BB500	History and Biography	8
199 PP000	Natural Resources (General)	8
200 PP320	Wetlands	8
201 MM000	Aquatic Sciences	7
202 BB700	Paleontology and Archaeology	7
203 LL080	Zoo Animals	7
204 EE720	Consumer Economics	6
205 LL030	Culture of Other Invertebrates (Not Aquaculture)	6
206 ZZ400	Environmental Sciences (General)	6
207 NN420	Fertilizer, Application Equipment	6
208 ZZ332	Animal Ecology	5
209 KK160	Arboriculture	5
210 MM110	Fisheries	5
211 VV600	Human Disorders (Not caused by Organisms)	5

SI Class No. code	Subfield name	Number of papers
212 VV050	Human Physiology and Biochemistry	5
213 QQ120	Microbiology of Food Processing	5
214 UU470	Participation and Self Help	5
215 LL000	Animal Science	4
216 UU360	Communication	4
217 KK130	Forest Fire Management	4
218 ZZ330	General Ecology	4
219 ZZ360	General Molecular Biology	4
220 VV060	Human Reproduction and Development	4
221 DD500	Laws and Regulations	4
222 UU600	Leisure (General)	4
223 UU620	Recreation and Sport	4
224 UU000	Sociology (General)	4
225 QQ060	Aquatic Produce	3
226 NN310	Environmental Control in Structures	3
227 UU670	Gardening, Landscaping and Landscapes	3
228 ZZ340	General Physiology	3
229 VV700	Human Treatment and Diagnosis (Non Drug)	3
230 FF800	Plant Toxicology	3
231 NN480	Animal Feeding and Watering Equipment	2
232 LL870	Animal Injuries	2
233 RR111	Biodeterioration, Storage Problems and Pests of Feed	2
234 CC400	Collections	2
235 NN452	Crop Tending Equipment	2
236 CC310	Documentation	2
237 QQ130	Food Additives	2
238 PP800	Natural Phenomena	2
239 QQ040	Poultry Produce (not Meat)	2
240 NN500	Storage equipment	2
241 LL150	Animal Husbandry (Other Products)	1
242 MM130	Aquaculture (Plants)	1
243 NN050	Computer and Electronic Systems	1
244 ZZ350	General Biochemistry	1
245 ZZ320	General Biology	1
246 VV900	Health and Safety at Work	1
247 LL700	in vitro Culture of Animal Tissue	1
248 UU640	Pastimes and Social Life	1
249 SS120	Residues and Contamination of Animal Products	1
250 CC720	Veterinary Profession	1
Total		51761

CAB Abstracts provides more than one classification codes for most papers, as a given paper may be relevant to more than one subfield. We have taken into account only the first of these classification codes.

**Table 7: Indian institutions publishing papers as seen from CAB Abstracts 1990-94
(Arranged by number of Indian papers)**

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1	Punjab Agricultural University	Ludhiana	2512
2	Haryana Agricultural University	Hissar	2377
3	Indian Agricultural Research Institute	New Delhi	1701
4	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Coimbatore	1252
5	Bidhan Chandra Krishi Vishwavidyalaya	Mohanpur	1023
6	National Dairy Research Institute	Karnal	897
7	University of Agricultural Sciences	Bangalore	840
8	Govind Ballabh Pant University of Agriculture and Technology	Pantnagar	823
9	Indian Veterinary Research Institute	Izatnagar	773
10	Banarus Hindu University	Varanasi	686
11	Forest Research Institute	Dehra Dun	662
12	International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics	Patancheru	591
13	University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology	Dharwad	585
14	Himachal Pradesh Agricultural University	Palampur	572
15	Gujarat Agricultural University	Anand	547
16	Punjabrao Agricultural University	Akola	543
17	Dr Yashwant Singh Parmar University of Horticulture and Forestry	Solan	532
18	Marathwada Agricultural University	Parbhani	530
19	Indian Institute of Horticultural Research	Bangalore	528
20	Aligarh Muslim University	Aligarh	484
21	Rajendra Agricultural University	Pusa	483
22	Andhra Pradesh Agricultural University	Hyderabad	473
23	Jawaharlal Nehru Agricultural University	Jabalpur	463
24	Mahatma Phule Agricultural University	Rahuri	441
25	Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology	Bhubaneswar	421
26	Delhi University	New Delhi	345
27	Assam Agricultural University	Jorhat	344
28	Madras Veterinary College	Madras	329
29	Chandra Shekhar Azad University of Agriculture and Technology	Kanpur	325
30	Birsa Agricultural University	Ranchi	296
31	Panjab University	Chandigarh	279
32	Central Rice Research Institute	Cuttack	270
33	Central Institute of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants	Lucknow	262
34	Narendra Deva University of Agriculture and Technology	Faizabad	259
35	Central Drug Research Institute	Lucknow	256

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
36	Calcutta University	Calcutta	251
37	Sher-e-Kashmir University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology	Srinagar	225
38	Gorakhpur University	Gorakhpur	221
39	Institute of Arid Zone Forestry Research	Jodhpur	220
40	Central Food Technological Research Institute	Mysore	210
41	Bhabha Atomic Energy Research Centre	Bombay	205
42	Indian Grassland and Fodder Research Institute	Jhansi	201
43	Sri Venkateswara University	Tirupati	201
44	University of Madras	Madras	194
45	Osmania University	Hyderabad	188
46	Jawaharal Nehru University	New Delhi	181
47	National Botanical Research Institute	Lucknow	180
48	University of Rajasthan	Jaipur	176
49	Central Soil Salinity Research Institute	Karnal	169
50	Post Graduate Institute of Medical Education and Research	Chandigarh	167
51	Allahabad University	Allahabad	166
52	Indian Institute of Science	Bangalore	156
53	University of Kalyani	Kalyani	154
54	Bhagalpur University	Bhagalpur	153
55	Lucknow University	Lucknow	149
56	Konkan Agricultural University	Dapoli	147
57	Central Avian Research Institute	Izatnagar	144
58	Central Sericultural Research and Training Institute	Mysore	142
59	Indian Institute of Sugarcane Research	Lucknow	141
60	Central Potato Research Institute	Shimla	140
61	Kumaun University	Nainital	140
62	Kerala Forest Research Institute	Peechi	138
63	Kakatiya University	Warangal	134
64	North-Eastern Hill University	Shillong	129
65	National Institute of Nutrition	Hyderabad	121
66	All India Institute of Medical Sciences	New Delhi	120
67	Maharaja Sayajirao University	Baroda	119
68	University of Mysore	Mysore	118
69	College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry	Jabalpur	117
70	College of Horticulture	Trichur	115
71	University of Kerala	Thiruvananthapuram	115
72	Agricultural College	Vellayani	112
73	Indira Gandhi Agricultural University	Ambikapur	110
74	Central Agricultural Research Institute	Port Blair	108
75	Himachal Pradesh University	Shimla	107

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
76	ICAR Research Complex for North-Eastern Hills Region	Shillong	107
77	Indian Institute of Technology	Kharagpur	107
78	Industrial Toxicology Research Centre	Lucknow	107
79	National Chemical Laboratory	Pune	107
80	Madurai Kamaraj University	Madurai	105
81	University Colleges of Science and Technology	Calcutta	104
82	Agricultural College	Bapatla	103
83	Bose Institute	Calcutta	103
84	Sugarcane Breeding Institute	Coimbatore	103
85	Agricultural College	Nagpur	101
86	Agricultural College	Dharwad	99
87	College of Veterinary Science	Tirupati	97
88	Kerala Agricultural University	Thiruvananthapuram	95
89	Central Coffee Research Institute	Chickmagalur	94
90	College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry	Mhow	94
91	Maharashtra Association for the Cultivation of Science	Pune	92
92	Sri Venkateswara Agricultural College	Tirupati	89
93	Calicut University	Calicut	87
94	Shri Karna Narendra College of Agriculture	Jobner	86
95	College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry	Anand	81
96	Fredrick Institute of Plant Protection and Toxicology (Fippat)	Padappai	81
97	Tocklai Experimental Station	Jorhat	80
98	Central Institute of Agricultural Engineering	Bhopal	79
99	Central Research Institute for Dryland Agriculture	Hyderabad	78
100	National Plant Tissue Culture Repository	New Delhi	78
101	Agricultural College	Pune	75
102	Agriculture College	Madurai	75
103	Andhra University	Visakhapatnam	75
104	Indian Institute of Chemical Biology	Calcutta	75
105	Kurukshetra University	Kurukshetra	75
106	National Research Centre for Spices	Calicut	75
107	Punjabi University	Patiala	75
108	College of Veterinary Science	Ludhiana	74
109	National Bureau of Soil Survey and Land Use Planning (N.B.S.S. and L.U.P.)	Nagpur	74
110	National Research Centre for Groundnut	Junagadh	74
111	College of Agriculture, J. N. Agricultural University	Indore	73
112	Indian Institute of Technology	New Delhi	73
113	Ranchi College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry	Ranchi	73

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
114	University of Jodhpur	Jodhpur	71
115	Meerut University	Baraut	70
116	National Institute of Virology	Pune	70
117	Rubber Research Institute of India	Kottayam	70
118	Visva-Bharati University	Santiniketan	70
119	Bharathiar University	Coimbatore	69
120	Dr Hari Singh Gour University	Sagar	69
121	Rajasthan Agricultural College	Udaipur	69
122	Tata Energy Research Institute	New Delhi	69
123	Vector Control Research Centre	Pondicherry	69
124	Andhra University	Waltair	68
125	Central Institute for Reseach on Goats	Makhdoom	68
126	Bombay Veterinary College	Bombay	67
127	Rajasthan Agricultural University	Bikaner	67
128	National Institute for Rural Development	Hyderabad	66
129	Rafi Ahmad Kidwai College of Agriculture	Sehore	66
130	Central Plantation Crops Research Institute	Kasaragod	65
131	Karnataka University	Dharwad	65
132	College of Veterinary Sciences	Pantnagar	63
133	Jammu University	Jammu	63
134	Raja Balwant Singh College	Bichpuri	63
135	Central Institute for Cotton Research	Nagpur	62
136	Central Soil and Water Conservation Research and Training Institute	Dehra Dun	62
137	Horticultural Experiments and Training Centre	Chaubattia	62
138	Indian Council of Agricultural Research	New Delhi	62
139	National Dairy Research Institute	Bangalore	62
140	Agriculture College	Bhubaneswar	61
141	Jawaharlal Agricultural University	Sehore	61
142	Marathwada University	Aurangabad	61
143	Nagpur Veterinary College	Nagpur	61
144	Raja Balwant Singh College	Agra	60
145	Sardar Patel University	Vallabh Vidyanagar	60
146	University of Kashmir	Srinagar	60
147	Vasantdada Sugar Institute	Pune	60
148	Rani Durgavati University	Jabalpur	59
149	Ravishankar University	Raipur	59
150	College of Veterinary Science	Gauhati	58
151	Central Tobacco Research Institute	Rajahmundry	57
152	Manipur University	Imphal	57
153	Nagarjuna University	Nagarjunanagar	57
154	National Environment Engineering Research Institute	Nagpur	57
155	Central Sheep and Wool Research Institute	Avikanagar	55

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
156	Burdwan University	Burdwan	54
157	Directorate of Rice Research	Hyderabad	54
158	Narendra Deva University of Agriculture and Technology	Bahraich	54
159	Agriculture college	Indore	53
160	Tamil Nadu Veterinary and Animal Sciences University	Madras	53
161	Agricultural Research Station	Jaipur	52
162	ICAR Research Complex for NEH Region, Division of Plant Breeding	Barapani	52
163	Agricultural Research Station	Bhavanisagar	51
164	College of Veterinary Science	Hyderabad	51
165	National Dairy Development Board	Anand	51
166	Botanical Survey of India	Coimbatore	50
167	Central Plantation Crops Research Institute	Kayankulam	50
168	Regional Research Station	Jorhat	49
169	University of Pune	Pune	49
170	University of Roorkee	Roorkee	49
171	Bidhan Chandra Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya	Kalyani	48
172	Gujarat Agricultural University	Navsari	48
173	Indian Veterinary Research Institute	Palampur	48
174	Rajasthan Agricultural University	Udaipur	48
175	Annamalai University	Parangipettai	47
176	Directorate of Pulse Research	Kanpur	47
177	National Institute of Communicable Diseases	New Delhi	47
178	National Institute of Immunology	New Delhi	47
179	College of Agriculture	Hyderabad	46
180	Conifers Research Centre	Shimla	46
181	H.N.B. Garhwal University	Srinagar	46
182	National Sugar Institute	Kanpur	46
183	Regional Research Laboratory (CSIR)	Thiruvananthapuram	46
184	Central Institute of Horticulture for Northern Plains	Lucknow	45
185	College of Veterinary Sciences and Animal Husbandry	Bikaner	45
186	Bihar Agricultural College	Bhagalpur	44
187	College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry	Mathura	44
188	Jawaharlal Nehru Agricultural University	Gwalior	44
189	Sambalpur University	Sambalpur	44
190	Sri Krishna Devaraya University	Anantapur	44
191	Agricultural University	Hissar	43
192	Meerut University	Meerut	43
193	Sheth M.C. College of Dairy Science	Anand	43
194	Vivekananda Laboratory for Hill Agriculture	Almora	43
195	Bangalore University	Bangalore	42

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
196	Central Plantation Crops Research Institute	Thiruvananthapuram	42
197	Gujarat Agricultural University	Sardar Krushinagar	42
198	Jadavpur University	Calcutta	42
199	Regional Research Station	Vriddhachalam	42
200	Vikram University	Ujjain	42
201	Central Horticultural Experiment Station	Ranchi	41
202	Central Potato Research Station	Shillong	41
203	Indian Institute of Chemical Technology	Hyderabad	41
204	Shivaji University	Kolhapur	41
205	Guru Nanak Dev University	Amritsar	40
206	Loyala College	Madras	40
207	Malaria Research Centre (ICMR)	New Delhi	40
208	National Pulses Research Centre	Pudukkottai	40
209	Navinchandra Mafatlal College of Agriculture	Navsari	40
210	Rajendra Agricultural University	Samastipur	40
211	University of Hyderabad	Hyderabad	40
212	Agricultural College	Rewa	39
213	Annamalai University	Annamalai Nagar	39
214	ICAR Research Complex for North-Eastern Hills Region	Gangtok	39
215	Magadh University	Bodh Gaya	39
216	Sugarcane Research Station	Cuddalore	39
217	Agra University	Agra	38
218	BAIF Development Research Foundation	Pune	38
219	Bansilal Amrutlal College of Agriculture	Anand	38
220	Indian Agricultural Statistical Research Institute	New Delhi	38
221	Institute of Deciduous Forests	Jabalpur	38
222	Agra College	Agra	37
223	College of Veterinary and Animal Science	Parbhani	37
224	College of Veterinary Science	Hissar	37
225	Dep. Agric. Chemistry and Soil Science	Rahuri	37
226	University of Garhwal	Srinagar	37
227	Bombay University	Bombay	36
228	College of Agriculture	Jobner	36
229	Fertiliser Development and Consultation Organisation	New Delhi	36
230	G.S. Sugarcane Breeding and Research Institute	Deoria	36
231	Gauhati University	Gauhati	36
232	Gujarat Agricultural University	Junagadh	36
233	ICAR Research Complex for North-Eastern Hills Region	Gantok	36
234	International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics	Hyderabad	36
235	Jiwaji University	Gwalior	36

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
236	Agricultural College	Raichur	35
237	Central Plantation Crops Research Institute	Vittal	35
238	Central Tasar Research and Training Institute	Ranchi	35
239	Ranchi University	Ranchi	35
240	Agricultural College and Research Institute	Madurai	34
241	Institute of Rural Management	Anand	34
242	National Centre for Mushroom Research and Training	Solan	34
243	School of Tropical Medicine	Calcutta	34
244	Veterinary College and Research Institute	Namakkal	34
245	Zoological Survey of India	Calcutta	34
246	Agricultural Institute Naini	Allahabad	33
247	Agricultural University	Junagadh	33
248	Bharathidasan University	Tiruchirapalli	33
249	Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources	New Delhi	33
250	Essential Oil Division, Regional Research Laboratory	Jammu Tawi	33
251	Institute of Wood Science and Technology	Bangalore	33
252	National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources	New Delhi	33
253	Central Arid Zone Research Institute	Jodhpur	32
254	Central Tuber Crops Research Institute	Thiruvananthapuram	32
255	Cotton Technological Research Laboratory	Bombay	32
256	Regional Research Laboratory	Jammu	32
257	Bihar Veterinary College	Patna	31
258	Central Institute for Research on Buffaloes	Hissar	31
259	Directorate of Plant Protection Quarantine and Storage	Faridabad	31
260	Fertiliser Association of India	New Delhi	31
261	Maharshi Dayanand University	Rohtak	31
262	Devi Ahilya University	Indore	30
263	Jute Agricultural Research Institute	Barrackpore	30
264	Kerala Agricultural University	Thrissur	30
265	Presidency College	Calcutta	30
266	Regional Medical Research Centre (ICMR)	Bhubaneswar	30
267	St. John's Medical College	Bangalore	30
268	Veterinary College	Bangalore	30
269	Christian Medical College and Hospital	Vellore	29
270	Defence Research and Development Establishment	Gwalior	29
271	Directorate of Oilseeds Research	Hyderabad	29
272	Kasturba Medical College and Hospital	Manipal	29
273	Pondicherry University	Pondicherry	29
274	St. Xavier's College	Palayankottai	29
275	Vallabhbhai Patel Chest Institute	New Delhi	29
276	Central Institute for Cotton Research	Coimbatore	28

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
277	Horticultural Research Station	Yercaud	28
278	Indian Institute of Management	Ahmedabad	28
279	Institute of Medical Sciences	Varanasi	28
280	Agricultural Research Station	Dharwad	27
281	Agricultural Research Station	Jalgaon	27
282	Agriculture College	Bangalore	27
283	Anna University	Madras	27
284	Bareilly College	Bareilly	27
285	College of Agriculture	Pantnagar	27
286	D.A.V. (Post Graduate) College	Dehra Dun	27
287	Utkal University	Bhubaneswar	27
288	Bhavnagar University	Bhavnagar	26
289	College of Veterinary and Animal Sciences	Trichur	26
290	D.A.V. College	Kanpur	26
291	Maharshi Dayanand Saraswati University	Ajmer	26
292	National Research Centre on Equines	Hissar	26
293	Potash Research Institute of India	Gurgaon	26
294	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Guntur	26
295	Thiagarajar College	Madurai	26
296	University of Burdwan	Golapbag	26
297	Agricultural Research Station	Palur	25
298	Berhampur University	Berhampur	25
299	Indian Statistical Institute	Calcutta	25
300	Institute of Forest Genetics and Tree Breeding	Coimbatore	25
301	Jawaharlal Institute of Post Graduate Medical Education and Research	Pondicherry	25
302	M.S. (Post Graduate) College	Saharanpur	25
303	National Institute of Oceanography	Goa	25
304	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Anakapalle	25
305	Regional Research Station	Mudigere	25
306	Sandal Research Centre	Bangalore	25
307	Agricultural College and Research Institute	Killikulam	24
308	Agricultural Research Station	Pilicode	24
309	Central Potato Research Station	Jalandhar	24
310	Central Potato Research Station	Modipuram	24
311	D.A.V. (Post Graduate) College	Muzaffamagar	24
312	ICAR Research Complex for N.E.H. Region	Bishnupur	24
313	Indian Institute of Technology	Madras	24
314	Institute of Advanced Studies	Meerut	24
315	National Centre for Integrated Pest Management	Bangalore	24
316	Associated Agricultural Development Foundation	Nashik	23
317	Centre for Research in Medical Entomology	Madurai	23
318	Institute of Social and Economic Change	Bangalore	23
319	Livestock Production Research (C G & LA) Indian Veterinary Research Institute	Mukteswar	23

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
320	Patna University	Patna	23
321	Rajasthan Agricultural University	Jobner	23
322	Veterinary Biological and Research Institute, Microbiology Laboratory	Hyderabad	23
323	Botanical Survey of India	Port Blair	22
324	Darjeeling Government College	Darjeeling	22
325	Gujarat University	Ahmedabad	22
326	Indian Council of Forestry Research and Education	Dehra Dun	22
327	Ministry of Agriculture	New Delhi	22
328	National Research Centre for Soybean (I.C.A.R.)	Indore	22
329	National Research Centre on Camels	Bikaner	22
330	Tripura University	Agartala	22
331	Andhra Pradesh Agricultural University	Tirupati	21
332	Central Insecticides Laboratory	Faridabad	21
333	Haryana Agricultural University	Karnal	21
334	Horticultural Research Station	Periyakulam	21
335	Indian Agricultural Research Institute	Kullu	21
336	Indian Veterinary Research Institute	Bangalore	21
337	Indira Gandhi Agricultural University	Raipur	21
338	Kerala Agricultural University	Trichur	21
339	M.S. Swaminathan Research Foundation	Madras	21
340	Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute	Aduthurai	21
341	University Department of Chemical Technology	Bombay	21
342	UPASI Tea Research Institute	Coimbatore	21
343	Avinashilingam Institute for Home Science and Higher Education for Women	Coimbatore	20
344	Entomology Research Institute	Madras	20
345	Indian Veterinary Research Institute	Srinagar	20
346	Jamia Millia Islamia	New Delhi	20
347	Jawaharlal Nehru Agricultural University	Indore	20
348	Karnataka State Sericulture Development Institute	Bangalore	20
349	King George's Medical College	Lucknow	20
350	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Pattambi	20
351	Regional Research Station	Karnal	20
352	School of Life Sciences	Hyderabad	20
353	Space Applications Centre	Ahmedabad	20
354	Sri Venkateswara University Post Graduate Centre	Kavali	20
355	State Forest Research Institute	Jabalpur	20
356	Agricultural Research Institute	Hyderabad	19
357	Agricultural Scientists Recruitment Board	New Delhi	19
358	Cancer Research Institute	Bombay	19
359	Christ Church College	Kanpur	19

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
360	College of Agriculture	Kolhapur	19
361	College of Fisheries	Mangalore	19
362	Haffkine Institute	Bombay	19
363	Livestock Production Research (C G & LA) Indian Veterinary Research Institute	Mukteshwar	19
364	National Research Centre for Sorghum	Hyderabad	19
365	Rajendra Memorial Research Institute of Medical Sciences	Patna	19
366	University of Sagar	Sagar	19
367	Agricultural Research Station	Aliyamagar	18
368	Agricultural Research Station	Durgapura	18
369	Agricultural Research Station	Sriganganagar	18
370	Central Sericultural Research and Training Institute	Berhampore	18
371	Central Soil and Water Conservation Research and Training Institute	Chandigarh	18
372	Indian Immunologicals	Hyderabad	18
373	Military Farms School and Research Centre	Meerut	18
374	National Dairy Research Institute	Kalyani	18
375	Punjab Agricultural University	Gurdaspur	18
376	Regional Research Laboratory	Hyderabad	18
377	University of Agricultural Sciences	Raichur	18
378	Uttar Pradesh Council of Sugarcane Research	Shahjahanpur	18
379	Awadhesh Pratap Singh University	Rewa	17
380	College of Agriculture	Junagadh	17
381	College of Animal Science	Hissar	17
382	College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry	Bhubaneswar	17
383	Forest Vegetation Survey	Midnapore	17
384	Hamdard University	New Delhi	17
385	ICAR Research Complex for North-Eastern Hills Region	Imphal	17
386	Indian Agricultural Research Institute	Simla	17
387	Indian Institute of Technology	Bombay	17
388	Institute of Economic Growth	New Delhi	17
389	Manipur Agricultural College	Imphal	17
390	National Institute of Animal Genetics	Karnal	17
391	North Bengal University	Siliguri	17
392	PSG College of Arts and Science	Coimbatore	17
393	Punjab Agricultural University Sugarcane Research Station	Jalandhar	17
394	Regional Research Station	Keonjhar	17
395	Seth G.S. Medical College and K.E.M. Hospital	Bombay	17
396	Assam Agricultural University	Gauhati	16
397	Central Institute of Freshwater Aquaculture	Bhubaneswar	16

SI No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
398	Government Post Graduate College	Kotdwara	16
399	Gulbarga University	Gulbarga	16
400	Indian Farmers Fertilizer Cooperative Limited	New Delhi	16
401	North Bengal University	Darjeeling	16
402	Regional Centre of the Sugarcane Breeding Institute	Karnal	16
403	Regional Research Institute	Chiplima	16
404	Regional Research Lab. Council of Scientific and Industrial Research	Jammu Tawi	16
405	S.K. University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology	Shalimar	16
406	Sukhadia University	Udaipur	16
407	University of Agricultural Sciences	Mangalore	16
408	Agricultural Research Institute	Patna	15
409	All India Co-ordinated Research Project on Buffaloes, Livestock Research Station	Vallabhnagar	15
410	Captain Srinivasa Murti Drug Research Institute for Ayurveda	Madras	15
411	Central Bee Research and Training Institute	Pune	15
412	Central Leather Research Institute	Madras	15
413	Central Rainfed Upland Rice Research Station	Hazaribagh	15
414	Central Salt and Marine Chemical Research Institute	Bhavnagar	15
415	Centre for Cellular and Molecular Biology	Hyderabad	15
416	Chettinad Stud and Agricultural Farm	Madras	15
417	College of Agriculture	Dapoli	15
418	Council of Scientific and Industrial Research Complex	Palampur	15
419	Harcourt Butler Technological Institute	Kanpur	15
420	ICAR Research Complex for NEH Region	Jharnapani	15
421	Institute of Science	Bombay	15
422	Punjab Agricultural University	Bathinda	15
423	Rice Research Station	Moncompu	15
424	Saurashtra University	Rajkot	15
425	Tata Institute of Fundamental Research	Bombay	15
426	Tirhut College of Agriculture	Muzaffarpur	15
427	Tropical Forest Research Institute, P.O. RFRC	Jabalpur	15
428	UPASI Tea Research Institute	Valpararai	15
429	Birbal Sahni Institute of Palaeobotany	Lucknow	14
430	Botanical Survey of India	Dehra Dun	14
431	Central Potato Research Station	Meerut	14
432	Central Tobacco Research Institute	Dinhata	14
433	College of Technology and Agricultural Engg.	Udaipur	14
434	Dungar College	Bikaner	14
435	Govind Ballabh Pant University of Agriculture and Technology	Ranichauri	14

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
436	L.N. Mithila University	Darbhanga	14
437	Mangalore University	Mangalagangothri	14
438	Medical Hospital and Research Centre	Moradabad	14
439	Meerut College	Meerut	14
440	National Institute of Occupational Health (ICMR)	Ahmedabad	14
441	Post Graduate and Research Centre	Hyderabad	14
442	Post Graduate College of Science	Hyderabad	14
443	Regional Agriculture Research Station	Chhindwara	14
444	University College of Medical Sciences	New Delhi	14
445	Agricultural Research Station	Paramakudi	13
446	Bihar University	Muzaffarpur	13
447	Central Arid Zone Research Institute	Bikaner	13
448	Centre for Development Studies	Thiruvananthapuram	13
449	College of Agricultural	Udaipur	13
450	Danielson College	Chhindwara	13
451	Garhwal University	Garhwal	13
452	Gujarat Agricultural University	Bharuch	13
453	Kongunadu Arts and Science College	Coimbatore	13
454	Maulana Azad Medical College	New Delhi	13
455	Medical College	Rohtak	13
456	Rajasthan Agricultural University	Alwar	13
457	Rohilkhand University	Bareilly	13
458	Sanatan Dharm College	Muzaffarnagar	13
459	Wildlife Institute of India	Dehra Dun	13
460	Agricultural Research Station	Maruteru	12
461	Agriculture Research Station	Anantapur	12
462	Bipin Bihari (Post Graduate) College	Jhansi	12
463	Central Marine Fisheries Research Institute	Cochin	12
464	Central Sheep and Wool Research Institute	Kodaikanal	12
465	College of Veterinary Science	Hebbal	12
466	Defence Research Laboratory	Tezpur	12
467	Embryo Transfer State Centre	Erode	12
468	Gokhale Institute of Politics and Economics	Pune	12
469	ICAR Research Complex for North-Eastern Hills Region	Lembucherra	12
470	Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science	Calcutta	12
471	Indian Cardamom Research Institute, Spices Board	Myladumpara	12
472	Indian Lac Research Institute	Ranchi	12
473	Lokmanya Tilak Municipal Medical College	Bombay	12
474	Mahatma Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences	Sevagram	12
475	National Malaria Eradication Programme	New Delhi	12
476	National Research Centre for Agroforestry	Jhansi	12
477	Project Directorate for Cropping Systems Res.	Modipuram	12

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
478	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Titabar	12
479	Regional Fruit Research Station	Shimla	12
480	Regional Research Station	Raichur	12
481	Rice Research Station	Chinsurah	12
482	Sanjay Gandhi Post Graduate Institute of Medical Sciences	Lucknow	12
483	Water and Land Management Institute	Aurangabad	12
484	World Health Organization, World Health House	New Delhi	12
485	Agricultural Research Station	Kovilpatti	11
486	Agricultural Research Station	Nipani	11
487	Cancer Institute	Madras	11
488	Central Biological Control Station	Solan	11
489	Central Inland Capture Fisheries Research Institute	Barrackpore	11
490	Central Institute of Fisheries Technology	Cochin	11
491	Centre of Studies in Resources Engineering	Bombay	11
492	Defence Food Research Laboratory	Mysore	11
493	Forest Research Laboratory	Bangalore	11
494	Forestry Research Station	Mettupalayam	11
495	Hindustan Lever Ltd.	Bombay	11
496	ICAR Research Complex for NEH Region	Lambucheera	11
497	Indian Institute of Soil Science	Bhopal	11
498	Indian Institute of Technology	Kanpur	11
499	Institute of Agriculture	Sriniketan	11
500	Institute of Animal Health And Veterinary Biologicals	Bangalore	11
501	Institute of Veterinary Preventive Medicine	Ranipet	11
502	Janta Mahavidyalaya Ajitmal	Etawah	11
503	Malaria Research Centre (Field Station)	Nadiad	11
504	National Bureau of Animal Genetic Resources	Karnal	11
505	National Bureau of Soil Survey and Land Use Planning	Bangalore	11
506	National Federation of Co-operative Sugar Factories Ltd.	New Delhi	11
507	Post Graduate Institute of Basic Medical Sciences	Madras	11
508	Project Directorate on Cattle (Indian Council of Agricultural Research)	Meerut	11
509	Rajendra Agricultural University	Muzaffarpur	11
510	Regional Research Station	Brahmavar	11
511	Regional Sericultural Research Station	Dehra Dun	11
512	St. John's College	Agra	11
513	University of Horticulture and Forestry, Regional Research Station	Kinnaur	11
514	A.N. Sinha Institute of Social Studies	Patna	10
515	Agricultural Research Station	Navile	10

SI No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
516	Bihar Agricultural College, Soil Survey and Land Use Planning Centre	Sabour	10
517	Coconut Research Station	Thanjavur	10
518	College of Veterinary and Animal Sciences	Mannuthy	10
519	College of Veterinary and Animal Sciences	Palampur	10
520	Government College	Ajmer	10
521	Gurukula Kangri University	Haridwar	10
522	Himachal Pradesh Agricultural University	Dhaulakuan	10
523	Institute for Research in Reproduction	Bombay	10
524	Konkan Agricultural University	Ratnagiri	10
525	M.M. Post Graduate College	Modinagar	10
526	Madras Medical College	Madras	10
527	Madras Veterinary College and Livestock Research Station	Kattupakkam	10
528	Malaria Research Centre	Shahjahanpur	10
529	National Institute of Cholera and Enteric Diseases	Calcutta	10
530	National Remote Sensing Agency	Hyderabad	10
531	National Research Centre for Cashew	Puttur	10
532	New College	Kolhapur	10
533	Oilseeds Research Station	Latur	10
534	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Morena	10
535	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Palem	10
536	Rice Research Station	Kaul	10
537	Rice Research Station	Tirur	10
538	Sugarcane Research Institute	Pusa	10
539	University of Agricultural Sciences	Brahmavar	10
540	Agricultural Research Station	Kota	9
541	Agricultural Research Station	Thirupathisaram	9
542	Agricultural Research Station	Warangal	9
543	Agricultural University, Livestock Research Institute	Sardar Krushinagar	9
544	AICRP (Maize), ARS	Mysore	9
545	All India Institute of Hygiene and Public Health	Calcutta	9
546	APA College of Arts and Culture	Palani	9
547	Banana Research Station	Trichur	9
548	Barkatullah University	Bhopal	9
549	Bombay Natural History Society	Bombay	9
550	Center for Biochemicals	New Delhi	9
551	Central National Herbarium, Botanical Survey of India	Howrah	9
552	Central Research Institute for Jute and Allied Fibres	Barrackpore	9
553	Central Sheep and Wool Research Institute	Bikaner	9
554	College of Agriculture	Akola	9

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
555	College of Agriculture	Khandwa	9
556	College of Basic Sciences and Humanities	Pantnagar	9
557	College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry	Sardar Krushinagar	9
558	D.B.S. College	Dehra Dun	9
559	Government College	Port Blair	9
560	Government Post Graduate College	Guna	9
561	Government Post Graduate College	Pithoragarh	9
562	Gujarat Narmada Valley Fertilizers Co. Ltd.	Bharuch	9
563	Himachal Pradesh Krishi Vishvavidyalaya	Kullu	9
564	Horticultural College and Research Institute	Periyakulam	9
565	Horticultural Experiment and Training Centre	Saharanpur	9
566	Indian Agricultural Research Institute	Indore	9
567	Indian Agricultural Research Institute Regional Station	Nilgiris	9
568	Indian Farmers Fertiliser Cooperative Ltd.	Phulpur	9
569	Indian Institute of Forest Management	Bhopal	9
570	Institute of Science	Nagpur	9
571	International Centre for Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology	New Delhi	9
572	Jai Research Foundation	Valsad	9
573	Jamia Hamdard	New Delhi	9
574	Kulbhaskar Ashram Degree College	Allahabad	9
575	Meteorological Office	Pune	9
576	MLK Post Graduate College	Balrampur	9
577	National Bureau of Soil Survey and Land Use Planning	Calcutta	9
578	National Bureau of Soil Survey and Land Use Planning	New Delhi	9
579	National Remote Sensing Agency	Balanagar	9
580	National Research Centre for Weed Science	Jabalpur	9
581	Poultry Research and Development Centre	Pudukkottai	9
582	Poultry Research Station	Madras	9
583	Punjab Agricultural University	Faridkot	9
584	Raj Rishi College	Alwar	9
585	Rajasthan Agricultural University	Jaipur	9
586	Rashtriya Chemicals and Fertilizers Ltd.	Bombay	9
587	Regional Horticultural Research Station	Jassur	9
588	Regional Medical Research Centre	Dibrugarh	9
589	Rural University, Faculty of Rural Development	Gandhigram	9
590	Shri Murali Manohar Town Post Graduate College	Ballia	9
591	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Madurai	9
592	Thapar Corporate Research and Development Centre	Patiala	9

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
593	Udai Pratap College	Varanasi	9
594	University College of Science	Hyderabad	9
595	University of Udaipur	Udaipur	9
596	Zonal Agricultural Research Station	Powarkheda	9
597	Zoological Survey of India	Dehra Dun	9
598	Agricultural Research Station	Bijapur	8
599	Agricultural Research Station	Niphad	8
600	Agriculture Research Station	Shimoga	8
601	Ahmednagar College	Ahmednagar	8
602	Alfa-Laval (India) Ltd.	Pune	8
603	Amar Singh College	Lakhaoti	8
604	American College	Madurai	8
605	Animal Disease Research Centre	Ludhiana	8
606	AP Centre, ICAR Research Complex for NEH Region	Basar	8
607	Burdwan Medical College	Burdwan	8
608	Central Biological Control Station	Bangalore	8
609	Central Potato Research Station	Patna	8
610	Central Silk Board, Regional Muga Research Station	Boko	8
611	Centre for Water Resources Development and Management	Calicut	8
612	Cochin University of Science and Technology	Cochin	8
613	College of Agricultural Engineering and Technology	Bhubaneswar	8
614	College of Agriculture	Latur	8
615	College of Agriculture	Thiruvananthapuram	8
616	Crop Research Station	Faizabad	8
617	D.S.College	Allgarh	8
618	Dr. A.L. Mudaliar Post Graduate Institute of Basic Medical Sciences	Madras	8
619	Faculty of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry	Srinagar	8
620	G.B. Pant Institute of Himalayan Environment and Development, HAPPRC	Srinagar Garhwal	8
621	Giri Institute of Development Studies	Lucknow	8
622	Government Arts College	Coimbatore	8
623	Government Arts College	Ootacamund	8
624	Hindustan Antibiotics Ltd.	Pune	8
625	Holkar Science College	Indore	8
626	ICAR Research Complex	Goa	8
627	Indian Agricultural Research Institute	Karnal	8
628	Indian Agricultural Research Institute	Shimla	8
629	Institute of Development Studies	Jaipur	8
630	Kerala Agricultural University	Mannuthy	8

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
631	Kumaun University	Almora	8
632	Maize Research Station	Hyderabad	8
633	Makarana Mohalla	Jodhpur	8
634	Ministry of Environment and Forests	New Delhi	8
635	Ministry of Science and Technology	New Delhi	8
636	Nagpur University	Nagpur	8
637	National Research Laboratory for Conservation of Cultural Properties	Lucknow	8
638	Nehru School of Agricultural Sciences and Rural Development	Medziphema	8
639	North Eastern Hill University	Medziphema	8
640	Osmania Medical College	Hyderabad	8
641	Physical Research Laboratory	Ahmedabad	8
642	Plant Quarantine and Fumigation Station	Madras	8
643	Ponni Sugars and Chemicals Ltd.	Erode	8
644	Projects and Development India Limited	Sindri	8
645	Pulses and Oilseeds Research Station	Berhampore	8
646	Rajendra Agricultural University	Patna	8
647	Ramie Research Station (ICAR)	Sorbhog	8
648	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Bilaspur	8
649	Regional Coffee Research Station	Chundale	8
650	Regional Medical Research Centre	Jodhpur	8
651	Regional Research Station	Udayagiri	8
652	Regional Research Station	Paipur	8
653	Regional Tasar Research Station	Imphal	8
654	Sardar Patel College	Hyderabad	8
655	Sheep Breeding Research Station	Sandynallah	8
656	Sher-e-Kashmir University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology	R. S. Pura	8
657	The Nizam's Institute of Medical Sciences	Hyderabad	8
658	Van Vigyan Kendra	Banderdeva	8
659	Water and Power Consultancy Services Ltd.	New Delhi	8
660	Agricultural College	Raipur	7
661	Agricultural Research Station	Bellary	7
662	Agricultural Research Station	Nellore	7
663	Amala Cancer Research Centre	Trichur	7
664	Brahmanand Mahavidyalaya	Rath	7
665	C.M. Science College	Darbhanga	7
666	Central Biological Control Field Laboratory	Kullu	7
667	Central Building Research Institute, Fire Research Laboratory	Roorkee	7
668	Central Horticultural Experiment Station	Kodagu	7
669	Central Institute of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants	Bangalore	7
670	Central Research Institute	Kasauli	7

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
671	Central Tobacco Research Institute Research Station	Pusa	7
672	Central Water Commission	New Delhi	7
673	Chandra Sekhar Azad University of Agriculture and Technology	Mathura	7
674	College of Agricultural Engineering	Raichur	7
675	CTRL Regional Unit, Regional Agricultural Research Station	Guntur	7
676	Dairy Training Centre	Visakhapatnam	7
677	Dayalbagh University	Agra	7
678	Forest Research Centre	Coimbatore	7
679	G.M. College	Sambalpur	7
680	Government Dairy Farm	Visakhapatnam	7
681	Government Science College	Chatrapur	7
682	Gujarat Agricultural University	Surat	7
683	H.N.B. Garhwal University	Garhwal	7
684	Haryana Agricultural University	Ludhiana	7
685	Himachal Pradesh Agricultural University	Bajaura	7
686	<i>Indian Institute of Management</i>	<i>Bangalore</i>	7
687	Indian Institute of Remote Sensing	Dehra Dun	7
688	Indian School of Mines	Dhanbad	7
689	Indian Veterinary Research Institute	Calcutta	7
690	Indian Veterinary Research Institute	Nainital	7
691	Indira Gandhi Institute of Development Research	Bombay	7
692	Institute of History of Medicine and Medical Research	New Delhi	7
693	Ispat General Hospital	Rourkela	7
694	J.V. Post Graduate College	Baraut	7
695	Livestock Research and Development Centre	Dharmapuri	7
696	National Academy of Agricultural Research Management	Hyderabad	7
697	National Geophysical Research Institute	Hyderabad	7
698	National Institute of Hydrology	Roorkee	7
699	Nimbkar Agricultural Research Institute	Phaltan	7
700	Nizam College	Hyderabad	7
701	Rajendra Agricultural University	Dholi	7
702	Rallis Agrochemical Research Station	Bangalore	7
703	Ravenshaw College	Cuttack	7
704	<i>Regional Agricultural Research Station</i>	<i>Jagtial</i>	7
705	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Nandyal	7
706	Regional Fruit Research Station	Pune	7
707	Regional Plant Resource Centre	Bhubaneswar	7
708	Regional Research Station	Bawal	7
709	Regional Research Station	Koraput	7
710	Regional Research Station	Shimoga	7

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
711	Rice Research Station	Kurukshetra	7
712	S.P. Chowgule College	Goa	7
713	S.P.M. College	Biharshari	7
714	Shibli National Post Graduate College	Azamgarh	7
715	Shreemati Nathibai Damodar Thakarsi Women's University Shreemati Nathibai Damod	Bombay	7
716	Silviculture Division, Sal Region	Haldwani	7
717	Sree Chitra Tirunal Institute for Medical Sciences and Technology	Thiruvananthapuram	7
718	State Forest Service College-cum-Research Centre	Bumihat	7
719	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Aduthurai	7
720	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Vellore	7
721	Tropical Botanic Garden and Research Institute	Thiruvananthapuram	7
722	Agricultural Research Station	Banswara	6
723	Agricultural Research Station	Chintamani	6
724	Agriculture Research Station	Coimbatore	6
725	Anand Niketan College of Agriculture	Warora	6
726	Anwarul-Uloom College	Hyderabad	6
727	Aromatic and Medicinal Plants Research Station	Ernakulam	6
728	B.C. Roy Post Graduate Institute of Basic Medical Sciences	Calcutta	6
729	Bihar State Agricultural Marketing Board	Patna	6
730	Cent. Soil Salinity Res. Inst., Regional Res. Sta.	Canning Town	6
731	Central Food Technological Institute	Ludhiana	6
732	Central Horticultural Experiment Station	Godhra	6
733	Central Institute of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants	Pantnagar	6
734	Central Plantation Crops Research Institute	Bangalore	6
735	Central Potato Research Station	Ootacamund	6
736	Central Sheep and Wool Research Institute	Jaipur	6
737	Centre for Biotechnology, SPIC Science Foundation	Madras	6
738	Centre for Tourism Research and Development	Lucknow	6
739	Civil Hospital	Nadiad	6
740	College of Agricultural Engineering	Pusa	6
741	College of Forestry	Solan	6
742	College of Technology	Pantnagar	6
743	College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry	Anjora	6
744	D.B.F. Dayananad College of Arts and Science	Solapur	6
745	Defence Agricultural Research Institute	Almora	6
746	Defence Materials and Stores Research and Development Establishment	Kanpur	6
747	Department of Forests	Bangalore	6
748	Dharamsi Morarji Chemicals Co. Ltd.	Bombay	6
749	Faculty of Veterinary Sciences and A. H	Nowshera	6

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
750	Forest Soil-Vegetation Survey	Medinipur	6
751	French Institute	Pondicherry	6
752	Government Model Science College	Bilaspur	6
753	Government Valley Fruit Research Station	Garhwal	6
754	Government Valley Fruit Research Station	Srinagar	6
755	Govind Ballabh Pant Institute of Himalayan Environment and Development	Almora	6
756	Gujarat Institute of Development Research	Ahmedabad	6
757	Gujarat Narmada Valley Fertilisers Co. Ltd.	Narmadanagar	6
758	Gujarat State Fertilizers Co. Ltd.	Baroda	6
759	Hindustan Fertiliser Corporation Ltd.	Calcutta	6
760	Hoechst India Ltd.	Bombay	6
761	Indian Farmers Fertiliser Co-operative Ltd.	Kalol	6
762	Indian Inst. Tropical Meteorology	Pune	6
763	Indian Statistical Institute	New Delhi	6
764	Institute of Medical Sciences	Srinagar	6
765	Institute of Microbial Technology	Chandigarh	6
766	Jamal Mohamed College	Tiruchirapalli	6
767	Jawaharlal Nehru Agricultural University	Mhow	6
768	Jawaharlal Nehru Krishi Vishwa Vidyalyaya	Chhindwara	6
769	Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College	Aligarh	6
770	Kasila Farms Ltd	Hyderabad	6
771	Main Cotton Research Station	Surat	6
772	National Academy of Sciences	Allahabad	6
773	National Centre for Integrated Pest Management	Faridabad	6
774	National Institute of Health and Family Welfare	New Delhi	6
775	Netaji Nagar Day College	Calcutta	6
776	Planning Commission	New Delhi	6
777	Presidency College	Madras	6
778	Publications and Information Directorate (CSIR)	New Delhi	6
779	Punjab Agricultural University	Abohar	6
780	Ramakrishna Mission Vivekananda College	Madras	6
781	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Gossaigaon	6
782	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Jammu	6
783	Regional Research Laboratory	Bhubaneswar	6
784	Regional Research Station	Balasore	6
785	Regional Research Station	Kullu	6
786	Regional Sericultural Research Station	Salem	6
787	Regional Wheat Rust Research Station	Mahabaleshwar	6
788	Research Foundation for Science Technology & Natural Resource Policy	Dehra Dun	6
789	S.G.N. Khalsa College	Sriganganagar	6
790	Satwik Electric Controls Pvt. Ltd.	Nashik	6
791	Shrijee Engineering Works	Ahmednagar	6

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
792	Social Forestry (S) Circle	Calcutta	6
793	Soil Salinity Research Centre	Tiruchirapalli	6
794	Sorghum Research Station	Parbhani	6
795	Southern Petrochemical Industries Corporation Ltd.	Tuticorin	6
796	State Bank of India	Bombay	6
797	Sugarcane Research Station	Sirugamani	6
798	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Tindivanam	6
799	Thanjavur Medical College	Thanjavur	6
800	Thapar Corporate Research and Development Centre	Patiala	6
801	Tuljaram Chaturchand College	Baramati	6
802	University of Horticulture and Forestry Regional Horticulture Research Station	Kullu	6
803	V.O. Chidambaram College	Tuticorin	6
804	Veterinary College	Bidar	6
805	Z.H. College of Engineering and Technology	Aligarh	6
806	Zuari Agro Chemicals Limited	Goa	6
807	A.E.S. College	Hingoli	5
808	Administrative Staff College of India	Hyderabad	5
809	Agricultural Research Station	Karad	5
810	Agricultural Research Station	Ponnampet	5
811	Agricultural Research Station, All India Co-ordinated Maize-Improvement Project	Arbhavi	5
812	Agriculture Research Station	Tirupati	5
813	Agro-Economic Research Centre	Shimla	5
814	Agronomic Research Station	Chalakudy	5
815	All India Soil and Land Use Survey	Bangalore	5
816	Ankur Agricultural Research Laboratory	Nagpur	5
817	Armed Forces Medical College	Pune	5
818	ASPEE College of Forestry and Horticulture	Navsari	5
819	Associated Agricultural Development Foundation	New Delhi	5
820	CAB International Institute of Biological Control	Bangalore	5
821	Central Agmark Laboratory	Nagpur	5
822	Central Biological Control Station	Hyderabad	5
823	Central College	Bangalore	5
824	Central Electronics Engineering Research Institute	Pilani	5
825	Central Experiment Station	Ratnagiri	5
826	Central Institute for Research on Cotton Technology (ICAR)	Bombay	5
827	Central Leprosy Teaching and Research Institute	Chengalpattu	5
828	Central Plant Protection Training Institute	Hyderabad	5
829	Centre for Economic and Social Studies	Hyderabad	5
830	College of Agricultural Engineering	Jabalpur	5

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
831	College of Agriculture	Dhule	5
832	College of Agriculture	Jabalpur	5
833	College of Dairy Science	Anand	5
834	College of Rural Home Science	Dharwad	5
835	Cotton Research Station	Sirsa	5
836	Dayanand Post Graduate College	Hissar	5
837	Department of Soil Science and Water Management	Solan	5
838	Directorate of Cocoa	Calicut	5
839	Dr. Yashwant Singh Parmar University of Horticulture and Forestry	Nauni	5
840	Ford Foundation	New Delhi	5
841	Giridih College	Giridih	5
842	Goa University	Goa	5
843	Government Livestock Farm	Banavasi	5
844	Government Model Science College	Gwalior	5
845	Government of India Ministry of Food	New Delhi	5
846	Government Post Graduate College	Gopeshwar	5
847	Government Post Graduate College	Rishikesh	5
848	Government Post Graduate College	Uttar Kashi	5
849	Gujarat Agricultural University	Baroda	5
850	Gujarat Co-operative Milk Marketing Federation Ltd.	Anand	5
851	Guru Nanak College, G.S. Gill Research Institute	Madras	5
852	Hans Raj College	New Delhi	5
853	HP Forest Training School, Forest Division	Chail	5
854	Indian Botanic Garden	Howrah	5
855	Indian Farmers Fertiliser Cooperative Ltd.	Aonla	5
856	Indira Gandhi Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Regional Agricultural Research Station	Bilaspur	5
857	Institute of Animal Nutrition and Livestock Research Station	Kattupakkam	5
858	ITC Bhadrachalam Paperboards Ltd.	Hyderabad	5
859	K.N. Government Post Graduate College	Gyanpur	5
860	Khalsa College	Amritsar	5
861	Lal Bahadur Shastri National Academy of Administration	Mussoorie	5
862	Madras Fertilizers Limited	Madras	5
863	Madurai College	Madurai	5
864	Mahatma Gandhi College	Gorakhpur	5
865	Mahatma Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences	Wardha	5
866	Main Sorghum Research Station	Surat	5
867	Medical College	Thiruvananthapuram	5
868	Mother Dairy	New Delhi	5
869	National Bureau of Soil Survey and Land Use Planning	Jorhat	5

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
870	National Institute of Mental Health and Neurosciences	Bangalore	5
871	National Institute of Science	New Delhi	5
872	Nehru Memorial Museum and Library	New Delhi	5
873	Oil Technological Research Institute	Anantapur	5
874	Orchid Centre	Tiptur	5
875	Punjab State Co-operative Milk Producers' Federation Ltd.	Chandigarh	5
876	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Diphu	5
877	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Jagdalpur	5
878	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Kumarakom	5
879	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Lakhimpur	5
880	Regional Centre of Central Tuber Crops Research Institute	Bhubaneswar	5
881	Regional Office for Health and Family Welfare	Patna	5
882	Regional Office for Health and Family Welfare	Shillong	5
883	Regional Research Laboratory (Br.)	Srinagar	5
884	Regional Research Station	Mandya	5
885	Regional Research Station	Sunabeda	5
886	S.B.P. Government College	Dungarpur	5
887	S.C.B. Medical College	Cuttack	5
888	S.K. University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology	Sopore	5
889	S.S.L. Jain College	Vidisha	5
890	Saifia College of Science and Education	Bhopal	5
891	Sardar Patel Institute of Economic and Social Research	Ahmedabad	5
892	Shah Beekeepers	Srinagar	5
893	Sher-e-Kashmir Institute of Medical Sciences	Srinagar	5
894	Shri A.M.M. Murugappa Chettiar Research Centre	Madras	5
895	Sonamukhi College	Bankura	5
896	SPM College	Udantpuri	5
897	Sri Avinashilingam Home Science College for Women	Coimbatore	5
898	Sri Chamundeswari Sugars Ltd.	Doddi	5
899	Sri Sarada College	Salem	5
900	Sri Sathya Sai Institute of Higher Learning	Anantapur	5
901	St. Andrew's College	Gorakhpur	5
902	Sugarcane Breeding Institute	Cannanore	5
903	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Ambasamudram	5
904	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Periyakulam	5
905	The Fertilisers and Chemicals Travancore Limited	Cochin	5
906	Udaipur South Forest Division	Udaipur	5

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
907	Union Carbide India Limited	Bhopal	5
908	University of Agricultural Sciences	Bijapur	5
909	Wadia Institute of Himalayan Geology	Dehra Dun	5
910	Afro-Asian Rural Reconstruction Organisation	New Delhi	4
911	Agricultural College	Hebbal	4
912	Agricultural College Dairy Farm	Pune	4
913	Agricultural Research Station	Amadalavalasa	4
914	Agricultural Research Station	Gangavati	4
915	Agricultural Research Station	Phondagat	4
916	Agricultural Research Station	Podalakur	4
917	Agricultural Research Station	Sirsi	4
918	Agroforestry Research and Development Centre, Wimco Seedlings Ltd.	Nainital	4
919	All India Co-ordinated Research Project for Dryland Agriculture	Solapur	4
920	All India Co-ordinated Research Project of Tropical Fruits on Citrus	Tirupati	4
921	Andhra Pradesh Agricultural University	Palamaner	4
922	Andhra Sugars Limited	Tanuku	4
923	Arts, Science and Commerce College	Satana	4
924	Bhogawati College	Kurukali	4
925	Bioved Research and Communication Centre	Allahabad	4
926	Botanical Survey of India	Calcutta	4
927	Botanical Survey of India	Itanagar	4
928	Botanical Survey of India	Shillong	4
929	C.T.R.I. Research Station	Hunsur	4
930	Cashew Research Station	Bapatla	4
931	Central Biological Control Station	Gorakhpur	4
932	Central Biological Control Station	Sriganganagar	4
933	Central Glass and Ceramic Research Institute	Calcutta	4
934	Central Horticultural Research Station	Chethalli	4
935	Central Institute of Fisheries Education	Bombay	4
936	Central Integrated Pest Management Centre	Solan	4
937	Central Potato Research Institute	Bangalore	4
938	Central Silviculture Zone	Bangalore	4
939	Centre for Science and Environment	New Delhi	4
940	Centre for Social Studies	Surat	4
941	Chittaarajan National Cancer Research Institute	Calcutta	4
942	College of Agricultural Engineering	Ludhiana	4
943	College of Agriculture	Hissar	4
944	College of Agriculture	Palampur	4
945	College of Agriculture	Parbhani	4
946	College of Agriculture	Sardar Krushinagar	4
947	College of Agriculture	Solan	4
948	College of Basic Science	Ludhiana	4

SI No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
949	College of Cooperation and Banking	Trichur	4
950	College of Dairy Science	Udaipur	4
951	College of Home Science	Hissar	4
952	College of Science	Udaipur	4
953	Cropping System Research Centre	Thiruvananthapuram	4
954	Deccan Sugar Institute	Pune	4
955	Department of Forests	Bhubaneswar	4
956	Department of Science and Technology	New Delhi	4
957	Eucalyptus Research Centre	Midnapore	4
958	Excel Industries Ltd.	Bombay	4
959	Fergusson College	Pune	4
960	Fertilisers and Chemicals Travancore Ltd.	Cochin	4
961	Forest Research Laboratory	Kanpur	4
962	Fruit Research Station	Kandaghat	4
963	Fruit Research Station	Sangareddy	4
964	Fruit Research Station	Solan	4
965	Gobind Ballabh Pant Hospital	New Delhi	4
966	Government Fruit Research Centre	Pithoragarh	4
967	Government Girls College	Bhopal	4
968	Government Medical College	Surat	4
969	Government of West Bengal	Calcutta	4
970	Gujarat Agricultural University	Ahmedabad	4
971	Gujarat Institute of Area Planning	Ahmedabad	4
972	Gujarat State Fertilizers Company Limited	Vadodara	4
973	Himachal Pradesh Agricultural University	Berthin	4
974	Hindustan CIBA-GEIGY Ltd	Bombay	4
975	Hindustan Paper Corporation Ltd.	Alwaye	4
976	Horticultural College and Research Institute	Coimbatore	4
977	Horticultural Experiment and Training Centre	Basti	4
978	Horticultural Research Station	Perumbarai	4
979	ICAR Research Complex for North-Eastern Hills Region	Kolasib	4
980	Indian Agricultural Research Institute	Pusa	4
981	Indian Cardamom Research Institute	Saklespur	4
982	Indian Drugs and Pharmaceuticals Ltd.	Hyderabad	4
983	Indian Grain Storage Institute	Hapur	4
984	Indian Institute of Public Administration	New Delhi	4
985	Indian Sugar Mills Association	New Delhi	4
986	Indo Gulf Fertilizers and Chemical Corporation Limited	New Delhi	4
987	Indo-Swiss Project	Visakhapatnam	4
988	Institute of Animal Health and Veterinary Biologicals	Calcutta	4
989	Institute of Nuclear Medicine and Allied Sciences	New Delhi	4
990	International Institute of Ayurveda	Coimbatore	4

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
991	Janta Vedic College	Meerut	4
992	JBS Haldane Research Centre	Nagercoil	4
993	Jhargram Raj College	Jhargram	4
994	Jute Research Station	Kendrapara	4
995	Kailash Nath Katju College of Agriculture	Mandsaur	4
996	Karim City College	Jamshedpur	4
997	Karnataka Forest Department	Bangalore	4
998	Khar Land Research Station	Panvel	4
999	King Edward Memorial Hospital Research Centre	Pune	4
1000	Kirlampudi Sugar Mills Ltd.	Pithapuram	4
1001	Krishak Bharati Co-operative Ltd.	Hazira	4
1002	Livestock Assistant's Training Centre	Banavasi	4
1003	Locust Warning Organisation	Jodhpur	4
1004	M.L.B. Medical College	Jhansi	4
1005	M.M.H. College	Ghaziabad	4
1006	Mahatma Gandhi College	Darbhanga	4
1007	Mahatma Phule Agricultural University	Pune	4
1008	Micronutrient Laboratory, IBFEP	Cuttack	4
1009	Military Farm	Mhow	4
1010	Motilal Vigyan Mahavidyalaya	Bhopal	4
1011	National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development	Bombay	4
1012	National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources	Shillong	4
1013	National Co-operative Dairy Federation of India Ltd.	Anand	4
1014	National Fertilizers Ltd	New Delhi	4
1015	National Institute of Communicable Diseases	Rajahmundry	4
1016	National Research Centre for Citrus	Nagpur	4
1017	National Research Centre on Yak (ICAR)	Dirang	4
1018	Naval Chemical and Metallurgical Laboratory	Bombay	4
1019	North Temperate Regional Station	Kullu	4
1020	Nutrition Foundation of India	New Delhi	4
1021	Office of the Principal Chief Conservator of Forests	Bhubaneswar	4
1022	Oil Seeds Research Station	Jalgaon	4
1023	Pepper Research Station	Panniyur	4
1024	Periyar District Co-operative Milk Producers' Union Ltd	Erode	4
1025	Pest Control	Nagpur	4
1026	Projects and Development India Ltd.	Dhanbad	4
1027	Pyrites Phosphates and Chemicals Ltd	New Delhi	4
1028	Ramlal Anand College	New Delhi	4
1029	Ranchi Agricultural College	Ranchi	4
1030	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Karimganj	4

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1031	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Kottayam	4
1032	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Shillongani	4
1033	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Tirupati	4
1034	Regional Forest Research Centre	Rajahmundry	4
1035	Regional Horticultural Research Station	Kangra	4
1036	Regional Horticultural Research Station	Kashmir	4
1037	Regional Office for Health and Family Welfare	Chandigarh	4
1038	Regional Research Station	Khandwa	4
1039	Regional Research Station	Sambalpur	4
1040	Regional Research Station and Faculty of Agriculture	Wadura	4
1041	Regional Sericultural Research Station	Coonoor	4
1042	Regional Sugarcane and Jaggary Research Station	Kolhapur	4
1043	Regional Sugarcane Research Station	Navsari	4
1044	Remount Training School and Depot	Saharanpur	4
1045	RLT Science College	Akola	4
1046	Rubber Board	Kottayam	4
1047	Rubber Research Institute of India	Agartala	4
1048	Ruda-Bilas Kisan Sahkari Sugar Mills	Bilaspur	4
1049	Sabarmati Ashram Gaushala	Lali	4
1050	Samanta Chandra Sekhar College	Puri	4
1051	Sanjay Gandhi Institute of Dairy Technology	Patna	4
1052	Shibpur D.B. Institution	Howrah	4
1053	Shukhadia University	Jobner	4
1054	SMS Medical College, BMRC	Jaipur	4
1055	State Agricultural Research Station	Arundhati Nagar	4
1056	State Bank Institute of Rural Development	Hyderabad	4
1057	State Sericultural Research Station	Baripada	4
1058	Surendranath College	Calcutta	4
1059	Survey of Medicinal Plants Unit, Regional Research Institute of Unani Medicine	Bhadra	4
1060	T.N.B. College	Bhagalpur	4
1061	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Melalathur	4
1062	Tea Research Association	Nagrakata	4
1063	Tiruttani Co-op. Sugar Mills Ltd.	Tiruttani	4
1064	University College for Women	Hyderabad	4
1065	University Mushroom Research Centre	Solan	4
1066	University of Agricultural Sciences	Gangavati	4
1067	University of Agricultural Sciences	Mysore	4
1068	University of Kurukshetra	Kurukshetra	4
1069	UPASI Tea Advisory Centre	Coonoor	4
1070	Vellalar College for Women	Erode	4
1071	Veterinary College	Nagpur	4
1072	Vidyasagar University	Midnapore	4

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1073	Wildlife Preservation	Calcutta	4
1074	World Bank	New Delhi	4
1075	Yashwantrao Chavan College of Science	Karad	4
1076	Zoological Survey of India	Madras	4
1077	Zoological Survey of India	Port Blair	4
1078	A.P. State Federation of Cooperative Sugar Factories Ltd	Hyderabad	3
1079	Additional Block Animal Health Centre	Murshidabad	3
1080	Agricultural Research Station	Berhampur	3
1081	Agricultural Research Station	Bidar	3
1082	Agricultural Research Station	Fathepur	3
1083	Agricultural Research Station	Gulbarga	3
1084	Agriculture Research Station	Jodhpur	3
1085	All India Co-ordinated Research Project on Cattle	Guntur	3
1086	Animal Health Centre	Mahbubnagar	3
1087	Animal Husbandry and Veterinary Biologicals	Calcutta	3
1088	Arid Forest Research Institute	Jodhpur	3
1089	Atul Systems and Controls Pvt. Ltd.	Bombay	3
1090	B.S.N.V. Degree College	Lucknow	3
1091	Bhopal University	Bhopal	3
1092	Bidi Tobacco Research Station	Anand	3
1093	Birla Institute of Technology	Ranchi	3
1094	Biswanath College of Agriculture	Biswanath	3
1095	Botanical Survey of India	Gangtok	3
1096	Botanical Survey of India	Pune	3
1097	Buxi Jagabandhu Bidyadhar College	Bhubaneswar	3
1098	C. Abdul Hakeem College	Melvisharam	3
1099	C.M.D. Post Graduate College	Bilaspur	3
1100	Central Arid Zone Research Institute	Jaisalmer	3
1101	Central Arid Zone Research Institute	Pali-Marwar	3
1102	Central Experiment Station	Wakawali	3
1103	Central Fertilizer Quality Control and Training Institute	Faridabad	3
1104	Central Inland Fisheries Research Institute	Rahara	3
1105	Central Institute of Brackishwater Agriculture	Madras	3
1106	Central Institute of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants	Hyderabad	3
1107	Central Institute of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants	Kodaikanal	3
1108	Central Military Veterinary Laboratory	Meerut	3
1109	Central Plantation Crops Research Institute	Calicut	3
1110	Central Potato Research Station	Pune	3
1111	Central Soil and Water Conservation Research and Training Institute	Bellary	3
1112	Central Soil Salinity Research Institute	Canning Town	3
1113	Central Soil Salinity Research Institute	Parganas	3
1114	Central Sugarcane Research Station	Pune	3

SI No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1115	Central Tobacco Research Institute Research Station	Dinhata	3
1116	Central Tobacco Research Institute Research Station	Vedasandur	3
1117	Central Tuber Crops Research Institute	Bhubaneswar	3
1118	Centre for Logistical Research and Innovation	New Delhi	3
1119	Chambal Fertilizers and Chemicals Limited	New Delhi	3
1120	Co-ordinated Agronomic Experiments on Sugarcane	Tiruchirapalli	3
1121	Coconut Development Board	Cochin	3
1122	Coffee Research Sub-Station	Chikmagalur	3
1123	College of Agriculture	Chiplima	3
1124	College of Agriculture	Ratnagiri	3
1125	College of Agriculture	Trichur	3
1126	College of Forestry	Trichur	3
1127	College of Home Science	Udaipur	3
1128	Cotton Research Station	Srivilliputter	3
1129	Dairy Science College	Bangalore	3
1130	Dayanand Medical College and Hospital	Ludhiana	3
1131	Department of Agriculture	Andaman	3
1132	Department of Agronomy, NEHU School of Agricultural Sciences and Rural Development	Medziphema	3
1133	Department of Forests	Calcutta	3
1134	Department of Forests	Chandigarh	3
1135	DGAFMS Ministry of Defence	New Delhi	3
1136	Dharani Sugar and Chemicals Ltd.	Dharani Nagar	3
1137	Dibrugarh University	Dibrugarh	3
1138	Directorate of Agriculture	Madras	3
1139	Directorate of Extension Education	Udaipur	3
1140	Dr. Yashwant Singh Parmar University of Horticulture and Forestry	Dhaulakuan	3
1141	Dry Farming Research Station	Solapur	3
1142	Dryland Research Project	Hoshiarpur	3
1143	Environmental Research Station (ICFRE)	Siliguri	3
1144	Fertiplant Engineering Company Pvt. Ltd.	Bombay	3
1145	Forest Soil Vegetation Survey	Kotebazar	3
1146	Forest Survey of India	Dehra Dun	3
1147	Frozen Semen Laboratory	Nagpur	3
1148	Frozen Semen Laboratory	Visakhapatnam	3
1149	Fruit Research Station	Hoshiarpur	3
1150	G.F. College	Shahjahanpur	3
1151	Geological Survey of India	Jaipur	3
1152	Geological Survey of India	Madras	3
1153	Goa College of Pharmacy	Panaji	3
1154	Gobi Arts College	Gobichettipalayam	3

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1155	Government Arts College	Ariyalur	3
1156	Government Autonomous College	Kota	3
1157	Government Autonomous Science College	Jabalpur	3
1158	Government Degree College	Kathua	3
1159	Government Fruit Preservation and Canning Institute	Lucknow	3
1160	Government M.S.J. College	Bharatpur	3
1161	Government of Himachal Pradesh	Shimla	3
1162	Government of India	New Delhi	3
1163	Government of Maharashtra	Bombay	3
1164	Grapes Research Station	Hyderabad	3
1165	Ground Water Dep.	Jodhpur	3
1166	Gujarat Ayurved University	Jamnagar	3
1167	H.D. Limited	Hyderabad	3
1168	Hanumanbox Surajmal Kanoi College	Dibrugarh	3
1169	Horticultural Research Station	Kodaikanal	3
1170	Horticultural Research Station	Ootacamund	3
1171	I.P. College	Bulandshahr	3
1172	IBFEP, HFC	Calcutta	3
1173	ICAR Research Complex for North-Eastern Hills Region	Medziphema	3
1174	Indian Farmers Fertiliser Cooperative Ltd.	Kandla	3
1175	Indian Institute of Advanced Study	Shimla	3
1176	Indian Institute of Horticultural Research	Gonikopal	3
1177	Indian Institute of Horticultural Research	Kodagu	3
1178	Indian Institute of Petroleum	Dehra Dun	3
1179	Indian School of Political Economy	Pune	3
1180	Indian Social Institute	New Delhi	3
1181	Indian Space Research Organisation Headquarters	Bangalore	3
1182	Indo Gulf Fertilizers and Chemical Corporation Limited	Jagdishpur	3
1183	Institute of Advanced Study in Science and Technology, Division of Life Science	Khanapara	3
1184	Institute of Animal Health and Veterinary Biologicals	Mhow	3
1185	International Institute for Population Sciences	Bombay	3
1186	International Potato Centre	New Delhi	3
1187	J.N. Government College	Port Blair	3
1188	Jain Irrigation Systems Ltd.	Jalgaon	3
1189	Jawaharlal Nehru Agricultural University	Powarkheda	3
1190	Jawaharlal Nehru Krishi Vishwa Vidyalyaya	Mandsaur	3
1191	Joseph Eye Hospital	Tiruchirapalli	3
1192	Jute Research Station	Katihar	3
1193	Kalawati Saran Children's Hospital	New Delhi	3

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1194	Karnataka Regional Engineering College	Surathkal	3
1195	KCP Ltd.	Vuyyuru	3
1196	Kerala Livestock Development Board	Muvattupuzha	3
1197	Khadi and Village Industries Commission	Pune	3
1198	KLDAV College	Roorkee	3
1199	KRIBHCO	New Delhi	3
1200	Krishak Bharati Co-operative Ltd.	New Delhi	3
1201	Krishnanagar Government College	Krishnanagar	3
1202	Krishnanagar Government College	Nadiad	3
1203	L.L.R.M. Medical College	Meerut	3
1204	L.S. College	Muzaffarpur	3
1205	Lady Irwin College	New Delhi	3
1206	Land Use Consultants International	New Delhi	3
1207	M.L.V. Government College	Bhilwara	3
1208	M/s. Indian Herbs	Saharanpur	3
1209	Madhav Science College	Ujjain	3
1210	Madhav Vigyan Mahavidyalaya (MVM)	Bhopal	3
1211	Madras Christian College	Madras	3
1212	Madras Institute of Development Studies	Madras	3
1213	Maharani's College	Jaipur	3
1214	Maharashtra Udayagiri Mahavidyalaya	Udgir	3
1215	Maharashtra Van Sanshodhan Sanstha	Chandrapur	3
1216	Main Rice Research Station	Navagam	3
1217	Malaria Research Centre	Jabalpur	3
1218	Maulana Azad College	Calcutta	3
1219	Medical College	Jabalpur	3
1220	Micronutrient Laboratory, IBFEP, HFC	Sindri	3
1221	Micronutrients Laboratory	Durgapura	3
1222	Ministry of Agriculture	Faridabad	3
1223	Ministry of Rural Development	New Delhi	3
1224	Ministry of Water Resources	New Delhi	3
1225	Mysore Paper Mills Ltd.	Shimoga	3
1226	N.E.S. Science College	Nandad	3
1227	Narain College	Shikohabad	3
1228	National Agricultural and Scientific Research Foundation	Calcutta	3
1229	National Agricultural Research Project	Achalpur	3
1230	National Agricultural Research Project	Bidar	3
1231	National Agricultural Research Project	G. Udayagiri	3
1232	National Agricultural Research Project	Sindewahi	3
1233	National Atlas and Thematic Mapping Organisation	Calcutta	3
1234	National Bureau of Fish Genetic Resources	Allahabad	3
1235	National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources	Hyderabad	3

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1236	National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources	Shimla	3
1237	National Horticultural Research and Development Foundation	Nashik	3
1238	National Institute of Banking Management	Pune	3
1239	National Institute of Communicable Diseases	Coonoor	3
1240	Niphad Sugar	Bhauasaheb Nagar	3
1241	Oilseeds Research Station	Kangra	3
1242	Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology	Sambalpur	3
1243	Pachaiyappa's College for Women	Kancheepura	3
1244	Paddy Breeding Station	Coimbatore	3
1245	Paddy Processing Research Centre	Thanjavur	3
1246	Plant Quarantine Regional Station	Hyderabad	3
1247	Project Directorate of Vegetable Research	Varanasi	3
1248	Project Directorate on Poultry Improvement	Hyderabad	3
1249	Punjab Agricultural University	Amritsar	3
1250	Punjab Remote Sensing Centre	Ludhiana	3
1251	R. Kuttan Amala Cancer Research Centre	Amala Nagar	3
1252	R.J. College	Bombay	3
1253	Raja Mahendra Pratap College	Narsan	3
1254	Rajasthan Co-operative Dairy Federation	Jaipur	3
1255	Ranchi College	Ranchi	3
1256	Ranchi Womens College	Ranchi	3
1257	Ravalgaon Sugar Farm Ltd.	Nashik	3
1258	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Nagaon	3
1259	Regional Agricultural Research Station	R. S. Pura	3
1260	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Sagar	3
1261	Regional Coffee Research Station	Visakhapatnam	3
1262	Regional College of Education	Bhopal	3
1263	Regional Forensic Science Laboratory, State of Maharashtra	Aurangabad	3
1264	Regional Fruit Research Station	Katol	3
1265	Regional Fruit Research Station	Patiala	3
1266	Regional Horticultural Research Station	Shimla	3
1267	Regional Medical College	Imphal	3
1268	Regional Muga Research Station	Mirza	3
1269	Regional Remote Sensing Service Centre	Nagpur	3
1270	Regional Research Laboratory	Bhopal	3
1271	Regional Research Station	Kovilangulam	3
1272	Regional Research Station	Palampur	3
1273	Regional Research Station	Sopore	3
1274	Research Laboratory	Darjeeling	3
1275	Rice Research Station	Ambasamudram	3
1276	Rice Research Station	Kapurthala	3
1277	Rice Research Station	Khudwani	3
1278	Rubber Research Institute	Gauhati	3

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1279	S.D.J. Post Graduate College	Chandesar	3
1280	S.N. Medical College	Agra	3
1281	S.V.T. College of Home Science	Bombay	3
1282	Safdarjung Hospital	New Delhi	3
1283	Salim Ali School of Ecology	Pondicherry	3
1284	Seshasayee Paper and Boards Limited	Erode	3
1285	Sir Theagaraya College	Madras	3
1286	South Gujarat University	Surat	3
1287	South Indian Textile Research Association	Coimbatore	3
1288	SPIC Science Foundation	Madras	3
1289	Sri J. N. Degree College	Lucknow	3
1290	Sri Venkateswara College	New Delhi	3
1291	St. Aloysius College	Mangalore	3
1292	State Forest Research Centre	Kanpur	3
1293	Sunnhemp Research Station	Pratapgarh	3
1294	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Aruppukottai	3
1295	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Vriddhachalam	3
1296	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Yercaud	3
1297	Tamil Nadu Sugar Corporation	Thanjavur	3
1298	Tata Institute of Social Sciences	Bombay	3
1299	The K.C.P. Ltd.	Madras	3
1300	Tilak Dhari College	Jaunpur	3
1301	University of Agricultural Sciences	Annigeri	3
1302	University of Agricultural Sciences	Gulbarga	3
1303	University of Kashmir	Kashmir	3
1304	Urmul Dairy	Bikaner	3
1305	Veterinary Hospital	Kakinada	3
1306	Veterinary Polyclinic	Gudivada	3
1307	Veterinary Polyclinic	Guntur	3
1308	Virudhunagar Hindu Nadar's Senthikumara Nadar College	Virudhunagar	3
1309	Water and Land Management Institute	Gandhinagar	3
1310	World Forestry Arboretum	Jaipur	3
1311	A.N.D. College	Kanpur	2
1312	A.N.S College Barh, Post Graduate Department of Botany	Patna	2
1313	A.V.V.M. Sri Pushpam College (Autonomous)	Poondi	2
1314	Abasaheb Garware College	Pune	2
1315	Adarsha College	Hingoli	2
1316	Aga Khan Rural Support Programme	Ahmedabad	2
1317	Agharkar Research Institute	Pune	2
1318	Agri-Horticultural Society of India	Calcutta	2
1319	Agricultural College and Research Institute	Kummulur	2
1320	Agricultural Meteorology Division	Pune	2

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1321	Agricultural Research Station	Chickballapur	2
1322	Agricultural Research Station	Madhira	2
1323	Agricultural Research Station	Mangalore	2
1324	Agricultural Research Station	Sidhi	2
1325	Agricultural Research Station	Tindivanam	2
1326	Agricultural Research Station	Ulla	2
1327	Agricultural University	Navsari	2
1328	Agriculture college	Tirunelveli	2
1329	Agriculture college	Tirupati	2
1330	Agriculture Research Station	Bhilwara	2
1331	Agriculture Research Station	Gurgaon	2
1332	Agriculture Research Station	Hissar	2
1333	Agriculture Research Station	Nagamangala	2
1334	Agriculture Research Station	Pondicherry	2
1335	Agriculture Research Station	Raichur	2
1336	Agriculture Research Station	Washim	2
1337	AICRP for Epidemiological Studies on Foot and Mouth Diseases	Calcutta	2
1338	All India Coordinated Research Project on Forage Crops	Jhansi	2
1339	All India Coordinated Research Project on Pigs	Tirupati	2
1340	All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project	Sambalpur	2
1341	All-India Co-ordinated Research Programme on Weed Control	Hebbal	2
1342	Ambur Co-op. Sugar Mills Limited	Vadapudupet	2
1343	Andhra Pradesh State Remote Sensing Applications Centre	Hyderabad	2
1344	Animal Health Centre	Chittoor	2
1345	Animal Health Centre	Vijayawada	2
1346	APDDCF Ltd.	Hyderabad	2
1347	Archaeological Survey of India	Dehra Dun	2
1348	Arigner Anna Government Arts College	Cheyyar	2
1349	Armed Forces Medical Services	New Delhi	2
1350	Arunachal Pradesh Centre	Basar	2
1351	Arya Vaidya Sala	Kottakkal	2
1352	Assam Agricultural University	Diphu	2
1353	Assam Agricultural University	Gossaigaon	2
1354	Associated Agricultural Development Foundation	Karnal	2
1355	Association of Food Scientists and Technologists	Mysore	2
1356	Astra Research Centre	Bangalore	2
1357	Ayya Nadar Janaki Ammal College	Sivakasi	2
1358	B.D. Ev. College	Patna	2
1359	B.M. College of Agriculture	Khandwa	2
1360	B.Y.L. Nair Charitable Hospital	Bombay	2
1361	Bajaj Hindusthan Limited	Gola Gokarannath	2

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1362	Base and Army Hospital	New Delhi	2
1363	BASF India Limited	Turbhe	2
1364	Betelvine Research Station	Chatarpur	2
1365	Bethune College	Bidhan Sarani	2
1366	Bharat Pumps and Compressors Ltd.	Allahabad	2
1367	Bhavan's College	Bombay	2
1368	Bhuneswar Dayal College	Patna	2
1369	Bidhan Chandra Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya	Bankura	2
1370	Bio Med Private Limited	Ghaziabad	2
1371	Biological Control Centre	Kheri	2
1372	Bisalpur Kisan Sahakari Chini Mill Ltd	Pilibhit	2
1373	Bisalpur Kisan Sahkari Chini Mills	Bisalpur	2
1374	Bombay Oil Industries Pvt. Ltd.	Bombay	2
1375	Botanical Survey of India	Yercaud	2
1376	BP Birsa Sciences Institute	Navsari	2
1377	BRD Post Graduate College	Deoria	2
1378	Buckau Wolf India Limited	Pune	2
1379	Burdwan Raj College	Burdwan	2
1380	Bureau of Indian Standards	New Delhi	2
1381	Camphor and Allied Products Ltd.	Bareilly	2
1382	Cardamom Research Station	Pampadumpara	2
1383	CARTMAN	Bangalore	2
1384	Castor Research Station	Sardar Krushinagar	2
1385	Cattle Breeding Farm	Kashmir	2
1386	Central Biological Control Station	Bhubaneswar	2
1387	Central Biological Control Station	Raipur	2
1388	Central Board of Irrigation and Power	New Delhi	2
1389	Central Cattle Breeding Farm	Sunabeda	2
1390	Central Inland Capture Fisheries Research Institute	Allahabad	2
1391	Central Inland Fisheries Research Institute	Tadepalligudem	2
1392	Central Institute for Cotton Research	Sirsa	2
1393	Central Integrated Pest Management Centre	Hyderabad	2
1394	Central Plantation Crops Research Institute	Jalpaiguri	2
1395	Central Plantation Crops Research Institute	Sipighat	2
1396	Central Potato Research Station	Kufri	2
1397	Central Poultry Training Institute	Bangalore	2
1398	Central Rainfed Lowland Rice Research Station	Kharagpur	2
1399	Central Sheep and Wool Research Institute	Kullu	2
1400	Central Sheep Breeding Farm	Hissar	2
1401	Central Silk Board, Regional Sericultural Research Station	Dehra Dun	2
1402	Central Soil and Water Conservation Research and Training Institute	Agra	2
1403	Central Surveillance Station	Kamal	2

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1404	Central Surveillance Station	Mysore	2
1405	Central Surveillance Station	Palampur	2
1406	Centre for Advanced Studies in Poultry Science	Trichur	2
1407	Centre for Application of Science and Technology for Rural Development	Pune	2
1408	Centre for Behavioural and Organizational Development (CBOD)	Hyderabad	2
1409	Centre for Earth Sciences	Thiruvananthapuram	2
1410	Centre for Environmental Planning and Technology	Ahmedabad	2
1411	Centre for Post Graduate Studies	Pondicherry	2
1412	Centre for Regional Ecological and Science Studies in Development Alternatives	Calcutta	2
1413	Century Seeds	Dharwad	2
1414	Chandernagore Government College	Chandernagore	2
1415	Cheyar Co-op. Sugar Mills Ltd	Cheyar	2
1416	Chh. Shahu Central Institute of Business Education and Research	Kolhapur	2
1417	Chikkaiah Naicker College	Erode	2
1418	CIL	Hyderabad	2
1419	Citrus Research Station	Tinsukia	2
1420	Co-operative College	Jamshedpur	2
1421	Co-operative Sugar Industries Ltd.	Nayagarh	2
1422	Co-ordinated Agronomic Experiment (Sugarcane)	Palacode	2
1423	Coconut Research Station	Vappankulam	2
1424	College of Agriculture	Karaikal	2
1425	College of Agriculture	Ludhiana	2
1426	College of Agriculture	Mandsaur	2
1427	College of Agriculture	Mysore	2
1428	College of Cooperation and Banking	Mannuthy	2
1429	College of Engineering	Madras	2
1430	College of Home Science	Chandigarh	2
1431	College of Pharmaceutical Sciences	Manipal	2
1432	College of Pharmacy	Indore	2
1433	College of Social Sciences and Humanities	Udaipur	2
1434	College of Veterinary Science and Animal Health	Durg	2
1435	Community Forestry Project	Baroda	2
1436	Consafe Science (India) Private Ltd.	Pune	2
1437	Coromandel Fertilisers Ltd.	Visakhapatnam	2
1438	Council for Social Development	Hyderabad	2
1439	Council of Science and Technology	Lucknow	2
1440	Council of Scientific and Industrial Research	Jammu	2
1441	Council of Scientific and Industrial Research	Jorhat	2
1442	Crop Research Station	Ghagharaghat	2

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1443	Cropping Systems Research Centre	Karamana	2
1444	Cyanamid (I) Ltd.	Hyderabad	2
1445	D.B. Mahavidyalaya	Bongaon	2
1446	D.B. Mahavidyalaya	Parganas	2
1447	D.R. College	Golaghat	2
1448	Daurala Sugar Works	Daurala	2
1449	Deccan College of Medical Sciences	Hyderabad	2
1450	Defence Agricultural Research Laboratory	Pithoragarh	2
1451	Defence Laboratory	Jodhpur	2
1452	Dep. Agriculture	Lamphepat	2
1453	Department of Animal Husbandry	Hyderabad	2
1454	Department of Fisheries	Kailash Nagar	2
1455	Department of Plant Pathology	Bangalore	2
1456	Department of Plant Pathology	Sabour	2
1457	Department of Sugar	Madras	2
1458	Department of Tribal Development	Bombay	2
1459	Diabetes Research Centre	Madras	2
1460	Directorate Irrigation Res. and Development	Pune	2
1461	Directorate of Agriculture	Midnapore	2
1462	Directorate of Lac Development	Ranchi	2
1463	Directorate of National Malaria Eradication Programme	New Delhi	2
1464	Directorate of Public Health and Preventive Medicine	Madras	2
1465	Disease Investigation Laboratory	Darjeeling	2
1466	District Rural Development Agency	Birbhum	2
1467	Documentation and Information Centre	New Delhi	2
1468	Dr. V.M. Medical College	Solapur	2
1469	Dry Farming Research Centre	Bawal	2
1470	Duck Research and Development Centre	Tiruchirappalli	2
1471	Dyal Singh College	Kamal	2
1472	Environmental Physiology Laboratory	Amravati	2
1473	Ergonomics Laboratory, NITIE	Bombay	2
1474	Ewing Christian College	Allahabad	2
1475	Fatima Mata National College	Kollam	2
1476	Filtra Material Research Pvt. Ltd.	Bombay	2
1477	Forest Department	Lucknow	2
1478	Forest Department	Madikeri	2
1479	Forest Department	Mysore	2
1480	Forest Department, Social Forestry Monitoring and Evaluation Division	Gangtok	2
1481	Forest Development Corporation	Bhopal	2
1482	Fruit Research Station	Bilaspur	2
1483	Fruit Research Station	Mangrol	2
1484	Ganesh Scientific Research Foundation	New Delhi	2

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1485	Gaya College	Gaya	2
1486	Godrej Soaps Limited	Bombay	2
1487	Government Arts and Science College	Durg	2
1488	Government Beekeeping Station	Nainital	2
1489	Government City Science College	Hyderabad	2
1490	Government College	Beawar	2
1491	Government College	Dholpur	2
1492	Government College	Kota	2
1493	Government College of Arts and Science	Kamareddy	2
1494	Government Medical College	Jabalpur	2
1495	Government Medical College	Jammu	2
1496	Government Model College of Science	Raipur	2
1497	Government of Madhya Pradesh	Indore	2
1498	Government Post Graduate College	Chhindwara	2
1499	Government Valley Fruit Research Station	Nainital	2
1500	Govind Ballabh Pant University of Agriculture and Technology	Meerut	2
1501	Gujarat Agricultural University	Vijapur	2
1502	Haryana Agricultural University	Kurukshetra	2
1503	Haryana Agricultural University	Sirsa	2
1504	Himachal Pradesh Krishi Vishvavidyalaya	Solan	2
1505	Hindu College	Moradabad	2
1506	Holy Cross College	Tiruchirapalli	2
1507	Horticultural Regional Research Sub-Station	Tabo	2
1508	Horticultural Research Station	Solan	2
1509	Horticultural Research Station	Uttar Kashi	2
1510	Horticulture Research Station	Jammu	2
1511	Hoskote Research Centre, Central Silvicultural Zone	Bangalore	2
1512	IARI Regional Station	Hyderabad	2
1513	ICI India Limited	Madras	2
1514	ICID Working Group on Irrigation Efficiency	New Delhi	2
1515	ICMR Advanced Centre in Reproductive Biology	Ludhiana	2
1516	ILO Asian Regional Team for Employment Promotion (ARTEP)	New Delhi	2
1517	Indian Agricultural Research Institute	Izatnagar	2
1518	Indian Cardamom Research Institute, Regional Research Station	Coimbatore	2
1519	Indian Council of Agricultural Research	Hyderabad	2
1520	Indian Council of Agricultural Research	Kanpur	2
1521	Indian Council of Agricultural Research, Jute Technological Research Laboratories	Calcutta	2
1522	Indian Grain Storage Institute	Jabalpur	2
1523	Indian Jute Industries' Research Association	Calcutta	2
1524	Indian Petrochemicals Corporation Limited	Baroda	2

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1525	Indian Veterinary Research Institute	Bhopal	2
1526	Indira Gandhi National Forest Academy	Dehra Dun	2
1527	Indo-Italian Fruit Development Project	Dehra Dun	2
1528	Institute Francais de Pondichery	Pondicherry	2
1529	Institute of Advanced Study in Science and Technology	Gauhati	2
1530	Institute of Animal Health and Veterinary Biologicals	Hebbal	2
1531	Institute of Applied Manpower Research	New Delhi	2
1532	Institute of Food and Dairy Technology	Koduvalli	2
1533	Institute of Medical Sciences	New Delhi	2
1534	Institute of Nuclear Medicine and Allied Sciences	Lucknow	2
1535	Institute of Pathology (ICMR)	New Delhi	2
1536	Institute of Post Graduate Medical Education and Research	Calcutta	2
1537	Institute of Rural Health Studies	Hyderabad	2
1538	Institute of Science	Aurangabad	2
1539	Institute of Technology	Varanasi	2
1540	International Rice Research Institute	New Delhi	2
1541	International Union for the Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources	New Delhi	2
1542	Isabella Thoburn College	Lucknow	2
1543	J. and J. DeChane Laboratories Pvt. Ltd.	Hyderabad	2
1544	J.J. College	Gaya	2
1545	J.N. Medical College	Belgaum	2
1546	J.N. Technological University	Hyderabad	2
1547	Jalgaon Forest Division	Jalgaon	2
1548	Jaslok Hospital, Nephrology Department	Bombay	2
1549	Jawaharlal Nehru College	Pasighat	2
1550	Jawaharlal Nehru Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya	Khandwa	2
1551	Jawaharlal Nehru Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya	Morena	2
1552	Jersey Cattle Farm	Banavasi	2
1553	Jeypore Forest Division	Koraput	2
1554	K.B. College	Bermo	2
1555	K.D. Research Station	Srinagar	2
1556	K.L. College of Engineering	Kunchanapalli	2
1557	K.N.P. College of Veterinary Science	Shirval	2
1558	K.R.G. Post Graduate College	Gwalior	2
1559	Kaira District Co-operative Milk Producers' Union Ltd.	Anand	2
1560	Kamaraj College	Tuticorin	2
1561	Kamla Nehru Institute of Physical and Social Sciences	Sultanpur	2
1562	Kerala State Land Use Board	Thiruvananthapuram	2
1563	Khaparde Bagicha	Amravati	2

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1564	Kilburn Engineering Limited	Bombay	2
1565	KN Government Post Graduate College	Varanasi	2
1566	Kolar Forest Division	Kolar	2
1567	Krishi Vigyan Kendra	Dhaulakuan	2
1568	Krishi Vigyan Kendra	Rampura	2
1569	L.M. College of Pharmacy	Ahmedabad	2
1570	Lady Hardinge Medical College	New Delhi	2
1571	Larsen and Toubro Ltd.	Bombay	2
1572	Livestock Research and Development Centre	Erode	2
1573	Livestock Research and Development Centre	Tirunelveli	2
1574	M.B.B. College	Agartala	2
1575	M.E.S. College	Bangalore	2
1576	M.L.N. Medical College	Allahabad	2
1577	M.S. College	Motihari	2
1578	M.U.C. Women's College	Burdwan	2
1579	Madhav Sugro Tech (P) Ltd.	Pune	2
1580	Madhya Pradesh Agricultural University	Rahuri	2
1581	Mahalakshmi Sugar Mills Co. Ltd.	Iqbalpur	2
1582	Maheshwaram Watershed Development Project	Hyderabad	2
1583	Makum and Namdang Tea Co.	Margherita	2
1584	Malaria Research Centre	Goa	2
1585	Malaria Research Centre	Madras	2
1586	Malaria Research Centre (Field Station)	Haridwar	2
1587	Malaria Research Centre (Field Station)	Rourkela	2
1588	Marwari College	Ranchi	2
1589	Mawana Sugar Works	Mawana	2
1590	Mecheri Sheep Research Station	Pottaneri	2
1591	Medical College	Amritsar	2
1592	Medical Hospital and Research Centre	New Delhi	2
1593	Medicolegal Institute, Gandhi Medical College Building	Bhopal	2
1594	Micronutrient Laboratory, IBFEP, HFC	Basti	2
1595	Micronutrient Laboratory, IBFEP, HFC	Gwalior	2
1596	Micronutrient Laboratory, IBFEP, HFC	Namrup	2
1597	Milind College of Sciences	Aurangabad	2
1598	Modern College	Pune	2
1599	Mysore Feeds Ltd.	Bangalore	2
1600	Nagarjuna Co-operative Sugars Ltd.	Gurazala	2
1601	Nagarjuna Fertilisers and Chemicals Ltd.	Kakinada	2
1602	National Academy of Sciences	New Delhi	2
1603	National Agricultural Research Project	Balasore	2
1604	National Biofertiliser Development Centre	Ghaziabad	2
1605	National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources, Regional Station	Jodhpur	2

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1606	National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources, Regional Station	Nainital	2
1607	National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources, Regional Station	Trichur	2
1608	National Bureau of Soil Survey and Land Use Planning (ICAR)	Udaipur	2
1609	National Centre for Mushroom Research Laboratory	Chambaghat	2
1610	National Centre of Agricultural Economics and Policy Research (NCAP)	New Delhi	2
1611	National Council of Applied Economic Research	New Delhi	2
1612	National Dairy Development Board	New Delhi	2
1613	National Environmental Engineering Research institute	Madras	2
1614	National Faculty for Plant Tissue Culture Repository	New Delhi	2
1615	National Fertilizers Ltd.	Panipat	2
1616	National Institute of Communicable Disease	Patna	2
1617	National Institute of Communicable Diseases	Calicut	2
1618	National Institute of Communicable Diseases	Varanasi	2
1619	National Malaria Eradication Programme	Jabalpur	2
1620	National Malaria Eradication Programme	Panaji	2
1621	National Museum of Natural History	New Delhi	2
1622	National Physical Laboratory	New Delhi	2
1623	National Research Centre for Spices	Madikeri	2
1624	National Research Institute	Bankura	2
1625	Neem Mission	Pune	2
1626	New Forest	Dehra Dun	2
1627	Neyveli Lignite Corporation Ltd.	Neyveli	2
1628	North Lakhimpur College	North Lakhimpur	2
1629	NWFP Agricultural University	Peshawar	2
1630	Oilseeds Research Station	Tindivanam	2
1631	Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology	G. Udayagiri	2
1632	Pachalyappa's College	Madras	2
1633	Paddy Processing Research Centre	Tiruvarur	2
1634	Paradeep Phosphates Limited	New Delhi	2
1635	Parasite Multiplication Unit	Bangalore	2
1636	Parasitological Research Station	Karnal	2
1637	Pashupalan Bhawan	Ranchi	2
1638	Patna Medical College	Patna	2
1639	Pesticides Association of India	New Delhi	2
1640	Plant Quarantine and Fumigation Station	Bombay	2
1641	Plasmodium falciparum Containment Programme (PFCP) Zone II	Bhubaneswar	2
1642	Plasmodium falciparum monitoring team	Bangalore	2
1643	Poornaprajna College	Udup	2

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1644	Poultry Research and Development Centre	Namakkal	2
1645	Poultry Research and Development Centre	Tiruchirapalli	2
1646	Pratisthan Mahavidyala	Paithan	2
1647	Projects and Development India Ltd.	New Delhi	2
1648	Providence Women's College	Calicut	2
1649	Pulse Research Station	Junagadh	2
1650	Pulses Research Station	Sardar Krushinagar	2
1651	Punjab Agricultural University	Kapurthala	2
1652	Rajasthan Agricultural University	Samastipur	2
1653	Rajasthan State Mines and Minerals Ltd.	Pune	2
1654	Ramnarain Ruia College	Bombay	2
1655	Ramniranjan Jhunjhunwala College	Bombay	2
1656	Rani Parvati Devi College	Belgaum	2
1657	Raymond's Embryo Research Centre	Gopalnagar	2
1658	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Mandsaur	2
1659	Regional Coffee Research Station	Wayanad	2
1660	Regional College of Education	Bhubaneswar	2
1661	Regional Engineering College	Kurukshetra	2
1662	Regional Engineering College	Tiruchirapalli	2
1663	Regional Engineering College	Warangal	2
1664	Regional Fruit Research Station	Vemgurla	2
1665	Regional Institute of Technology	Jamshedpur	2
1666	Regional Malaria Research Centre	Dibrugarh	2
1667	Regional Office for Health and Family Welfare	Pune	2
1668	Regional Research Laboratory	Itanagar	2
1669	Regional Research Station	Bajaura	2
1670	Regional Research Station	Bathinda	2
1671	Regional Research Station	Bhawanipatna	2
1672	Regional Research Station	Kalahandi	2
1673	Regional Research Station	Ropar	2
1674	Regional Research Station	Sardar Krushinagar	2
1675	Regional Research Station	Tikamgarh	2
1676	Regional Research Station	Tiptur	2
1677	Regional Sericultural Research Station	Koraput	2
1678	Regional Station	Coimbatore	2
1679	Rhone-Poulence Agrochemicals (India) Limited	Bombay	2
1680	Rice Research Station	Kayankulam	2
1681	Rice Research Station	Palampur	2
1682	Rishi Bankim Chandra College	Naihat	2
1683	RLSY College	Aurangabad	2
1684	RNT Medical College	Udaipur	2
1685	Roussels India Limited	New Delhi	2
1686	Rubber Research Institute of India	Kunjban	2
1687	Rural Home Science College	Dharwad	2

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1688	S.A.T Hospital	Thiruvananthapuram	2
1689	S.D. Coll.	Hathras	2
1690	S.H. Kisan Post Graduate College	Basti	2
1691	S.P. College	Srinagar	2
1692	S.S. Memorial College	Ranchi	2
1693	Sabarmati Ashram Gaushala	Kheda	2
1694	Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics	Calcutta	2
1695	Sahu Jain College	Najibabad	2
1696	Sakthi Sugars Limited	Periyar	2
1697	Sandoz	Bombay	2
1698	Sarabhai Research Centre	Baroda	2
1699	Sardar Sarovar Narmada Nigam Ltd.	Gandhinagar	2
1700	Sarvodaya Mahavidyalaya of Science Arts and Commerce	Sindewahi	2
1701	School of Life Sciences	Indore	2
1702	School of Planning, CEPT	Navrangpura	2
1703	Science College	Nanded	2
1704	SciTech Centre	Bombay	2
1705	Scott-Christian College	Nagercoil	2
1706	Seed Technology Research Project	Hyderabad	2
1707	Senthikumara Nadar College	Virudhunagar	2
1708	Shahabad Cooperative Sugar Mills Ltd.	Shahabad	2
1709	Shanti Kutir	Bikaner	2
1710	Sharda Sahayak Command Area Development Project	Lucknow	2
1711	Shivaji College	Udgir	2
1712	Shri Bhogawati S.S.K. Ltd.	Kolhapur	2
1713	Shri Bhogawati Sahkari Sakhar Karkhana Ltd.	Parite	2
1714	Shri G.S. Institute of Science and Technology	Indore	2
1715	Shri Ram Centre for Industrial Relations and Human Resources	New Delhi	2
1716	Shri Shivaji College of Agriculture	Amravati	2
1717	Siliguri College	Siliguri	2
1718	Silvicultural Division	Guahati	2
1719	Smt. Kasu Raghavamma Brahmananda Reddy College	Narasaraopet	2
1720	SNDT Women's University	Bombay	2
1721	Social Forestry Division	Panipat	2
1722	Social Forestry Division	Rae Bareli	2
1723	Social Forestry Project Division	Sundargarh	2
1724	Society of Indian Foresters	Dehra Dun	2
1725	Socio-Economic Unit	Thiruvananthapuram	2
1726	Soil and Water Management Research Institute	Thanjavur	2
1727	Soil Research Laboratory	Midnapore	2
1728	South Calcutta Veterinary Clinic	Calcutta	2

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1729	Southern Petrochemical Industries Corporation Limited	Madras	2
1730	Spices Board	Cochin	2
1731	Spices Research Station	Mehsana	2
1732	Sri Ramachandra Medical College	Madras	2
1733	Sri Sathya Sai Institute of Higher Learning	Prasantinilayam	2
1734	Sri Venkateswara Medical College	Tirupati	2
1735	Sripat Singh College	Jiaganj	2
1736	St. Columba's College	Hazaribagh	2
1737	St. Joseph's College	Tiruchirapalli	2
1738	St. Martha's Hospital	Bangalore	2
1739	State Planning Board	Bhubaneswar	2
1740	Sugar and Process Industry, HiG, L-1, Kursi Road, Aliganj	Lucknow	2
1741	Sugar Technologists' Association of India	New Delhi	2
1742	Suri Vidyasagar College	Birbhum	2
1743	Syndicate Bank	Betigeri	2
1744	Synthite Industrial Chemicals Ltd	Kolenchery	2
1745	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Bhavanisagar	2
1746	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Madras	2
1747	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Mettupalayam	2
1748	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Sirugamani	2
1749	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Tiruchirapalli	2
1750	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Tirur	2
1751	Tamil Nadu Newsprint and Papers Limited	Kagithapuram	2
1752	Tata Oil Mills Company Ltd.	Bombay	2
1753	Tata Research Development Design Centre	Pune	2
1754	Tata Tea Limited	Munnar	2
1755	Techno-Economic Research Institute	New Delhi	2
1756	The Fertilisers and Chemicals Travancore Ltd	Hyderabad	2
1757	The Voluntary Health Services	Madras	2
1758	Tropical Pine Research Centre	Kodaikanal	2
1759	Udyog Vihar	Gurgaon	2
1760	University College of Agriculture	Calcutta	2
1761	University College of Medicine	Calcutta	2
1762	University of Agricultural Sciences	Tiptur	2
1763	University of Indore	Indore	2
1764	University of Manipur	Canchipur	2
1765	University of Orissa	Bhubaneswar	2
1766	University of Visva-Bharati	Santiniketan	2
1767	Uttar Pradesh Council of Agricultural Research	Lucknow	2
1768	Uttar Pradesh Council of Sugarcane Research	Muzaffarnagar	2
1769	V.P. and R.P.T.P. Science College	Vallabh Vidyanagar	2
1770	VC Farm	Mandya	2

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1771	Vegetable Research Station	Jalandhar	2
1772	Vegetable Research Station	Kinnaur	2
1773	Vellore Cooperative Sugar Mills Ltd.	Ambedkar	2
1774	Venco R & D Farm Ltd	Pune	2
1775	Veterinary College	Dharwad	2
1776	Veterinary College	Udgir	2
1777	Vidyasagar College for Women	Calcutta	2
1778	Vittal Mallya Scientific Research Foundation	Bangalore	2
1779	Vivek Vardhini College	Hyderabad	2
1780	Walchand College of Engineering	Vishrambag	2
1781	WALMI	Bhubaneswar	2
1782	WAPCOS	New Delhi	2
1783	Wasteland Development Corporation	Calcutta	2
1784	Water and Land Management Institute	Anand	2
1785	Water Management Research Centre	Belvatagi	2
1786	Western India Plywoods Ltd.	Cannanore	2
1787	Western Regional Research Center (CIRG)	Jaipur	2
1788	Wilson College	Bombay	2
1789	Working Plans Division	Dharwad	2
1790	Yashwantrao Chavan Maharashtra Open University	Nashik	2
1791	Zoological Survey of India	Itanagar	2
1792	Zoological Survey of India	Jodhpur	2
1793	Zoological Survey of India	Pune	2
1794	Zoological Survey of India	Shillong	2
1795	A. Antony School of Marine Sciences	Cochin	1
1796	A. R. Mehta Head and Neck Service 'C', Tata Memorial Hospital	Bombay	1
1797	A.C. College	Madras	1
1798	A.N College, Post Graduate Centre	Patna	1
1799	A.P.C. College	New Barrackpore	1
1800	A.V. Thomas Group Companies	Cochin	1
1801	Academic Staff College	Waltair	1
1802	ACSTI	Dhalli Shimla	1
1803	Action for Food Production	New Delhi	1
1804	Adaptive Research Station	Madhapur	1
1805	Additional Block Animal Health Centre	Baraturigram	1
1806	Agri-Tech Associates	Pune	1
1807	Agric. Res. Inst., Water Technol. Cent.	New Delhi	1
1808	Agric. Univ., Dep. Soils	Ludhiana	1
1809	Agricultural and Technology University	Kanpur	1
1810	Agricultural College, Soil Survey and Land Use Planning Centre	Bihar	1
1811	Agricultural Consultant	Madras	1
1812	Agricultural Department	Srinagar	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1813	Agricultural Engineering Institute	Raichur	1
1814	Agricultural Experiment Station	Durgapura	1
1815	Agricultural Market Committee	Guntur	1
1816	Agricultural Research Information Centre	Hissar	1
1817	Agricultural Research Institute, National Facility for Blue-Green Algal Collections	New Delhi	1
1818	Agricultural Research Service	Mandya	1
1819	Agricultural Research Station	Achalpur	1
1820	Agricultural Research Station	Adilabad	1
1821	Agricultural Research Station	Anantharajupeta	1
1822	Agricultural Research Station	Bheemaranaganudi	1
1823	Agricultural Research Station	Kathalagere	1
1824	Agricultural Research Station	Mugad	1
1825	Agricultural Research Station	Navgaon	1
1826	Agricultural Research Station	North Lakhimpur	1
1827	Agricultural Research Station	Pulla	1
1828	Agricultural Research Station	Sangli	1
1829	Agricultural Research Station	Shirgaon	1
1830	Agricultural Research Station	Waraseoni	1
1831	Agricultural Research Sub-Station	Aklera	1
1832	Agricultural Research Sub-Station	Diggi	1
1833	Agricultural Research Substation	Jhalawar	1
1834	Agricultural School	Hiwara	1
1835	Agricultural Station	Chintapalli	1
1836	Agricultural University	Anantapur	1
1837	Agricultural University	Namakkal	1
1838	Agricultural University	Sriganganagar	1
1839	Agriculture and Cooperation Department	Hyderabad	1
1840	Agriculture college	Annamalai Nagar	1
1841	Agriculture college	Coimbatore	1
1842	Agriculture college	Guntur	1
1843	Agriculture College	Gwalior	1
1844	Agriculture Research Station	Badnapur	1
1845	Agriculture Research Station	Cuddapah	1
1846	Agriculture Research Station	Hassan	1
1847	Agriculture Research Station	Kadiri	1
1848	Agriculture Research Station	Mandsaur	1
1849	Agriculture Research Station	Mohol	1
1850	Agriculture Research Station	Palghar	1
1851	Agriculture Research Station	Sikar	1
1852	Agriculture Research Station	Sirsa	1
1853	Agriculture Research Station	Solan	1
1854	Agriculture Research Station	Udaipur	1
1855	Agriculture Research Station	Vriddhachalam	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1856	Agro-Economic Research Centre	Jabalpur	1
1857	Agro-Economic Research Centre	Shantiniketan	1
1858	Agroforestry Livestock Research Station	Palghat	1
1859	Agronomic Cropping System Research	Indore	1
1860	Agronomy, KVK	Bidar	1
1861	Ahmedabad Study Action Group	Ahmedabad	1
1862	AIC Wheat Improvement Project	Bilaspur	1
1863	AICRP on Forage Crops, Regional Research Station	Tiptur	1
1864	AICRP on Pigs	Jabalpur	1
1865	Alagappa College of Technology	Madras	1
1866	Alchemie Research Centre	Thane	1
1867	All India Co-ordinated Agronomic Research Project	Meerut	1
1868	All India Co-ordinated Cashew Improvement Project	Bhubaneswar	1
1869	All India Co-ordinated Maize Improvement Project	Kolhapur	1
1870	All India Co-ordinated Project on Tuber Crops	Hyderabad	1
1871	All India Co-ordinated Research Project for Dryland Agriculture	Hyderabad	1
1872	All India Co-ordinated Research Project on Cattle	Mohanpur	1
1873	All India Co-ordinated Research Project on Oilseeds (Safflower)	Solapur	1
1874	All India Co-ordinated Soil Test Crop Response Project	Hyderabad	1
1875	All India Coordinated Pulses Improvement Project	Badnapur	1
1876	All India Coordinated Research Project on Agroforestry	Rahuri	1
1877	All India Coordinated Research Project on Whitegrubs (ICAR)	Durgapura	1
1878	All India Coordinated Vegetable Improvement Project	Ambajogai	1
1879	All India Directorate of Rice Research Institute	Hyderabad	1
1880	All India Soil and Land Use Survey	New Delhi	1
1881	Alphonsa College	Arunapuram	1
1882	Ambedkar Medical College	Bangalore	1
1883	Amrat Kapadia Navjivan Women's College	Hyderabad	1
1884	Amravati Forest Division	Amravati	1
1885	Amul Research and Development Association	Anand	1
1886	Analchem Laboratories	Mysore	1
1887	Anantapur Circle	Anantapur	1
1888	Anbil Dharmalingam Agricultural College	Pallapuram	1
1889	Andhra Medical College	Visakhapatnam	1
1890	Andhra Pradesh Agricultural University	Jagtial	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1891	Animal Disease Investigation Unit	Tirunelveli	1
1892	Animal Health and Production Institute	Patna	1
1893	Animal Health Centre	Kurnool	1
1894	Animal Health Centre	Lalgola	1
1895	Animal Health Centre	Sadamashipur	1
1896	Animal Health Centre	Srikakulam	1
1897	Animal Health Centre	Visakhapatnam	1
1898	Animal Husbandry	Nellore	1
1899	Animal Husbandry	Vizianagaram	1
1900	Animal Husbandry and Veterinary Services	Cuttack	1
1901	Animal Husbandry and Veterinary Services	Port Blair	1
1902	Animal Production Research Institute	Samastipur	1
1903	Anthropological Survey of India	Calcutta	1
1904	Anthropological Survey of India	New Delhi	1
1905	APE Bellis India Ltd.	New Delhi	1
1906	Arabinda Sarani	Basunagar	1
1907	Aranya Bhavana	Bangalore	1
1908	Aravalli Afforestation Programme	Udaipur	1
1909	Aravind Eye Hospital and Post Graduate Institute of Ophthalmology	Madurai	1
1910	Archaeological Survey of India	Bhubaneswar	1
1911	Archaeology and Museums	Jaipur	1
1912	Arignar Anna Government Arts College for Men	Namakkal	1
1913	Arignar Anna Zoo	Madras	1
1914	Aromatic and Medicinal Plants Research Station	Odakkali	1
1915	ARTEP	New Delhi	1
1916	Artificial Insemination Extension Office, Sheep and Wool Department	Bikaner	1
1917	Arts, Science and Commerce College	Shahada	1
1918	Arts, Science and Commerce College Post Graduate Department of Zoology	Shahabad	1
1919	Assam Agriculture University	Khanapara	1
1920	Atarra Post Graduate College	Atarra (Banda)	1
1921	Atul Products Ltd.	New Delhi	1
1922	Avadh Girls College	Lucknow	1
1923	Avadh University	Faizabad	1
1924	Ayacut Research Station Khaperkheda	Hoshangabad	1
1925	B. J. Medical College and New Civil Hospital	Asarwa	1
1926	B.J. Medical College and Civil Hospital	Ahmedabad	1
1927	B.K.S Jain and Associates	Bombay	1
1928	B.N. College	Hooghly	1
1929	B.R. Singh Hospital and Centre for Medical Education and Research	Calcutta	1
1930	B.R.M. College	Munger	1
1931	Bai Jerbai Wadia Hospital for Children	Bombay	1

SI No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1932	Ballarpur Industries Ltd.	Chandrapur	1
1933	Bangabasi College	Calcutta	1
1934	Bangur Institute of Neurology	Calcutta	1
1935	Bank of Baroda	Palapamu	1
1936	Bapuji Dental College and Hospital	Davangere	1
1937	Basic Seed Multiplication and Training Centre	Varanasi	1
1938	Basik Breeders Pvt. Ltd.	Hyderabad	1
1939	BBJP Science College	Talod	1
1940	Bee Research Station	Nagrota-bagwan	1
1941	Beloniya College	Beloniya	1
1942	Beneficiary Assessment of National Sericulture Project	Bangalore	1
1943	Bengal Engineering College	Howrah	1
1944	BERC, IIT	Hauz Khas	1
1945	Betelvine Research Station	Nashik	1
1946	Bhadrak College	Bhadra	1
1947	Bhagwanpura Sugar Mills Limited	Dhuri	1
1948	Bhakra Beas Management Board	Nangal	1
1949	Bharat Kala Bhavan	Varanasi	1
1950	Bharathidasan College for Women	Pondicherry	1
1951	Bharatiya Sugar	Pune	1
1952	Bhartiya Agro-Industries Foundation	Ahmedabad	1
1953	Bhavan's New Science College	Narayangud	1
1954	Bhubaneswar Development Authority	Bhubaneswar	1
1955	Bidhan Chandra Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya	Calcutta	1
1956	Bidhan Chandra Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya	Cooch Behar	1
1957	Bihar Agricultural Research Institute	Patna	1
1958	Bio-Control Laboratory	Harinagar	1
1959	Bio-Tissue Labs Private Ltd.	Hyderabad	1
1960	Biocontrol and Pest Management Consultant	Bangalore	1
1961	Biodeg Chemical and Allied Industry	Kanpur	1
1962	Biolaboratory	Calcutta	1
1963	Biological Control Station	Lalandi	1
1964	Biological Control Station	Srinagar	1
1965	Biotechnology and Seeds Division	Madras	1
1966	Biotechnology Centre for Tree Improvement	Tirupati	1
1967	Birla College of Arts, Science and Commerce	Kalyani	1
1968	Birla Institute of Scientific Research	Amlai	1
1969	Birla Institute of Scientific Research	Jaipur	1
1970	Birla Institute of Technology and Science	Pilani	1
1971	Birla Vidya Mandir	Nainital	1
1972	Bishop Heber College	Tiruchirapalli	1
1973	BN Mahavidyalaya	Itachun	1
1974	Bombay College of Pharmacy	Bombay	1
1975	Bombay Hospital	Bombay	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1976	Botanical Survey of India	Pauri Garhwal	1
1977	Brahmanand Post Graduate College	Hamirpur	1
1978	BRD Medical College	Gorakhpur	1
1979	Brijal Science College	Amravati	1
1980	Britannia Industries Limited, Soya Complex	Vidisha	1
1981	British Council Division, British High Commission	New Delhi	1
1982	BSA College	Mathura	1
1983	BSH College	Bangalore	1
1984	BSK Post Graduate College	Maithon	1
1985	Buffalo Breeding Centre	Nekarikallu	1
1986	Bundelkhand Farm Development Centre	Hamirpur	1
1987	Bureau of Indian Standards	Ahmedabad	1
1988	Bureau of Indian Standards	Kanpur	1
1989	Bureau of Industrial Costs and Prices	New Delhi	1
1990	C.C. Patel and Associates	New Delhi	1
1991	C.G.N. College	Gola Gokarannath	1
1992	C.T. Bora College, Shirur-Ghodnadi	Pune	1
1993	Calcutta Metropolitan Water and Sanitation Authority	Calcutta	1
1994	Calcutta Municipal Corporation	Calcutta	1
1995	Calcutta National Medical College	Calcutta	1
1996	Calcutta Port Trust	Haldia	1
1997	Canara Bank	Dharwad	1
1998	Cardamom Planters' Association College	Bodinayakanur	1
1999	Cardamom Research Centre	Kodagu	1
2000	Carishma Food Consultancy Services	New Delhi	1
2001	Cashew Research Station	Kavali	1
2002	Cattle Project, L.R.S.	Guntur	1
2003	Cauvery Sugars and Chemical	Cauvery	1
2004	CBM College	Coimbatore	1
2005	Cecidological Society of India	Allahabad	1
2006	CENDIT	New Delhi	1
2007	Center for Women's Development	New Delhi	1
2008	Central Avian Research Institute	Bareilly	1
2009	Central Biological Control Station	Burdwan	1
2010	Central Board for Control of Water Pollution	New Delhi	1
2011	Central Botanical Research Institute	Lucknow	1
2012	Central Coffee Research Inst., Coffee Research Station	Balehonnur	1
2013	Central Council for Research in Ayurveda and Siddha	Tarikhet	1
2014	Central Council for Research in Ayurveda and Siddha, Government of India	Calcutta	1
2015	Central Electro-Chemical Research Institute	Madras	1

SI No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2016	Central Electro-Chemical Research Institute	Tuticorin	1
2017	Central Food Laboratory	Calcutta	1
2018	Central Food Technological Research Institute	Nagpur	1
2019	Central Ground Water Board	New Delhi	1
2020	Central Inland Capture Fisheries Research Sub-Station	Calcutta	1
2021	Central Inland Fisheries Centre	Gauhati	1
2022	Central Inland Fisheries Research Institute	Bhubaneswar	1
2023	Central Institute for Research on Cotton Technology, Regional Unit	Guntur	1
2024	Central Institute of Brackishwater Aquaculture	Madras	1
2025	Central Institute of Coastal Engineering for Fishery	Bangalore	1
2026	Central Institute of Coir Technology	Bangalore	1
2027	Central Institute of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants	Nagla	1
2028	Central Institute of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants	Srinagar	1
2029	Central Integrated Pest Management Centre	Faridabad	1
2030	Central Livestock Research and Breeding Station	Haringhata	1
2031	Central Mango Research Station (IHR)	Lucknow	1
2032	Central Muga Research and Training Institute	Jorhat	1
2033	Central Plant Protection Station	Cuttack	1
2034	Central Plantation Crops Research Institute	Tumkur	1
2035	Central Plantation Crops Research Institute Research Centre	Kodagu	1
2036	Central Pollution Control Board	New Delhi	1
2037	Central Potato Research Station	Gwalior	1
2038	Central Potato Research Station	Mukteswar	1
2039	Central Potato Research Station	Muthorai	1
2040	Central Poultry Breeding Farm	Bombay	1
2041	Central Poultry Farm	Patna	1
2042	Central Public Health and Drugs Laboratory	Calcutta	1
2043	Central Road Research Institute	New Delhi	1
2044	Central Sericultural Research and Training Institute	Jalpaiguri	1
2045	Central Sericultural Research and Training Inst.	Samayanallur	1
2046	Central Silk Board	Muzaffarpur	1
2047	Central Silk Board	Vellanadu	1
2048	Central Silk Board, Regional Sericultural Research Station	Kalimpong	1
2049	Central Soil and Materials Research Station	New Delhi	1
2050	Central Soil and Water Conservation Research and Training Institute	Ootacamund	1
2051	Central Soil Research Institute, Regional Research Station	Anand	1
2052	Central Surveillance Station	Shimoga	1
2053	Central Surveillance Station	Tiruchirapalli	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2054	Central Tasar Research and Training Institute	Bir	1
2055	Central Tasar Research and Training Institute	Faizabad	1
2056	Central Tasar Silkworm Seed Station	Lakha	1
2057	Central Tobacco Research Institute	Guntur	1
2058	Central Warehousing Corporation	Bangalore	1
2059	Central Warehousing Corporation	New Delhi	1
2060	Central Wool Sheep Research Institute	Garsa	1
2061	Centre for Agricultural Marketing	Jaipur	1
2062	Centre for Animal Health Studies and Veterinary Biological Research Centre	Madras	1
2063	Centre for Applied Systems Analysis in Development	Pune	1
2064	Centre for Development Alternatives	New Delhi	1
2065	Centre for Economic and Development Research	Ghaziabad	1
2066	Centre for Life Sciences	Siliguri	1
2067	Centre for Policy Research	New Delhi	1
2068	Centre for Research in Rural and Industrial Development	Chandigarh	1
2069	Centre for the Study of Developing Societies	New Delhi	1
2070	Centre for Weed Science and Technology	Vijayawada	1
2071	Centre of Advanced Studies in Agricultural Communication	Pantnagar	1
2072	Centre of Advanced Study in Botany	Varanasi	1
2073	Centre of Research for Development	Srinagar	1
2074	Centre of Sciences to Villages	Duttapur Wardima	1
2075	Century Pulp and Paper	Lalkua	1
2076	CEU/ACCERT, Institute of Child Health	Madras	1
2077	Chambal Command Area Development Project	Gwalior	1
2078	Chetackal Experiment Station	Chetackal	1
2079	Chief Conservator of Forests	Bhopal	1
2080	Children Medical Centre	New Delhi	1
2081	Chowgule College	Goa	1
2082	Christian Medical College and Hospital	Ludhiana	1
2083	Churachandpur College	Churachandpur	1
2084	CIPET	Madras	1
2085	Civil Veterinary Hospital	Dadahu	1
2086	Classified Specialist Preventive and Social Medicine	No. 8 Wing Air Force	1
2087	Coal Mining Research Station	Dhanbad	1
2088	Coconut Development Board	Thanjavur	1
2089	Coconut Research Station	Thiruvananthapuram	1
2090	Coconut Research Station,RCRS	Tandigudi	1
2091	Coffee Board	Mysore	1
2092	Coffee Board Research Department	Chettalli	1
2093	Coffee Research Substation	Kodagu	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2094	College of Agricultural Engineering	Samastipur	1
2095	College of Agricultural Engineering and Technology	Akola	1
2096	College of Agricultural Technology	Parbhani	1
2097	College of Agriculture	Anand	1
2098	College of Agriculture	Bijapur	1
2099	College of Agriculture	Meerut	1
2100	College of Agriculture	Samastipur	1
2101	College of Agriculture	Shalimar	1
2102	College of Agriculture and R.R. Station	Sopore	1
2103	College of Agriculture	Chittoor	1
2104	College of Basic Science and Humanities	Bhubaneswar	1
2105	College of Commerce	Patan	1
2106	College of Dairy Technology	Krishak Nagar	1
2107	College of Dental Surgery, K.M.C.	Manipal	1
2108	College of Engineering	Thiruvananthapuram	1
2109	College of Fisheries	Dholi	1
2110	College of Fisheries	Pantnagar	1
2111	College of Home Science	Hyderabad	1
2112	College of Home Science	Ludhiana	1
2113	College of Home Science	Parbhani	1
2114	College of Horticulture	Coimbatore	1
2115	College of India	Hyderabad	1
2116	College of Pharmaceutical Sciences	Thiruvananthapuram	1
2117	College of Science	Karad	1
2118	College of Veterinary Science	Khanapara	1
2119	College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry	Bangalore	1
2120	College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry	Gabalpur	1
2121	Commission for Agricultural Costs and Prices, Government of India	New Delhi	1
2122	Commissioner of Land Revenue	Hyderabad	1
2123	Committee for Child Care	Saharanpur	1
2124	Commonwealth Institute of Biological Control	Bangalore	1
2125	Community Organization	Rupnagar	1
2126	Conservator of Forests	Bellary	1
2127	Conservator of Forests (Planning)	Vadodara	1
2128	Consolidated Coffee Ltd.	Bangalore	1
2129	Consolidated Coffee Ltd.	Pollibetta	1
2130	Consulting Engineering Services (P) Ltd	New Delhi	1
2131	Contai Polytechnic	Minapore	1
2132	Coordinated Agronomic Research Project	Aligarh	1
2133	Coromandel Fertilisers Ltd.	Hyderabad	1
2134	Cotton Breeding Substation	Dhule	1

SI No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2135	Cotton College	Gauhati	1
2136	Cotton Research Institute	Sakrand	1
2137	Cotton Research Staion	Nanded	1
2138	Cotton Research Station	Muktsar	1
2139	Cotton Research Station	Nandad	1
2140	Cotton Technological Research Laboratory	Surat	1
2141	Council for Social Development	New Delhi	1
2142	Council of Agricultural Research	Lucknow	1
2143	Council of Applied Economic Research	New Delhi	1
2144	Council of Scientific and Industrial Research	Muzaffarnagar	1
2145	Council of Scientific and Industrial Research	Srinagar	1
2146	Crescent Hatchery and Prawn Farm	Eriyad	1
2147	Crop Health Product Limited	New Delhi	1
2148	CSR, ARS	Siruguppa	1
2149	CTRI Research Station	Jeelugumill	1
2150	Cummings Laboratory	New Delhi	1
2151	Cynamid India Ltd	Bangalore	1
2152	Cynamid India Ltd.	Bombay	1
2153	D.A.V. College	Chandigarh	1
2154	D.N. College	Hissar	1
2155	D.P.S. College	Dehra Dun	1
2156	D.R.R. Rajendranagar	Hyderabad	1
2157	D.S.B. College	Nainital	1
2158	Dairy Research Institute, Dairy Technology Division	Karnal	1
2159	Damodar Valley Corporation	Hazaribagh	1
2160	Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital	Laheriasarai	1
2161	Date Palm Research Sub-Station	Jhang	1
2162	Deccan College	Pune	1
2163	Deccan Development Society	Hyderabad	1
2164	Deccan Sugar Technologists' Association	Pune	1
2165	Defence Agricultural Research Laboratory	Nainital	1
2166	Defence Institute of Physiology and Allied Sciences	New Delhi	1
2167	Degree College	Supau	1
2168	Delhi School of Economics	New Delhi	1
2169	Dep. Agric. Engineering Inst. of Tech.	Kharagpur	1
2170	Department of Agriculture	Bilaspur	1
2171	Department of Agriculture	Arundhati Nagar	1
2172	Department of Agriculture	Hutbay	1
2173	Department of Agriculture	Imphal	1
2174	Department of Agriculture	Jorhar	1
2175	Department of Agriculture	Muzaffarabad	1
2176	Department of Agriculture	Port Blair	1

SI No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2177	Department of Agriculture	Pune	1
2178	Department of Agriculture	Shimla	1
2179	Department of Agronomy	Jodhpur	1
2180	Department of Animal Husbandry	Ghatanj	1
2181	Department of Animal Husbandry	Pune	1
2182	Department of Aquatic Biology	Mangalore	1
2183	Department of Assam	Khanapara	1
2184	Department of Atomic Energy	Hyderabad	1
2185	Department of Atomic Energy	New Delhi	1
2186	Department of Atomic Energy	Shillong	1
2187	Department of Biochemistry	Thiruvananthapuram	1
2188	Department of Biology	Haridwar	1
2189	Department of Biology	Pantnagar	1
2190	Department of Botany	Calcutta	1
2191	Department of Botany	Garhwal	1
2192	Department of Botany	Nanded	1
2193	Department of Child Health	Vellore	1
2194	Department of Economics and Politics	Santiniketan	1
2195	Department of Forestry	Nagpur	1
2196	Department of Forestry, Pharamshala Circle	Pharamshala	1
2197	Department of Forests	Bhopal	1
2198	Department of Forests	Dharwad	1
2199	Department of Forests	Panchkula	1
2200	Department of Forests	Thiruvananthapuram	1
2201	Department of Microbiology L.I.T. Premises	Nagpur	1
2202	Department of Neurovirology	Bangalore	1
2203	Department of Plant Breeding	Pantnagar	1
2204	Department of Plant Breeding	Rahuri	1
2205	Department of Plant Pathology	Diggi	1
2206	Department of Plant Pathology	Udaipur	1
2207	Department of Racing	Madras	1
2208	Department of Science, Tech. and Environment	Bhubaneswar	1
2209	Department of Sheep Husbandry	Jammu	1
2210	Department of Zoology	Chandigarh	1
2211	Deputy Conservator of Forests (Retd.)	Bangalore	1
2212	Deshbandhu College	New Delhi	1
2213	Devidayal Agro-chemicals	Pune	1
2214	Dey's Med. Stores (Mgf.) Ltd.	Calcutta	1
2215	Dhamala Beat, Surajpur Block, Pinjore Range	Haryana	1
2216	Dharamshala (Kangra)	Kangra	1
2217	Dinabandhu Andrews College	Calcutta	1
2218	Directorate General of Health Services	New Delhi	1
2219	Directorate of Agriculture	Durg	1
2220	Directorate of Agriculture	Haripad	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2221	Directorate of Agriculture	Jaipur	1
2222	Directorate of Agriculture	Port Blair	1
2223	Directorate of Cinchona and Other Medicinal Plants	Darjeeling	1
2224	Directorate of Economics and Statistics	New Delhi	1
2225	Directorate of Extension Education	Kota	1
2226	Directorate of Fisheries	Cottack	1
2227	Directorate of Health Services (Malaria and Filaria)	Pune	1
2228	Directorate of Horticulture	Bhubaneswar	1
2229	Directorate of Horticulture	Hyderabad	1
2230	Directorate of Marketing and Inspection	Nagpur	1
2231	Directorate of Plant Protection	Bikaner	1
2232	Directorate of Rice Research	Aduthurai	1
2233	Directorate of Sheep Husbandry	Srinagar	1
2234	Directorate of Sugar	Madras	1
2235	Directorate of Vegetable Research	New Delhi	1
2236	Directorate of Vegetable Research	Varanasi	1
2237	Directorate of Veterinary Services	Calcutta	1
2238	Directorate of Veterinary Services	Nadiad	1
2239	Directorate of Veterinary Services	Siliguri	1
2240	Directorate of Water Management Research M.P.K.V.	Rahuri	1
2241	Disease Insect Survey Regional Forest Research Centre	Jabalpur	1
2242	District Health Office	Ootacamund	1
2243	District Industries Centre	Muzaffarpur	1
2244	District Veterinary Hospital	Srinagar	1
2245	District Veterinary Office	Darjeeling	1
2246	Distt. Rural Dev. Agency	Gurdaspur	1
2247	Divisional Forest Officer	Dhenkanal	1
2248	Divisional Forest Officer	Gangtok	1
2249	DN College	Meerut	1
2250	Downy Mildew Research Laboratory	Mysore	1
2251	DPR, Regional Centre	Gwalior	1
2252	Dr P. R. Ghogery Science College	Dhule	1
2253	Dr. B.R. Ambedkar College	Hyderabad	1
2254	Dr. K.S. Krishnan Marg	New Delhi	1
2255	Dr. Sampurnanand Medical College	Jodhpur	1
2256	Dr. Y.S. Parmar University of Horticulture and Forestry	Nagarjunanagar	1
2257	Drug Laboratory	Calcutta	1
2258	Drug Research Laboratory	Jammu	1
2259	Durga College	Raipur	1
2260	Eco-development of Ganga Basin Projects	Kalyani	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2261	EID Parry Ltd.	Ennore	1
2262	Energy and Environment Group	New Delhi	1
2263	Engineering College	Tirupati	1
2264	Entomology College of Agriculture	Dharwad	1
2265	Entomology Unit, Karnataka State Sericulture Development Institute	Bangalore	1
2266	Environmental Planning and Coordination Organisation	Bhopal	1
2267	Environmental Research Station	Shimla	1
2268	Environmental Resources Research Centre	Thiruvananthapuram	1
2269	Eskayef Ltd.	Bangalore	1
2270	Evaluation and Monitoring Department	Lucknow	1
2271	Evening College	Shimla	1
2272	Extension Education Institute	Hyderabad	1
2273	FACT Engineering and Design Organization	Thiruvananthapuram	1
2274	FAI	Madras	1
2275	Faridabad Stainless and Steel Product Co. Pvt. Ltd.	Faridabad	1
2276	Feed and Fodder Jersey Cattle Farm	Kurnool	1
2277	Feroze Gandhi College	Rae Bareli	1
2278	Fertiliser and Manure Division	New Delhi	1
2279	Fertilizer Corp. of India	Fertilizer City	1
2280	Fertilizer Promotion and Agricultural Research Division, HFC	Sindri	1
2281	Fertiplant Engineering Co. Pvt. Ltd.	Bandra	1
2282	Field Station for Investigations on Locusts	Bikaner	1
2283	Fisheries College	Tuticorin	1
2284	Food and Drugs Laboratory	Vadodara	1
2285	Forest College and Research Institute	Mettupalayam	1
2286	Forest Department	Baroda	1
2287	Forest Department	Bellary	1
2288	Forest Department	Goa	1
2289	Forest Department	Hoshiarpur	1
2290	Forest Department	Karnal	1
2291	Forest Department	Kokrajhar	1
2292	Forest Department	Midnapore	1
2293	Forest Department	Multan	1
2294	Forest Department	Nagpur	1
2295	Forest Department	Ranchi	1
2296	Forest Division	Athmallik	1
2297	Forest Division	Vellore	1
2298	Forest Protection Division Institute of Deciduous Forests	Jabalpur	1
2299	Forest Research and Utilization Circle	Bangalore	1
2300	Forest Research and Working Plan Circle	Calcutta	1

SI No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2301	Forest Research Circle	Pune	1
2302	Forest Research Office	Ranchi	1
2303	Forest Research Station	Cuddapah	1
2304	Forest Research Station	Jalna	1
2305	Forest Research Wing of Mysore Paper Mills Ltd.	Shimoga	1
2306	Forest Soil-Vegetation Survey	Coimbatore	1
2307	Forest Soil-Vegetation Survey Western Region	Jabalpur	1
2308	Forest Utilization Division	Bangalore	1
2309	Forestry Consultant	Lucknow	1
2310	Forestry Department	Calcutta	1
2311	Forestry Department	Jammu	1
2312	Forestry Department	Kullu	1
2313	Forestry Research Station	Coimbatore	1
2314	Forests Department	Rajpipla	1
2315	Formulation Development Lab., IDPL	Virbhadra	1
2316	FORRAD	New Delhi	1
2317	Foundation Seed Programme for Sugarcane. Sub-Centre	Pravaranagar	1
2318	Foundation to Aid Industrial Recovery	New Delhi	1
2319	FRCH	Bombay	1
2320	Freshwater Fisheries Research Station	Kalyani	1
2321	Frontier Biotech	Phaltan	1
2322	Frozen Semen Laboratory	Pune	1
2323	Fruit Research Station	Gurdaspur	1
2324	Fruit Research Station	Nagpur	1
2325	Fruit Research Station	Rewa	1
2326	Fruit Research Station	Srinigar	1
2327	Fruit Research Sub-station	Gurgaon	1
2328	G.B. Mahavidyalaya	Rohtas	1
2329	G.B. Plant Institute of Himalayan Environment and Development	Tadong	1
2330	G.G.M. Science College	Jammu	1
2331	G.N. Khalsa College	Bombay	1
2332	G.P. Women's College	Imphal	1
2333	Gandhi Hospital	Hyderabad	1
2334	Gandhian Institute of Studies	Varanasi	1
2335	Gandhigram Rural Institute	Gandhigram	1
2336	Ganga Kisan Sahkari Chini Mills Ltd.	Muzaffarnagar	1
2337	Ganga Project (Central Sheep and Wool Research Station)	Rishikesh	1
2338	Gauhati Medical College	Gauhati	1
2339	Gazipur Dairy Farm Veterinary Hospital	New Delhi	1
2340	GB Pant Institute of Himalayan Environment and Development	Gangtok	1
2341	GB Pant University	Nainital	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2342	Gene Campaign	New Delhi	1
2343	Genetic Engineering Unit	Jammu	1
2344	Geological Survey of India	Calcutta	1
2345	Geological Survey of India	Shillong	1
2346	Glendale Estate	Coonoor	1
2347	Godrej Soaps Ltd	Madras	1
2348	Government College	Gurgoan	1
2349	Government Agriculture Research Station	Ajmer	1
2350	Government Arts College	Karaikudi	1
2351	Government Arts college	Nandanam	1
2352	Government Arts College (Men)	Madras	1
2353	Government Ayurvedic College	Gauhati	1
2354	Government Beekeeping Station	Jeolikote	1
2355	Government City College	Hyderabad	1
2356	Government College	Banswara	1
2357	Government College	Chandigarh	1
2358	Government College	Jhalawar	1
2359	Government College	Parka	1
2360	Government College	Patiala	1
2361	Government College	Rourkela	1
2362	Government College	Sardar Shahar	1
2363	Government College	Sawai Madhopur	1
2364	Government College for Women	Patiala	1
2365	Government College of Pharmacy	Bangalore	1
2366	Government College of Science Education and Research	Jagraon	1
2367	Government Degree College	Bareli	1
2368	Government Degree College	Garhwal	1
2369	Government Degree College	Punganoor	1
2370	Government Dental College and Hospitals	Ahmedabad	1
2371	Government Department of Horticulture and Farm Forestry	Indore	1
2372	Government Fruit Research Station	Basti	1
2373	Government Fruit Research Station	Ganganagar	1
2374	Government General Hospital	Kakinada	1
2375	Government Girls College	Rewa	1
2376	Government Home Science College	Chandigarh	1
2377	Government HS School	Bhadra	1
2378	Government Jr. College	Nagari	1
2379	Government Junior College for Boys	Nalgonda	1
2380	Government Lahiri College	Chirimiri	1
2381	Government M.A.M. College	Jammu	1
2382	Government M.J.S. College	Bhind	1
2383	Government Medical College	Chandigarh	1
2384	Government Medical College	Nagpur	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2385	Government Medical College	Patiala	1
2386	Government Model Science College	Rewa	1
2387	Government Museum	Erode	1
2388	Government of Andhra Pradesh	Hyderabad	1
2389	Government of India	Hissar	1
2390	Government of India	Hyderabad	1
2391	Government of India, Regional Office for Health and Family Welfare	Chandigarh	1
2392	Government of Karnataka	Bangalore	1
2393	Government of Orissa	Bhubaneswar	1
2394	Government of Pondicherry	Pondicherry	1
2395	Government of Tamil Nadu	Madras	1
2396	Government Polytechnic	Anantapur	1
2397	Government Polytechnic	Sundemagar	1
2398	Government Post Graduate College	Almora	1
2399	Government Post Graduate College	Balaghat	1
2400	Government Post Graduate College	Jind	1
2401	Government Post Graduate College	Mhow	1
2402	Government Post Graduate College	Tikamgarh	1
2403	Government Poultry Farm	Ambala	1
2404	Government Research Farm	Joara	1
2405	Government Sanjay Nikunja	Chhindwara	1
2406	Government Science College	Raipur	1
2407	Government Science College	Rewa	1
2408	Government Valley Fruit Research Station	Chamoli	1
2409	Government Vidarbha Mahavidyalaya	Amravati	1
2410	Govind Ballabh Pant Hospital	New Delhi	1
2411	Govind Ballabh Pant University of Agriculture and Technology	Garhwal	1
2412	Gram Sewak Training Centre	Sindewahi	1
2413	Gramsevak Training Centre	Manjari	1
2414	Grapes adviser	Hyderabad	1
2415	GSVM Medical College	Kanpur	1
2416	Gujarat Agricultural College	Sardar Krushinagar	1
2417	Gujarat Agricultural University	Vadodara	1
2418	Gujarat Agricultural University	Vallabh Vidyanagar	1
2419	Gujarat Agricultural University	Valsad	1
2420	Gujarat Cancer and Research Institute	Ahmedabad	1
2421	Gujarat Cancer Society, Cell Biology Division	Ahmedabad	1
2422	Gujarat Cooperative Milk Marketing Federation Ltd.	Ahmedabad	1
2423	Gujarat Forest Department Community Forestry Project	Baroda	1
2424	Gujarat Forest Rangers College	Rajpipla	1
2425	Gujarat State Fertilizers Company Limited	Fertilizernagar	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2426	Gujarat Water Resources Development Corp.	Gandhinagar	1
2427	Gunti Wildlife Sanctuary	Jatanbar	1
2428	H.F.R.C.	Jabalpur	1
2429	Hamdard College of Pharmacy	New Delhi	1
2430	Hamdard Research and Educational Institutions	New Delhi	1
2431	Harishchandra Post Graduate College	Varanasi	1
2432	Haryana Agricultural University	Ambala	1
2433	Haryana Agricultural University	Gurgaon	1
2434	Haryana State Cooperative Bank	Chandigarh	1
2435	Hattialli Tea Estate	Dibrugarh	1
2436	Havukal Estate	Kotagiri	1
2437	Health and Family Welfare Training Centre	Nagpur	1
2438	Heavy Water Plant	Thana	1
2439	High Altitude Plant Physiology Research Centre	Garhwal	1
2440	High Altitude Plant Physiology Research Centre	Srinagar	1
2441	High Altitude Research Station	Koraput	1
2442	Hill Cattle Development Centre	Kandaghat	1
2443	Himachal Pradesh Krishi Vishra Vidyalaya, Bee Research Station	Bagwan	1
2444	Himachal Pradesh Krishi Vishvavidyalaya	Kangra	1
2445	Himachal Pradesh Krishi Vishvavidyalaya	Sangla	1
2446	Hindu College of Pharmacy	Sonepat	1
2447	Hindu Rao Hospital	New Delhi	1
2448	Hindustan Fertiliser Corp. Ltd.	New Delhi	1
2449	Hindustan Fertilizer Corp. Ltd.	Haldia	1
2450	Hindustan Fertilizer Corp. Ltd.	Namrup	1
2451	Hindustan Lever Ltd.	Haldia	1
2452	Hindustan Newsprint Ltd.	Kottayam	1
2453	Hindustan Petro-Chemicals Ltd.	Anand	1
2454	Hirakud College	Hirakud	1
2455	Hoechst India Ltd.	Madras	1
2456	Holy Cross College	Nagercoil	1
2457	Holy Cross Krishi Vigyan Kendra	Hazaribagh	1
2458	Home Science College	Dharwad	1
2459	Homoeopathic Pharmacopoeia Laboratory	Ghaziabad	1
2460	Hooghly Mohsin College	Chinsurah	1
2461	Horticultural Research Complex	Nagicherra	1
2462	Horticultural Research Station	Dhaulakuan	1
2463	Horticultural Research Station	Gauhati	1
2464	Horticultural Research Station	Kanyakumari	1
2465	Horticultural Research Station (U.H.F.)	Jachh	1
2466	Horticulture Experiments and Training Centre	Almora	1
2467	Hospital for Genetic Diseases	Hyderabad	1
2468	HPT Arts and RYK Science College	Nashik	1

SI No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2469	Hydel Designs Organisation	Chandigarh	1
2470	I. G. Medical College	Shimla	1
2471	IBFEP, HFC	Bhopal	1
2472	IBFEP, HFC	Bhubaneswar	1
2473	IBFEP, HFC	Gauhati	1
2474	IBFEP, HFC	Lucknow	1
2475	IBFEP, HFC	Patna	1
2476	IBPGR Office for South and Southeast Asia	New Delhi	1
2477	ICAR	Kalyanpur	1
2478	ICAR Co-ordinated Research Project on Management of Salt Affected Soils and Use of Saline Water in Agr	Agra	1
2479	ICAR Research Complex for NEH Region, Soil Science Division	Shillong	1
2480	ICI(India) Ltd.	Kanpur	1
2481	ICRISAT Cooperative Research Station	Hissar	1
2482	IDL-NitroNobel Basic Research Institute	Bangalore	1
2483	IEL Limited	Madras	1
2484	IGNP	Bikaner	1
2485	India Meteorological Department	New Delhi	1
2486	India Meteorological Department Observatory	Jodhpur	1
2487	Indian Agricultural Research Institute	Dharwad	1
2488	Indian Agricultural Research Institute	Sirsa	1
2489	Indian Bee Research Institute	Ranchi	1
2490	Indian Bureau of Mines	Dhanbad	1
2491	Indian Council for Agricultural Research	Bangalore	1
2492	Indian Council of Medical Research	Madurai	1
2493	Indian Forestry Service	Bhubaneswar	1
2494	Indian Grassland and Fodder Research Insitute	Jhour	1
2495	Indian Grassland and Fodder Research Institute	Srinagar	1
2496	Indian Institute of Agricultural Research	Bangalore	1
2497	Indian Institute of Health Management Research	Jaipur	1
2498	Indian Institute of Management	Calcutta	1
2499	Indian Institute of Pulses Research	Kanpur	1
2500	Indian Journal of Applied Economics	Bangalore	1
2501	Indian Medical Association	New Delhi	1
2502	Indian Meteorological Department	New Delhi	1
2503	Indian National Scientific Documentation Centre	New Delhi	1
2504	Indian Oil and Produce Exporters Assn.	Bombay	1
2505	Indian Overseas Bank	Madras	1
2506	Indian Potash Ltd.	New Delhi	1
2507	Indian Poultry Science Association	Bhubaneswar	1
2508	Indian Resources Information and Management Technology Ltd	Nagpur	1
2509	Indian Rural Reconstruction Movement	Bangalore	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2510	Indian Turpentine and Rosin Co. Ltd.	Bareilly	1
2511	Indian Vaccine Corporation Ltd.	New Delhi	1
2512	Indira Gandhi Centre for Atomic Research	Kalpakkam	1
2513	Indira Gandhi Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya	Durg	1
2514	Indira Gandhi National Open University	New Delhi	1
2515	Indo-American Hybrid Seeds, Biotechnology Division	Bangalore	1
2516	Indo-Danish Project on Seed Procurement and Tree Improvement	Coimbatore	1
2517	Indo-Danish Project on Seed Procurement and Tree Improvement	Hyderabad	1
2518	Indo-Gulf Fertilisers and Chemicals Corporation Ltd.	Lucknow	1
2519	Insecticide Control Lab.	Midnapore	1
2520	Inst. Hydro., Jal Vigyan Bhawan	Roorkee	1
2521	Institute for Research in Medical Statistics	Madras	1
2522	Institute for Study of Society and Culture	Sambalpur	1
2523	<i>Institute of Water and Land Management</i>	Aurangabad	1
2524	Institute of Agriculture	Anand	1
2525	Institute of Animal Health and Biological Products	Srinagar	1
2526	Institute of Child Health	Calcutta	1
2527	Institute of Engineering and Technology, Applied Chemistry Section	Lucknow	1
2528	Institute of Himalayan Studies	Srinagar	1
2529	Institute of Home Science	Srinagar	1
2530	Institute of Horticultural Research, Division of Entomology and Nematology	Bangalore	1
2531	<i>Institute of Hotel Management</i>	New Delhi	1
2532	Institute of Hydraulics and Hydrology	Poondi	1
2533	Institute of Jute Technology	Calcutta	1
2534	Institute of Management in Government	Thiruvananthapuram	1
2535	Institute of Management Studies	Ghaziabad	1
2536	Institute of Peace Research and Action	New Delhi	1
2537	Institute of Social Sciences	New Delhi	1
2538	Institute of Veterinary Compounder's and Dresser's Course	Calcutta	1
2539	Institute of Water and Land Management	Cuttack	1
2540	Institute of Wetland Management and Ecological Design	Calcutta	1
2541	Intensive Cattle Development Project	Gauhati	1
2542	Interdisciplinary Centre for Women and Children	Pune	1
2543	Intermediate College	Nowshera	1
2544	International Development Research Centre	New Delhi	1
2545	International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Society	New Delhi	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2546	International Institute of Biological Control	Bangalore	1
2547	International Management Institute	New Delhi	1
2548	Ion Exchange (India) Limited	Thane	1
2549	IPTRID, Rajad Project	Kota	1
2550	Irrigation and Power Research Institute	Amritsar	1
2551	Irrigation Circle	Udaipur	1
2552	Irrigation Research Institute	Roorkee	1
2553	Irrigation Research Station	Araria	1
2554	J. N. Hospital and Research Centre	Bhilai	1
2555	J. P. Mukherji and Associates Pvt. Ltd.	Pune	1
2556	J.C.B.M. College	Sringeri	1
2557	J.D.B. Commerce and N.S.C. Science College	Nashik	1
2558	J.J. Hospital	Bombay	1
2559	J.K. Synthetics Ltd., Sir Padampat Research Centre	Kota	1
2560	J.K. University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology	Srinagar	1
2561	J.L.N. College	Etawah	1
2562	J.N. Mahavidyalaya	Wadi	1
2563	J.S.S. College of Pharmacy, Rocklands	Ootacamund	1
2564	Jagjeevan College	Gaya	1
2565	Jammu Cooperative Milk Federation Ltd.	Jammu	1
2566	Janta College	Meerut	1
2567	Janta College of Pharmacy	Sonepat	1
2568	Jawaharlal Nehru Agricultural University	Raipur	1
2569	Jawaharlal Nehru Agricultural University	Bilaspur	1
2570	Jawaharlal Nehru Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya	Sagar	1
2571	Jawaharlal Nehru Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya	Tikamgarh	1
2572	Jhargram Raj College	Midnapore	1
2573	Jivrajbhai Patel Agroforestry Centre	Surendrabag Kardej	1
2574	Joint Women's Programme	New Delhi	1
2575	K.A. Post Graduate College	Kasgan	1
2576	K.C. College	Hetampur	1
2577	K.G. Arts and Science College	Raigad	1
2578	K.K. Das College of Commerce	Calcutta	1
2579	K.K. Post Graduate College	Etawah	1
2580	K.R. College	Mathura	1
2581	Kakdwip Research Centre of CIBA	Kakdwip	1
2582	Kalyanakere-Mavathurkere Watershed Development Programme	Nelamangala	1
2583	Kanara Circle	Dharwad	1
2584	Kanchenzonga National Park, Wild Life Circle	Gangtok	1
2585	Kandi Research Station	Ballawal Saunkhri	1
2586	Kanger Valley National Park	Jagdajpur	1
2587	Kangsabati Soil Conservation Division-I	Puruli	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2588	Kanha National Park	Mandla	1
2589	Kanpur Sugar Works	Kanpur	1
2590	Kanpur University	Allahabad	1
2591	Kanpur University	Rae Bareli	1
2592	Kamal Co-operative Sugar Mills Ltd.	Karnal	1
2593	Karnataka Engineering Research Station	Krishnarajasagara	1
2594	Karnataka Forest Department	Mysore	1
2595	Karnataka Institute of Applied Agricultural Research	Sameerwadi	1
2596	Karnataka Regional Engineering College	Srinivasanagar	1
2597	Karnataka Silk Industries Corporation	Bangalore	1
2598	Karnataka University	Belgaum	1
2599	Kasturba College for Women	Hyderabad	1
2600	Kasturba Medical College	Mangalore	1
2601	Katwa College	Katwa	1
2602	Kelappaji College of Agricultural Engineering and Technology	Tavanur	1
2603	Kendrapara College	Kendrapara	1
2604	Kerala Agricultural University	Kasaragod	1
2605	Kerala Forest Research Institute	Trichur	1
2606	Kerala Livestock Development and Milk Marketing Board Ltd.	Thiruvananthapuram	1
2607	Khadir Mohideen College	Adirampattina	1
2608	Khallikote College	Berhampur	1
2609	Khalsa Post Graduate College	Sriganganagar	1
2610	Khariar College	Kharia	1
2611	Kidwai Memorial Institute of Oncology	Bangalore	1
2612	Kinetics Technology India Ltd.	New Delhi	1
2613	Kirti College	Bombay	1
2614	Kisan Sahakari Chini Mills Ltd.	Budaun	1
2615	Kitply Industries Limited	Calcutta	1
2616	Kittel Science College	Dharwad	1
2617	Kothari Centre of Gastroenterology	Calcutta	1
2618	Kothari Medical Centre	Calcutta	1
2619	Krishi Gyan Kondra	Gurgaon	1
2620	Krishi Vigyan Kendra	Bhanjanagar	1
2621	Krishi Vigyan Kendra	Kakdwip	1
2622	Krishi Vigyan Kendra	Shirgaon	1
2623	Krishi Vigyan Kendra/Trainer's Training Centre of CIFA	Bhubaneswar	1
2624	Krishna District Milk Producers' Cooperative Union Ltd.	Vijayawada	1
2625	Krishna Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana Ltd	Shivnagar	1
2626	KSSPG College	Faizabad	1
2627	Kunigal Stud Farm	Karnataka	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2628	Kunneth Hospital and Medical Research Centre	Madichal	1
2629	Kurseong Forest Division	Dowhill	1
2630	Kusum Products Limited	Calcutta	1
2631	Kutir Degree College	Jaunpur	1
2632	L.N. Government College	Ponneri	1
2633	L.N. Mishra Institute of Economic Development and Social Change	Patna	1
2634	L.S.U. Sujathanagar	Khammam	1
2635	Laboratory for Electro-Optics Systems	Bangalore	1
2636	Laboratory of Fruit Pathology	Mashobra	1
2637	Lady Amrutabai Daga College for Women	Nagpur	1
2638	Lady Doak College	Madurai	1
2639	Lady Sri Ram College for Women	New Delhi	1
2640	Lakshmbai National College of Physical Education	Thiruvananthapuram	1
2641	Lalbagh	Bangalore	1
2642	Leprosy Training Centre	Hyderabad	1
2643	Lipton India Limited	Chandigarh	1
2644	Litchi and Mango Research Station	Kangra	1
2645	Litchi and Mango Research Station	Nagrota-bagwan	1
2646	Literature Museum	Raipur	1
2647	Livestock Development Office	Pune	1
2648	Livestock Production and Management, Sonia Enterprises	Indore	1
2649	Livestock Research and Development Centre	Nagercoil	1
2650	Livestock Research Station	Guntur	1
2651	Livestock Research Station	Hyderabad	1
2652	Livestock Research Station	Junagadh	1
2653	Livestock Research Station	Mondira	1
2654	Livestock Research Station	Tiruvazhamkunru	1
2655	Livestock Supervisory Unit	Nizamabad	1
2656	Lokayan Centre	New Delhi	1
2657	LSS Pediatric Hospital and Research Centre	Kota	1
2658	LV Prasad Eye Institute	Hyderabad	1
2659	Lyallpur Khalsa College	Jalandhar	1
2660	M.A. Medical College and Associated LNJP Hospital	New Delhi	1
2661	M.D College	Bombay	1
2662	M.J.S. College, Shrigonda	Ahmednagar	1
2663	M.L.B. College	Bhopal	1
2664	M.M.D. College	Gondia	1
2665	M.P. College for Women	Mandi	1
2666	M.P. Pollution Control Board	Bhopal	1
2667	M.P. State Forest Development Corporation	Bhopal	1
2668	M.P. State Industries Corporation Ltd.	Ujjain	1

SI No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2669	M.P.C. College	Baripada	1
2670	M.S. Ramaiah Medical College	Bangalore	1
2671	M/S Balaji Hatcheries	Nellore	1
2672	M/s. Poshak Feeds Pvt. Ltd.	Hyderabad	1
2673	Madanmohan Malviya Post Graduate College	Kalakankar	1
2674	Madhya Pradesh Council of Science and Technology	Bhopal	1
2675	Madhya Pradesh Pradushan Niwaran Mandal	Bhopal	1
2676	Madras Crocodile Bank Trust	Mamallapuram	1
2677	Madurai Kamaraj University	Palayankottai	1
2678	Madurai Medical College	Madurai	1
2679	Mahanand Dairy	Bombay	1
2680	Maharashtra Engineering Res. Inst.	Nashik	1
2681	Maharashtra State Electricity Board	Bombay	1
2682	Maharashtra State Seeds Corporation Ltd.	Akola	1
2683	Mahatma Phule Agriculture University	Ahmednagar	1
2684	Mahendra Agricultural Farm	Sadabad	1
2685	Mahindra Days Hotels and Resorts	Bangalore	1
2686	Main Crops Research Station	Surat	1
2687	Main Research Station	Dharwad	1
2688	Maize Products	Ahmedabad	1
2689	Malaria Investigation Centre	Mandya	1
2690	Malaria Research Centre	Shankargarth	1
2691	Malaria Research Centre (Field Station)	Haldwani	1
2692	Malaria Research Field Station	Nayapara	1
2693	Malnad College of Engineering	Hassan	1
2694	Mangalore Chem. and Fert. Ltd.	Bangalore	1
2695	Mangesh International Services	Bombay	1
2696	Mango Research Station	Malda	1
2697	Manihari College	Manihari	1
2698	Manonmaniam Sundaranar University	Palayankottai	1
2699	Mar Ivanios College	Thiruvananthapuram	1
2700	Mar Thoma College	Tiruvalla	1
2701	Marari College	Darbhanga	1
2702	Margol College	Gulbarga	1
2703	Marine Products Export Development Authority	Cochin	1
2704	Masfed Poultry Consultancy and Disease Diagnostic Lab.	Hyderabad	1
2705	Mastitis Control Unit. I.A.H. and V.B.	Calcutta	1
2706	Mathura Veterinary College	Mathura	1
2707	McDA Agro Pvt. Ltd. 9	Bombay	1
2708	MDDM College	Muzaffarpur	1
2709	Medical and Cancer Research and Treatment Centre	Nagercoil	1
2710	Medical College	Calcutta	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2711	Medical College	Kottayam	1
2712	Medical College	Patna	1
2713	Medical College and Hospital	Darbhanga	1
2714	Medical College Hospital	Calicut	1
2715	Medical College Hospital	Jodhpur	1
2716	Mehsana District Co-operative Milk Producers Union Limited	Mehsana	1
2717	Meteorological Department	Mysore	1
2718	Meteorological Office	Bangalore	1
2719	Micronutrient Laboratory, IBFEP, HFC	Siliguri	1
2720	Midnapur College	Midnapore	1
2721	Military Hospital	Agra	1
2722	Military Veterinary Hospital	Karakwasia	1
2723	Milk Food Ltd.	Guragon	1
2724	Milk Plant	Paonta Sahib	1
2725	Milk Product Dairy	Dharwad	1
2726	Milk Union Ropar Milk Plant Mohali	Ropar	1
2727	Millet Research Station	Jamnagar	1
2728	Ministry of Defence	New Delhi	1
2729	Ministry of Finance, Government of India	New Delhi	1
2730	Ministry of Health and Family Welfare	New Delhi	1
2731	Ministry of Home Affairs	Shillong	1
2732	Ministry of Human Resource Development	New Delhi	1
2733	Ministry of Industry	New Delhi	1
2734	Ministry of Science and Technology	Calcutta	1
2735	Minor Irrigation Department	Lucknow	1
2736	Minuthong Hafiz Hatta	Imphal	1
2737	MKCG Medical College	Berhampur	1
2738	MLV Shranjeevi College	Udaipur	1
2739	Model Holker Science College	Indore	1
2740	Monitoring and Evaluation, Forest Department	Gangtok	1
2741	Montari Agaricultural Research Station	Zirakpur	1
2742	Moolchand Kharaiti Ram Hospital	New Delhi	1
2743	Mother Terasa Women's University	Kodaikanal	1
2744	Motilal Pesticides (I) Pvt Ltd.	New Delhi	1
2745	MRS	Hebbal	1
2746	MS University of Baroda	Vadodara	1
2747	Mukand Lal National College	Yamuna Nagar	1
2748	Multimetals Ltd.	Kota	1
2749	Multiple Action Research Group (MARG)	New Delhi	1
2750	Mushroom Research Laboratory	Solan	1
2751	Mycotoxin Research Laboratory	Lucknow	1
2752	N.J.S.A. Government College	Kapurthala	1
2753	N.R.C. Seminary Hill	Nagpur	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2754	N.R.S. Medical College	Calcutta	1
2755	N.V. Arts and Science and Dr. Patki Commercial College	Gulbarga	1
2756	Nagaraj Pet	Cuddapah	1
2757	Nagarjuna Co-op. Sugars Ltd.	Guntur	1
2758	Nagarjuna University	Guntur	1
2759	Nalanda College	Biharsharif	1
2760	Nalanda Medical College	Patna	1
2761	Nalanda Research Institute and College	Biharshari	1
2762	Naoradehi Wildlife Division	Sagar	1
2763	Narendra Deva University of Agriculture and Technology	Kumarganj	1
2764	NARP	Paiyur	1
2765	NARP Substation	Anand	1
2766	National Agricultural Research Project	Arnej	1
2767	National Agricultural Research Project	Aurangabad	1
2768	National Agricultural Research Project	Balassore	1
2769	National Agricultural Research Project	Chandrapur	1
2770	National Agricultural Research Project	Kolhapur	1
2771	National Aluminium Can Co. Ltd.	Damanjodi	1
2772	National Bank	Madras	1
2773	National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development	Dehra Dun	1
2774	National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development	New Delhi	1
2775	National Biotechnology Research Institute, Plant Virus Laboratory	Lucknow	1
2776	National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources	Barapani	1
2777	National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources	Cuttack	1
2778	National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources, Regional Station	Akola	1
2779	National Bureau of Soil Survey and Land Use Planning	Amravati	1
2780	National Bureau of Soil Survey and Land Use Planning (ICAR), Regional Centre	Hebbal	1
2781	National Bureau Soil Survey and Land Use Planning	Vadodara	1
2782	National Camel Research Centre	Bikaner	1
2783	National Centre for Management of Agricultural Extension	Hyderabad	1
2784	National Co-op. Sugar Mills	Madurai	1
2785	National College	Bangalore	1
2786	National College	Tiruchirapalli	1
2787	National Committee on the use of Plastics in Agriculture	New Delhi	1
2788	National Cooperative Development Corporation	New Delhi	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2789	National Cooperative Training College	Madras	1
2790	National Council of Medical Research	Hyderabad	1
2791	National Demonstration Scheme	Ballia	1
2792	National Drinking Water Mission	New Delhi	1
2793	National Environmental Engineering Research Institute	Hyderabad	1
2794	National Environmental Research Institute	Ahmedabad	1
2795	National Fertilizers Ltd.	Nangal	1
2796	National Herbarium and Plant Laboratories	Godavari	1
2797	National Institute of Miners' Health	Kolar	1
2798	National Institute for Training in Industrial Engg.	Bombay	1
2799	National Institute of Communicable Diseases	Shertallai	1
2800	National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration	New Delhi	1
2801	National Institute of Oceanography	Cochin	1
2802	National Insurance Academy	Pune	1
2803	National Labour Institute	New Delhi	1
2804	National Malaria Eradication Programme	Chandigarh	1
2805	National Malaria Eradication Programme	Jagdalpur	1
2806	National Metallurgical Lab.	Jamshedpur	1
2807	National Museum of Man	Bhopal	1
2808	National Plant Protection Training Institute	Hyderabad	1
2809	National Plant Resource Centre	Nayapalli	1
2810	National Research Centre for Spices	Calcutta	1
2811	National Seed Corporation Ltd.	New Delhi	1
2812	National Seeds Corporation Ltd.	Guntur	1
2813	National Sericultural Project	Udaipur	1
2814	National Sericulture Project	Kishanganj	1
2815	National Silkworm Seed Project	Madivala	1
2816	National Textile Corporation (MP) Ltd.	Indore	1
2817	National Turicum Leaf Blight Disease Resistance Breeding Centre	Mysore	1
2818	Nawapara	Kalahandi	1
2819	Naya Sarkanda	Bilaspur	1
2820	Nehru college	Hubli	1
2821	Nehru Zoological Park	Hyderabad	1
2822	Netaji Subhas National Institute of Sports	Patiala	1
2823	Neuen Zurcher Zeitung	New Delhi	1
2824	New College	Madras	1
2825	NICD/ICMR Scheme for Malaria	Jagdalpur	1
2826	Nilgiris District Co-operative Milk Producers' Union	Udhagamandalam	1
2827	Niloufer Hospital	Hyderabad	1
2828	Nirmal Niwas	Shimla	1
2829	Nirula Comer House Ltd.	New Delhi	1

SI No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2830	Nizam Sugar Factory Limited	Hyderabad	1
2831	North Balaghat Forest Division	Balaghat	1
2832	North Bengal Medical College	Darjeeling	1
2833	North Eastern Hill University	Aizawl	1
2834	Northern Book Centre	New Delhi	1
2835	Northern Region Farm Machinery Training and Testing Institute	Hissar	1
2836	NPC	Bangalore	1
2837	Office of the Commissioner Archaeology and Museums	Bhopal	1
2838	Office of the Joint Director of Agriculture	Erode	1
2839	Offshore Platform and Marine Electrochemistry Centre, CECRI Unit	Tuticorin	1
2840	Oil of India Limited	Jodhpur	1
2841	Oilseeds Research Unit	Akola	1
2842	Om Sai Ram Centre for Financial Management Research and Training	Bombay	1
2843	On-Farm Research Unit	Mannuthy	1
2844	Operational Research Project	Raigad	1
2845	Operational Research Project	Sidhi	1
2846	Operational Research Project of Directorate of Rice Research	Khammam	1
2847	Oragon Research Centre	Calcutta	1
2848	Orchid Research and Development Centre	Bhalukpong	1
2849	Oriental Carbon and Chemicals Company	New Delhi	1
2850	Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology	Berhampur	1
2851	Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology	Chiplima	1
2852	Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology	Koraput	1
2853	Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology	Phulbani	1
2854	P.C. Jabin Science College	Vidyanagar	1
2855	P.E.S. College of Engineering	Mandya	1
2856	P.G. Science College, Department of Biosciences	Gardol	1
2857	P.J.N. College of Agriculture	Karaikal	1
2858	P.N.R. Rao and Associates	Pune	1
2859	P.P.N. Post Graduate College	Kanpur	1
2860	P.V.P. College of Arts Science and Commerce	Pravaranagar	1
2861	Paddy Research Station	Sindewahi	1
2862	Padmashree Dr. Vithalrao Vikhe Patil SSK Ltd.	Ahmednagar	1
2863	Palli Sisksha Bhavana (Institute of Agricultural) Visva-Bharati	Sriniketan	1
2864	Panchayat College	Bargar	1
2865	Panchayat College	Sambalpur	1
2866	Pandharpur College	Pandharpur	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2867	Paradeep Phosphates Ltd.	Bhubaneswar	1
2868	Paramount Imaging Centre	Bombay	1
2869	Pepsi Agro Food Processing Research Institute	Ludhiana	1
2870	Pest and Parasite Research Laboratory	Bareilly	1
2871	Pest Control Consultant	Reshimbag	1
2872	Pesticide and Industrial Toxicology Centre	Tirupati	1
2873	PHD Chamber of Commerce and Industry	New Delhi	1
2874	Phulsing Naik Mahavidyalaya Pusad	Yavatmal	1
2875	Pineapple Research Centre	Vellanikkara	1
2876	Plan Monitoring Cell	Bangalore	1
2877	Planar Chromatography Research and Applications Center (Camag Extended Application Laboratory)	Bombay	1
2878	Planning and Development Department	Guwahati	1
2879	Planning Commission	Bhopal	1
2880	Plant Breeding and Genetics Regional Agricultural Research Station	R. S. Pura	1
2881	Plant Improvement Division, IGFR	Jhansi	1
2882	Plant Quarantine and Fumigation Station	Cochin	1
2883	Plant Quarantine Research and Fumigation Station	Bongaon	1
2884	Plant Virus Research Centre	Kalyani	1
2885	Plantation Crops Research Station	Mahuva	1
2886	Pollution Monitoring Laboratory	Gopeshwar	1
2887	Polyolefins Industries Ltd.	Bombay	1
2888	Pondicherry Central University	Pondicherry	1
2889	Ponni Sugars and Chemicals	Cauvery	1
2890	Post Graduate College of Veterinary Sciences	Akola	1
2891	Post Graduate Department of Microbiology	Nagpur	1
2892	Post Graduate Science College	Bardoli	1
2893	Post-Harvest Technology Scheme	Bhopal	1
2894	Poultry Research and Development Centre	Tirupur	1
2895	Poultry Research and Development Centre	Vellore	1
2896	Pradeshik Co-operative Dairy Fed. Ltd.	Lucknow	1
2897	Pragjyotish College	Gauhati	1
2898	Proctor and Gamble India Ltd	New Delhi	1
2899	Progeny Testing Programme	Chittoor	1
2900	Projects and Development India Limited	Baroda	1
2901	Pt. L.M.S. Government Post Graduate College	Dehra Dun	1
2902	Public Health Laboratory	Pondicherry	1
2903	Pulse and Oilseeds Research Centre	Pandharpur	1
2904	Pulses Res. Sta H.Q.	Bari Brahamana (Samba)	1
2905	Punjab Agricultural University	Kheri	1
2906	Punjab Housing Development Board	Chandigarh	1

SI No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2907	Punjab State Federation of Coop. Sugar Mills Ltd.	Chandigarh	1
2908	Punjab State Planning Board	Chandigarh	1
2909	Punjabrao Krishi Vidyapeeth	Nagpur	1
2910	Pyrites Phosphates and Chemicals Ltd.	Patna	1
2911	QE Unit of Circot Agricultural Farm	Athwa	1
2912	Quality Control Department	Sagar	1
2913	Quality Control Laboratory	Mohanpur	1
2914	Quality Evaluation Unit	Surat	1
2915	Queen Mary's College	Madras	1
2916	R & D Cadila Laboratories Pvt. Ltd.	Ahmedabad	1
2917	R. Khullar, Medical College Campus	Jodhpur	1
2918	R. P. Chemicals Ltd.	Bombay	1
2919	R.G. Kar Medical College	Calcutta	1
2920	R.K. Ashram Krishi Vigyan Kendra	Parganas	1
2921	R.L. College	Alinagar	1
2922	R.M.L. Hospital	New Delhi	1
2923	Rabbit Breeding Station	Tirchur	1
2924	Rabindra Bharati University	Calcutta	1
2925	Rabindra Mahavidyalaya	Champadanga	1
2926	Race Course	Vadodara	1
2927	Radeus Advertising Pvt. Ltd.	Bombay	1
2928	Rahem Mansion Building	Bombay	1
2929	Rail Board	New Delhi	1
2930	Raja Pearymohan College	Hooghly	1
2931	Rajaji International Institute of Public Affairs and Administration	Hyderabad	1
2932	Rajasthan Agricultural University	Banswara	1
2933	Rajasthan Agricultural University	Jaisalmer	1
2934	Rajendra Agricultural University	Sabour	1
2935	Rajgarh Working Plan Forest Division	Solan	1
2936	Rajshree Sugars and Chemicals Ltd.	Madurai	1
2937	Ramakrishna Mission	Narendrapur	1
2938	Ramanada College	Bishnupur	1
2939	Rampur Distillery and Chemical Ltd.	Rampura	1
2940	Ranbaxy Laboratories Limited	New Delhi	1
2941	Rangaraya Medical College	Kakinada	1
2942	Rashtra Chemical and Fertilizers (RCF)	Thal	1
2943	Rathnavel Subramaniam Institutes of Science, Agriculture and Technology	Coimbatore	1
2944	RD and DJ College	Munger	1
2945	Regional A. I. Centre, Animal Husbandry Department	Payyannur	1
2946	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Balaghat	1
2947	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Karjat	1

SI No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2948	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Karnal	1
2949	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Khandwa	1
2950	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Pusa	1
2951	Regional Agricultural Research Station	R.S. Pura	1
2952	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Tikamgarh	1
2953	Regional Agricultural Research Station	Wayanad	1
2954	Regional Coffee Research Station	Diphu	1
2955	Regional College of Education	Ajmer	1
2956	Regional Conservation Laboratory	Mysore	1
2957	Regional Cotton Research Station	Bharuch	1
2958	Regional Disease Investigation Laboratory	Bethuadahari	1
2959	Regional Engineering College	Calicut	1
2960	Regional Engineering College	Durgapura	1
2961	Regional Farm	Jagtial	1
2962	Regional Filaria Training Research Centre	Varanasi	1
2963	Regional Fruit Research Station	Abohar	1
2964	Regional Fruit Research Station	Anantharajupeta	1
2965	Regional Horticultural Research Station	Solan	1
2966	Regional Horticulture Research Station	Srinagar	1
2967	Regional Horticulture Research Station (Skuast)	Jammu	1
2968	Regional Laboratory	Tiruchirapalli	1
2969	Regional Medical Centre	Port Blair	1
2970	Regional Medical Research Centre	Jabalpur	1
2971	Regional Office for Health and Family Welfare	Ahmedabad	1
2972	Regional Office for Health and Family Welfare	Jaipur	1
2973	Regional Office for Health and Family Welfare	Madras	1
2974	Regional Pesticide Testing Laboratory	Kanpur	1
2975	Regional Quality Education Unit of Cotton Technological Research Laboratory	Guntur	1
2976	Regional Remote Sensing Service Centre	Dehra Dun	1
2977	Regional Remote Sensing Service Centre	Jodhpur	1
2978	Regional Research Centre	Amravati	1
2979	Regional Research Centre	Bangalore	1
2980	Regional Research Institute	Jaipur	1
2981	Regional Research Institute	Lucknow	1
2982	Regional Research Institute of Unani Medicine	Aligarh	1
2983	Regional Research Station	Berhampur	1
2984	Regional Research Station	Bijapur	1
2985	Regional Research Station	Dharwad	1
2986	Regional Research Station	Dhaulakuan	1
2987	Regional Research Station	Gurdaspur	1
2988	Regional Research Station	Khargone	1
2989	Regional Research Station	Kurukshetra	1
2990	Regional Research Station	Madhepur	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
2991	Regional Research Station	Pali-Marwar	1
2992	Regional Research Station	Phulbani	1
2993	Regional Research Station	Uchani	1
2994	Regional Research Station	Wayanad	1
2995	Regional Research Station, Indian Cardamom Research Institute	Gangtok	1
2996	Regional Research Station, Spices Board	Gangtok	1
2997	Regional Research Sub-Station	Sangla	1
2998	Regional Sericultural Research Station	Anantapur	1
2999	Regional Sericultural Research Station	C.r. Nagar	1
3000	Regional Sericultural Research Station	Malda	1
3001	Regional Sericulture Research Station	Kashmir	1
3002	Regional Station of Agricultural Research	Sumerpur	1
3003	Regional Station of Agricultural Research	Udaipur	1
3004	Regional Station of CARI	Minicoy	1
3005	Regional Tasar Research Station	Jagdalpur	1
3006	Remote Sensing Applications Centre	Lucknow	1
3007	Remote Sensing Applications Centre for Resource Evaluation and Geoengineering Muslim University	Aligarh	1
3008	Reproductive Physiology Unit, Department of Physiology	Calcutta	1
3009	Research and Development Cell, P.C.D.F. Ltd.	Lucknow	1
3010	Research and Development Circle	Lucknow	1
3011	Research and Development Department	Balipara Lokr	1
3012	Research and Information System for the Non-Aligned and Other Developing Country	New Delhi	1
3013	Research and Training Division	Haryana	1
3014	Research Extension Centre	Sijapur	1
3015	Research Project on Dryland Agriculture	Rewa	1
3016	Research Project on Oilseeds (Safflower)	Solapur	1
3017	Research Station	Palamaner	1
3018	Rice Research Station	Tirurkuppam	1
3019	Rice Research Station	Vyttila	1
3020	Rice Research Unit	Bapatla	1
3021	Rinderpest Diagnostic Laboratory	Barasat	1
3022	Rinderpest eradication scheme	Palghat	1
3023	RMPPV (Post Graduate) College	Saharanpur	1
3024	RMPPV College	Haridwar	1
3025	Rockefeller Foundation	New Delhi	1
3026	Ross Institute of Parasitology	Hyderabad	1
3027	RS and DJ College	Munger	1
3028	Rubber Research Institute of India	Dapchari	1
3029	Rubber Research Institute of India	Tura	1
3030	Rural Development Agency	Gurdaspur	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
3031	Rural Housing and Low Cost Housing Cell	Bhubaneswar	1
3032	Rural Medical College	Loni	1
3033	S. K. and H. S. K. Sc. Institute	Vidyanagar	1
3034	S.B. College	Hooghly	1
3035	S.B. National Chambal Sanctuary	Etawah	1
3036	S.D.J. Post Graduate College Chandesar	Azamgarh	1
3037	S.F.S. College	Coimbatore	1
3038	S.G. Sastry Research Centre	Bangalore	1
3039	S.K. Basu Institute of Microbial Technology	Chandigarh	1
3040	S.K. University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology	Jammu	1
3041	S.L. Raheja Hospital	Bombay	1
3042	S.M. College	Bhagalpur	1
3043	S.N. Sinha College	Gaya	1
3044	S.P. College	Bijainagar	1
3045	S.P. College	Dumka	1
3046	S.S. College	Jahanabad	1
3047	S.S.K. Ltd.	Akluj	1
3048	S.S.K. Sangh Ltd.	Bombay	1
3049	S.S.P. Pvt. Ltd.	New Delhi	1
3050	S.S.R.J. Arts and Science College	Khammam	1
3051	S.V. Degree College	Hyderabad	1
3052	Sacred Heart College	Thevara	1
3053	Sagayathottam Institute of Agriculture and Rural Development	Takkolam	1
3054	Sahibganj College	Sahibganj	1
3055	Saiva Bhanu Kshatriya College	Aruppukottai	1
3056	Sakhar Karkhana Ltd.	Parite	1
3057	Sakthi Wood Treats	Thiruvananthapuram	1
3058	Sal Research Centre	Bilaspur	1
3059	Salar Jung Museum	Hyderabad	1
3060	Salar Jung Sugar Mills Ltd.	Raichur	1
3061	Saline Water Scheme	Bapatla	1
3062	Sangamner College	Sangamner	1
3063	SANLAAP	Calcutta	1
3064	Saraswathi Narayanan College	Madurai	1
3065	Sardar Sarovar Plantation Project	Vadodara	1
3066	Sarojini Naidu College for Women	Calcutta	1
3067	Satyanagar	Bhubaneswar	1
3068	School of Studies in Chemistry	Raipur	1
3069	Science College	Bhusawal	1
3070	SDM College of Dental Sciences	Dharwad	1
3071	SDNB Vaishnav College for Women	Madras	1
3072	Searle (India) Limited	Hyderabad	1
3073	Seed Farm	Mudigere	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
3074	Seed Testing Laboratory	Coimbatore	1
3075	Seed Testing Laboratory	Dharwad	1
3076	Sericulture Extension Office	Hassan	1
3077	Sericulture Research Substation	Jammu	1
3078	Seva Mandir	Udaipur	1
3079	Shahdol Circle	Shahdol	1
3080	Shahu Agricultural School	Kolhapur	1
3081	Sheep and Wool Department	Rajasthan	1
3082	Sheep Husbandry Department	Nowshera	1
3083	Sheep Husbandry Department	Srinagar	1
3084	Shia Degree College	Lucknow	1
3085	Shibli National Post Graduate Medical College	Azamgarh	1
3086	Shibnath Sastri College	Calcutta	1
3087	Shimoga Circle	Shimoga	1
3088	Shivalik Agro Poly Products Limited	New Delhi	1
3089	Shivalik College	Naya Nangal	1
3090	Shree Jayendrapuri Arts and Science College	Bharuch	1
3091	Shree Mahuva Pradesh Sahakari K.U.M. Ltd.	Surat	1
3092	Shree Warana Mahavidyalaya	Warananagar	1
3093	Shri AMM Murugappa Chettiar Research Centre (MCRC)	Saveriyarpuram	1
3094	Shri Bhogawati Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana Ltd.	Shahunagar	1
3095	Shri Chalthan Vibhag Khand Udyog Mandali Ltd.	Chalthan	1
3096	Shri Datta Shetkari Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana Ltd	Shirol	1
3097	Shri Jain Post Graduate College	Bikaner	1
3098	Shri Shardagram Arts and Commerce College	Mangrol	1
3099	Shri Shivaji College	Akola	1
3100	Shri Shivaji College of Arts and Commerce	Akola	1
3101	Shri Shivaji Science College	Amravati	1
3102	Shri Vighnagar SSK Ltd.	Pune	1
3103	Shriram Fertilisers and Chemicals	Kota	1
3104	Shriram Foods and Fertiliser Industries	New Delhi	1
3105	Shroff Research Institute	Bombay	1
3106	Shukhadia University	Durgapura	1
3107	Silviculture (Hills) Division	Darjeeling	1
3108	Similpal Tiger Reserve	Baripada	1
3109	Simram Group	Indore	1
3110	Sind Sugar Industry Research Institute	Hyderabad	1
3111	Sindh Agricultural University	Tandojam	1
3112	Siva Essential Oils and Chemicals	New Delhi	1
3113	SMSG College	Sherghati	1
3114	Social Forestry Circle	Bharuch	1
3115	Social Forestry Division	Lateha	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
3116	Social Forestry Monitoring	Madras	1
3117	Social Forestry Project Division	Balasure	1
3118	Social Forestry, Kothi Annexe	Vadodara	1
3119	Social Science Institute	Allahabad	1
3120	Society for the Promotion of Wasteland Development	New Delhi	1
3121	Soil Chemistry, Tabela House	Kota	1
3122	Soil Science, c/o the Conservator of Forests (Research)	Coimbatore	1
3123	Soil Survey	Aizawl	1
3124	Soil Survey and Land Use Organization	Dehra Dun	1
3125	Soil Survey and Landuse Organization	Madras	1
3126	SOL Antibiotics Ltd	Hyderabad	1
3127	Solvent Extractors' Association of India	Bombay	1
3128	Somaiya Organics (India) Ltd.	Ahmednagar	1
3129	South Indian Education Society College of Arts Science and Commerce	Bombay	1
3130	Sree Narayana College	Quilon	1
3131	Sreekariyam	Thiruvananthapuram	1
3132	Sri Avinashilingam Water and Energy Training Institute	Coimbatore	1
3133	Sri Jayahamarajendra College of Engineering	Mysore	1
3134	Sri Ramachandra Educational and Health Trust	Madras	1
3135	Sri Ramakrishna Mission Vidyalaya Autonomous Arts College	Coimbatore	1
3136	Sri S.R.N.M. College	Sattur	1
3137	Sri Sharanabasaveshwara College of Arts	Gulbarga	1
3138	Sri Venkateswara Arts College	Tirupati	1
3139	Sri Venkateswara University	Kumool	1
3140	Sri Venkateswara University Post Graduate Centre	Cuddapah	1
3141	SRT College	Tehri Garhwal	1
3142	SSN College	New Delhi	1
3143	SSTL, Central Silk Board	Bangalore	1
3144	SSVP College	Dhule	1
3145	St Antony's College	Shillong	1
3146	St Thomas College	Kozhencherry	1
3147	St. Edmund's College	Shillong	1
3148	St. Francis College	Hyderabad	1
3149	St. Joseph's College	Bangalore	1
3150	St. Joseph's College	Calicut	1
3151	St. Teresa's College	Ernakulam	1
3152	St. Xavier's College	Bombay	1
3153	State Agricultural Research Station	Mokokchung	1
3154	State Bank of India	Palghar	1
3155	State Forest Service College	Dehra Dun	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
3156	State Livestock Breeding Farm	Kalamati	1
3157	State Museum	Lucknow	1
3158	State Remote Sensing Application Centre	Jodhpur	1
3159	State Veterinary Hospital	Bhopal	1
3160	Steel Authority of India Ltd.	Rourkela	1
3161	Sub Research Station	Sakoli	1
3162	Sub-Divisional Headquarter Hospital	Jaipur	1
3163	Sucro Consult International	New Delhi	1
3164	Sugarcane Research Centre	Menonpara	1
3165	Sugarcane Research Institute	Faizalabad	1
3166	Sugarcane Research Institute	Samastipur	1
3167	Sugarcane Research Institute	Shahjahanpur	1
3168	Sugarcane Research Station	Bethuadahari	1
3169	Sugarcane Research Station	Buraliction	1
3170	Sugarcane Research Station	Gudiyatham	1
3171	Sugarcane Research Station	Jorhat	1
3172	Sugarcane Research Station	Thiruvalla	1
3173	Sugarfed Punjab	Chandigarh	1
3174	Sukhadia University	Jhalawar	1
3175	Sulabh International	Patna	1
3176	Surajmal Kanoi College	Dibrugarh	1
3177	Surat District Co-operative Milk Producers' Union Ltd.	Surat	1
3178	Suri Vidyasagar College	Suri	1
3179	Swanand Attikolla	Dharwad	1
3180	Syndicate Bank	Dharwad	1
3181	Syndicate Bank	Manipal	1
3182	Synthite Industrial Chemicals Pvt. Ltd.	Cochin	1
3183	System Analysis and Water Resources Dev.	Baroda	1
3184	T.D. Medical College Hospital	Alleppey	1
3185	T.P. Varna College	Narkatia Ganj	1
3186	Tagore Arts College	Pondicherry	1
3187	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Aliyarnagar	1
3188	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Kovilpatti	1
3189	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Paramakudi	1
3190	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Pudukkottai	1
3191	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Thadiyankudisai	1
3192	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Tirunelveli	1
3193	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Tuticorin	1
3194	Tamil Nadu Arasu Medical Science and Research Institute	Madras	1
3195	Tamil Nadu Co-operative Sugar Federation, Main Bio-Control Research Laboratory	Changalpett	1
3196	Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute	Cauvery	1

SI No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
3197	Tamil Nadu Sugar Corporation Ltd.	Madras	1
3198	Tangra Livestock Yard and Slaughter House, Calcutta Municipal Corporation	Calcutta	1
3199	Tata College	Chaibasa	1
3200	Tata Consulting Engineers	Thiruvananthapuram	1
3201	Tea Experiment Station	Palampur	1
3202	Tea Research Association	Darjeeling	1
3203	Tea Research Association	Jalpaiguri	1
3204	Terna S.S.S.K. Ltd.	Ternanagar	1
3205	Thankam Laboratories	New Delhi	1
3206	The Asiatic Oxygen and Acetylene Co. Ltd.	Calcutta	1
3207	The Assam Company Ltd.	Calcutta	1
3208	The Cooperative League of the USA	New Delhi	1
3209	The Environmental Engineering Company	Madras	1
3210	The Fertiliser Association of India	Pune	1
3211	The Mahalakshmi Sugar Mills Co. Ltd.	Haridwar	1
3212	The Nizams Institute of Medical Sciences	Punjagutta	1
3213	The Pondicherry Co-operative Milk Producers' Union Ltd.	Pondicherry	1
3214	The Saraswati Sugarmills	Yamuna Nagar	1
3215	The Sonjivani (Takli) S.S. Ltd.	Ahmednagar	1
3216	The Soyabean Processors Association of India	Indore	1
3217	The World Bank Resident Mission	New Delhi	1
3218	Thermax and Wilcox Private Ltd.	Pune	1
3219	Thiru Arooran Sugars Limited	Koonancheri	1
3220	Tinsukia Commerce College	Tinsukia	1
3221	Tissue Culture Laboratory, Division of Plant Physiology and Biochemistry Research	Hessaraghatta	1
3222	Tong Swasthya Bhavan ⁴⁰ Institutional Area Near Qutab Hotel	New Delhi	1
3223	Toxicology Unit Regional Res. Lab.	Hyderabad	1
3224	Tribal Agricultural Research Station	Mandla	1
3225	Tribal Area Reseach Centre	Phulbani	1
3226	Tribal Area Research Project	Chickhaldara	1
3227	Triveni Engineering Works Ltd.	New Delhi	1
3228	Tuberculosis Research Centre	Amargadh	1
3229	Tuberculosis Research Centre	Madras	1
3230	Tungabhadra Machinery and Tools Ltd.	Hyderabad	1
3231	Tungbhadra Sugar Works Limited	Shimoga	1
3232	U.P. Financial Corporation	Ghaziabad	1
3233	U.P. State Sugar Corporation Ltd.	Dehra Dun	1
3234	Ubeshwar Vikas Mandal	Udaipur	1
3235	UCI, UNICEF.	Jaipur	1
3236	Udhewala Fruit Research Station	Jammu	1
3237	Ugar Sugar Works Ltd.	Belgaum	1

SI No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
3238	Ugar Sugar Works Ltd.	Ugarkhurd	1
3239	Ujjain University	Ujjain	1
3240	Umaid Hospital	Jodhpur	1
3241	Unicorn Biotek Ltd.	Hyderabad	1
3242	UNIDO	Madras	1
3243	Union Carbide R & D Center	Bhopal	1
3244	University Biochemical Laboratories	Madras	1
3245	University College	Thiruvananthapuram	1
3246	University of Agricultural Science and Technology	Kashmir	1
3247	University of Agricultural Sciences	Belvatagi	1
3248	University of Agricultural Sciences	Chintamani	1
3249	University of Agricultural Sciences	Hessaraghatta	1
3250	University of Agricultural Sciences	Magod	1
3251	University of Agricultural Sciences	Mandya	1
3252	University of Agricultural Sciences	Shimoga	1
3253	University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology	Manasbal	1
3254	University of Agriculture	Faizalabad	1
3255	University of Agriculture and Technology	Nainital	1
3256	University of Horticulture and Forestry	Solan	1
3257	University of Horticulture and Forestry, Regional Fruit Research Station	Shimla	1
3258	University of Jordan	Jordan	1
3259	University of Medical Sciences and G.T.B. Hospital	New Delhi	1
3260	UP Council of Sugarcane Research	Kashipur	1
3261	UPASI Krishi Vigyan Kendra	Coonoor	1
3262	UPASI Tea Advisory Service	Gudalur	1
3263	UPASI Tea Advisory Service	Munnar	1
3264	UPASI Tea Research Sub-Station	Vandiperiyar	1
3265	Uttar Pradesh State Sugar Corporation Ltd.	Meerut	1
3266	V.B. Rural Institute	Udaipur	1
3267	V.S. Mehta College of Science	Bharwari	1
3268	V.S.J. College	Rajnagar	1
3269	Vaccine Research Centre, Centre for Animal Health Studies	Madras	1
3270	Vaikunth Mehta National Institute of Cooperative Management	Pune	1
3271	Vaish College	Rohtak	1
3272	Vanaspati Manufacturers' Association of India	New Delhi	1
3273	Vasantdad Shetkari Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana Ltd.	Sangli	1
3274	Vegetable Research Station	Kalyanpur	1
3275	Vellore Coop. Sugar Mills Ltd.	Vellore	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
3276	Vellore Sugar Mills	Vellore	1
3277	Venkataramapuram	Valliveda	1
3278	Venkateshwara Hatcheries Pvt. Limited	Pune	1
3279	Veterinary Clinics	New Delhi	1
3280	Veterinary College and Research Institute	Salem	1
3281	Veterinary Diagnostic Laboratory	Mysore	1
3282	Veterinary Dispensary	Tirunelveli	1
3283	Veterinary Dispensary	Trichur	1
3284	Veterinary Dispensary cum Key Village Centre	Madras	1
3285	Veterinary Hospital	Mehla	1
3286	Veterinary Hospital	Solan	1
3287	Veterinary Polyclinic	Ahmednagar	1
3288	Veterinary Polyclinic	Calicut	1
3289	Veterinary Polyclinic Campus	Srikakulam	1
3290	Veterinary Reasearch Institute	Hyderabad	1
3291	VHL Laboratory	Hyderabad	1
3292	Victoria Jubilee Technical Institute	Bombay	1
3293	Vidyawardhini College	Kolhapur	1
3294	Vigyan Ashram	Pune	1
3295	Vindhyachal Distilleries P. Ltd.	Bhopal	1
3296	Visakha Cooperative Dairy	Visakhapatnam	1
3297	Vishnu Sugar Mills Ltd.	Gopalganj	1
3298	Visveswaraya Iron and Steel Ltd.	Bhadravathi	1
3299	Vivekananda Mahavidyalaya	Burdwan	1
3300	VLN Hospital	Razole	1
3301	Voluntary Health Association of India	New Delhi	1
3302	Vrindaban Research Institute	Raman Reti	1
3303	Walchandnagar Industries Limited	Walchandnagar	1
3304	Water and Land Management Inst.	Bhopal	1
3305	Water and Land Management Institute	New Delhi	1
3306	Water and Land Management Training and Res. Inst.	Hyderabad	1
3307	Water and Mineral Exploration Research and Training Institute	Hyderabad	1
3308	Water Research Centre	Chandigarh	1
3309	Water Resources Department	Gandhinagar	1
3310	Water Resources Development Training Cent.	Roorkee	1
3311	Watershed Development Project	Mangrulpir	1
3312	Wesley Boys' College	Hyderabad	1
3313	West Bengal Forest Department	Calcutta	1
3314	West Coast Herbochem Pvt. Ltd.	Bombay	1
3315	Western India Industries	Pune	1
3316	Western Regional Research Centre	Avikanagar	1
3317	Wheat Research Station	Junagadh	1

Sl No.	Institution	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
3318	WHO Plasmodium falciparum Containment Programme	Bhubaneswar	1
3319	Wimco Ltd.	Bombay	1
3320	Wimco Ltd.	New Delhi	1
3321	Winrock International	New Delhi	1
3322	Women's Christian College	Madras	1
3323	Women's College	Jamshedpur	1
3324	Women's University	Bombay	1
3325	Wood Science and Technology Division	Palampur	1
3326	Working Plan and Research Circle	Srinagar	1
3327	Working Plans and Development Circle	Bangalore	1
3328	World Food Programme	Jaisalmer	1
3329	Xavier Institute of Management	Bhubaneswar	1
3330	Yellow Fever Vaccine Section, Central Research Institute	Kasauli	1
3331	Yeshwant Mahavidyalaya	Nanded	1
3332	Zakir Hussain College	New Delhi	1
3333	Zandu Pharmaceutical Works Ltd.	Bombay	1
3334	Zonal Adaptive Research Station	Krishnanagar	1
3335	Zonal Agricultural Research Station	Raipur	1
3336	Zonal Agricultural Research Station	Rewa	1
3337	Zoological Gardens Alipore	Calcutta	1
	PRIVATE		300
Total			51761

The names of institutions are not standardized in *CAB Abstracts*. For example, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Vishvavidyalaya is also referred to as BC Agricultural University, BCKV, and Bidhan Chandra University. It took considerable effort to merge all papers from the same institution named differently. Also most agricultural university have many centres. For example Panjab Agricultural University has its main centre at Ludhiana and other centre in eight other towns viz. Gurdaspur, Jalandhar, Bathinda, Faridkot, Abohar, Amritsar, Kapurthala, Kheri. However, these are not merged into a single entry.

Table 8: Contributions made by different organisations as seen from CAB Abstracts 1990 - 94

Academic	-	32805		
Research	-	10966		
Ministries (Central)	-	1830		
State Govt	-	3614		
Private	-	924		
International	-	704		
Home Address	-	122		
Hospital	-	178		
Foundation	-	137		
Society	-	109		
Project	-	63		
Bank	-	13		
Unknown	-	296		
		<u>51761</u>		
Academic				
<i>Universities</i>				
Agricultural	-	16555	<i>Colleges</i>	
General	-	9933	Agricultural	- 3463
Medical	-	304	General	- 2026
Engineering	-	110	Medical	- 334
		<u>26902</u>	Engineering	- 70
				<u>5903</u>
Scientific Agencies				
Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR)	-			7856
Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR)	-			2248
Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR)	-			527
Department of Atomic Energy (DAE)	-			253
Defence Research and Development Organization (DRDO)	-			82
				<u>10966</u>
Ministries				
Ministry of Environment and Forests	-			360
Ministry of Commerce	-			278
Ministry of Science and Technol	-			255
Ministry of Health and Family Welfare	-			250
Ministry of Textiles	-			222
Ministry of Agriculture	-			156
Ministry of Food and Civil Supplies	-			71
Ministry of Human Resource	-			65
Ministry of Chemical fertilizers	-			53
Ministry of Planning	-			37
Ministry of Water Resource	-			23
Ministry of Rural development	-			18
Ministry of Defence	-			14
Ministry of Industry	-			11
Ministry of Mines	-			7
Ministry of Energy	-			4
Ministry of Steel and Mines	-			4
Ministry of Finance	-			1
Ministry of Railways	-			1
Total				<u>1830</u>

Table 9: Indian states contributing to the world literature of agriculture as seen from CAB Abstracts 1990 - 94 (Arranged by number of papers)

Sl No.	State / Union territory	Number of papers
1	Uttar Pradesh	8327
2	Maharashtra	4084
3	Tamil Nadu	4072
4	Haryana	4017
5	Karnataka	3984
6	New Delhi (UT)	3666
7	Andhra Pradesh	3557
8	Punjab	2910
9	West Bengal	2866
10	Madhya Pradesh	2091
11	Himachal Pradesh	1799
12	Rajasthan	1798
13	Gujarat	1710
14	Kerala	1484
15	Bihar	1303
16	Orissa	1158
17	Assam	737
18	Jammu & Kashmir	675
19	Chandigarh (UT)	507
20	Meghalaya	376
21	Andaman & Nicobar Islands (UT)	157
22	Pondicherry (UT)	130
23	Manipur	111
24	Goa	60
25	Sikkim	54
26	Tripura	51
27	Nagaland	38
28	Arunachal Pradesh	14
29	Mizoram	5
30	Lakshadweep	1
31	Unknown	19
Total		51761

UT denotes Union Territory

Table 10: Indian cities contributing to the world literature of agriculture as seen from *CAB Abstracts 1990 – 1994* (Arranged by number of papers)

Sl No.	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
1	New Delhi	3664
2	Ludhiana	2636
3	Hissar	2545
4	Bangalore	2086
5	Coimbatore	1666
6	Hyderabad	1643
7	Lucknow	1245
8	Kamal	1180
9	Mohanpur	1013
10	Madras	950
11	Pantnagar	938
12	Izatnagar	923
13	Calcutta	904
14	Dehra Dun	883
15	Anand	821
16	Dharwad	784
17	Jabalpur	754
18	Varanasi	740
19	Bombay	688
20	Palampur	668
21	Pune	664
22	Bhubaneswar	642
23	Solan	623
24	Patancheru	591
25	Parbhani	579
26	Akola	563
27	Kanpur	519
28	Ranchi	518
29	Mysore	510
30	Aligarh	507
31	Chandigarh	506
32	Jorhat	483
33	Rahuri	482
34	Srinagar	467
35	Pusa	452
36	Thiruvananthapuram	450
37	Tirupati	439
38	Nagpur	418
39	Simla	367
40	Jodhpur	366

Sl No.	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
41	Shillong	321
42	Madurai	288
43	Jaipur	287
44	Faridabad	272
45	Allahabad	239
46	Indore	237
47	Gorakhpur	236
48	Jhansi	234
49	Agra	223
50	Meerut	219
51	Udaipur	206
52	Trichur	204
53	Raipur	198
54	Cuttack	197
55	Bikaner	190
56	Calicut	184
57	Nainital	178
58	Kalyani	174
59	Bhagalpur	172
60	Junagadh	164
61	Bhopal	163
62	Dapoli	162
63	Patna	160
64	Port Blair	154
65	Jobner	149
66	Warangal	145
67	Pondicherry	143
68	Peechi	137
69	Guwahati	136
70	Ahmedabad	134
71	Sehore	127
72	Gwalior	124
73	Cuddapah	116
74	Bapatla	115
75	Baroda	114
76	Mhow	110
77	Faizabad	108
78	Kharagpur	108
79	Visakhappatinam	105
80	Samastipur	102
81	Chickmagalur	101
82	Navsari	101
83	Patiala	98
84	Burdwan	95
85	Sambalpur	95

Sl No.	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
86	Almora	92
87	Kurukshetra	92
88	Sagar	92
89	Parangipettai	91
90	Aurangabad	85
91	Kolhapur	84
92	Santiniketan	84
93	Gangtok	83
94	Mathura	83
95	Kottayam	80
96	Raichur	79
97	Imphal	78
98	Jammu	76
99	Guntur	75
100	Jammu & Kashmir	74
101	Rohtak	73
102	Vallabh Vidyanagar	71
103	Ananthapur	70
104	Sardar Krushinagar	70
105	Tiruchirapalli	70
106	Waltair	70
107	Roorkee	68
108	Rajahmundry	65
109	Rewa	60
110	Berhampore	59
111	Kasaragod	58
112	Vellayani	58
113	Kalayani	55
114	Mukteswar	55
115	Amritsar	53
116	Avikanagar	53
117	Barapani	53
118	Bhavanisagar	53
119	Kochi	51
120	Ujjain	51
121	Darjeeling	50
122	Kullu	50
123	Barrackpore	47
124	Jalandhar	47
125	Mangalore	47
126	Padappai	47
127	Vridhachalam	47
128	Bareilly	45
129	Gaya	43
130	Sabour	43

SI No.	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
131	Annamalainagar	42
132	Vadodara	42
133	Vellore	42
134	Bhavnagar	41
135	Nashik	41
136	Vittal	41
137	Chaubattia	39
138	Deoria	39
139	Jalgaon	38
140	Surat	38
141	Erode	37
142	Mudigere	37
143	Periyakulam	37
144	Bilaspur	36
145	Chhindwara	36
146	Manipal	36
147	Saharanpur	36
148	Cuddalore	35
149	Gurgaon	35
150	Jammu Tawi	35
151	Kayangulam	35
152	Midnapore	35
153	Modipuram	35
154	Nagarjunanagar	34
155	Trichur	34
156	Shimoga	33
157	Shahjahanpur	32
158	Muzaffarnagar	31
159	Muzaffarpur	30
160	Aduthurai	29
161	Canchipur	29
162	Pudukkottai	29
163	Udhagamandalam	29
164	Siliguri	28
165	Alwar	26
166	Anakapalle	26
167	Bharuch	26
168	Gulbarga	25
169	Makhdoom	25
170	Palur	25
171	Medziphema	24
172	Pilicode	24
173	Kota	22
174	Sriganganagar	22
175	Thanjavur	22

Sl No.	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
176	Yercaud	22
177	Brahmavar	21
178	Sriniketan	21
179	Vamban	21
180	Agartala	20
181	Aliyarnagar	20
182	Gurdaspur	20
183	Hazaribagh	20
184	Mannuthy	20
185	Namakkal	20
186	Pattambi	20
187	Ratnagiri	20
188	Ahmednagar	19
189	Dibrugarh	19
190	Dona Paula	19
191	Howrah	19
192	Unknown	19
193	Hardwar	18
194	Kodaikanal	18
195	Latur	18
196	Solapur	18
197	Dinhata	17
198	Goa	17
199	Moradabad	17
200	Nadiad	17
201	Shalimar	17
202	Shantiniketan	17
203	Khandwa	16
204	Killikulam	16
205	Palayankottai	16
206	Tuticorin	16
207	Valparai	16
208	Bathinda	15
209	Bijapur	15
210	Dhanbad	15
211	Durgapur	15
212	Farah	15
213	Garhwal	15
214	Lembucherra	15
215	Moncompu	15
216	Pithoragarh	15
217	Rajkot	15
218	Ajmer	14
219	Biharsharif	14
220	Darbhanga	14

Sl No.	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
221	Dhaulakuan	14
222	Keonjhar	14
223	Mettupalayam	14
224	Ranichauri	14
225	Amravati	13
226	Bidar	13
227	Chinsurah	13
228	Etawah	13
229	Ghaziabad	13
230	Jamshedpur	13
231	Kodagu	13
232	Kotdwara	13
233	Madikeri	13
234	Nipani	13
235	Paramakudi	13
236	Sunabeda	13
237	Udayagiri	13
238	Ambikapur	12
239	Cooch Behar	12
240	Hassan	12
241	Kandali	12
242	Kattupakkam	12
243	Kovilpatti	12
244	Mandya	12
245	Maruteru	12
246	Morena	12
247	Rourkela	12
248	Salem	12
249	Tezpur	12
250	Titabar	12
251	Banavasi	11
252	Basar	11
253	Basti	11
254	Sirsa	11
255	Azamgarh	10
256	Chattarpur	10
257	Dhule	10
258	Gandhigram	10
259	Karad	10
260	Kaul	10
261	Kinnaur	10
262	Mandsaur	10
263	Nagercoil	10
264	Palem	10
265	Puttur	10

Sl No.	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
266	Ranbir Singh Pura	10
267	Ranikhet	10
268	Sandynallah	10
269	Tindivanam	10
270	Bahraich	9
271	Balrampur	9
272	Bawal	9
273	Cannanore	9
274	Canning Town	9
275	Chettalli	9
276	Durg	9
277	Faridkot	9
278	Jagtial	9
279	Jassur	9
280	Katrain	9
281	Kavali	9
282	Nandad	9
283	Nellore	9
284	Palani	9
285	Sopore	9
286	Tirur	9
287	Tripura	9
288	Vallanad	9
289	Wardha	9
290	Warora	9
291	Ambasamudram	8
292	Bankura	8
293	Banswara	8
294	Boko	8
295	Chundale	8
296	Dholi	8
297	Diphu	8
298	Gossaigaon	8
299	Guna	8
300	Haldwani	8
301	Jagdapur	8
302	Kasauli	8
303	Kottakkal	8
304	Negaland	8
305	Niphad	8
306	Paiyur	8
307	Phaltan	8
308	Powarkheda	8
309	Sirugamani	8
310	Sorbhag	8

Sl No.	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
311	Abohar	7
312	Bajaura	7
313	Banderdewa	7
314	Bellary	7
315	Bulandshahr	7
316	Burnihat	7
317	Chintamani	7
318	Chiplima	7
319	Dharmapuri	7
320	Ernakulam	7
321	Girdh	7
322	Hingoli	7
323	Hoshiarpur	7
324	Kakinada	7
325	Kangra	7
326	Kedrapara	7
327	Modinagar	7
328	Nagaon	7
329	Nandyal	7
330	Parganas	7
331	Puri	7
332	Udgir	7
333	Uttarkashi	7
334	Valsad	7
335	Vellanikkara	7
336	Balasore	6
337	Ballia	6
338	Baripada	6
339	Belgaum	6
340	Bhadreswar Hooghly	6
341	Bhalukpong	6
342	Chengalpattu	6
343	Chittoor	6
344	Gandhinagar	6
345	Godhra	6
346	Iduuky	6
347	Kapurthala	6
348	Mahabaleswar	6
349	Margao	6
350	Medinipur	6
351	Munger	6
352	Myladumpara	6
353	Panaji	6
354	Phulpur	6
355	Pilani	6

Sl No.	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
356	Sandynallah	6
357	Sindri	6
358	Siruguppa	6
359	Tirunelveli	6
360	Tirupathisaram	6
361	Vidisha	6
362	Aonla	5
363	Arbhavi	5
364	Bhadrak	5
365	Bhilwara	5
366	Birbhum	5
367	Chail	5
368	Chalakudy	5
369	Doddi	5
370	Gopeshwar	5
371	Gynapur	5
372	Jaisalmer	5
373	Jharmapani	5
374	Kalol	5
375	Palamaner	5
376	Ponnampet	5
377	Rishikesh	5
378	Srivilliputhur	5
379	Tiptur	5
380	Virudhunagar	5
381	Alwaye	4
382	Amadalavalasa	4
383	Anjora	4
384	Aruppukottai	4
385	Balaghat	4
386	Berthin	4
387	Coonoor	4
388	Gangavanthi	4
389	Gangavati	4
390	Hazira	4
391	Hunsur	4
392	Itanagar	4
393	Jalpaiguri	4
394	Jaunpur	4
395	Jhalawar	4
396	Jhargram	4
397	Kandaghat	4
398	Karimganj	4
399	Kheri	4
400	Koraput	4

Sl No.	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
401	Kumarakom	4
402	Kurnool	4
403	Lakhaoti	4
404	Lali	4
405	Mehsana	4
406	Melalathur	4
407	Mussoorie	4
408	Namrup	4
409	Narmadanagar	4
410	Panipat	4
411	Panvel	4
412	Perumalapalle	4
413	Phondagat	4
414	Pithapuram	4
415	Podalakur	4
416	Pratapgarh	4
417	Sangareddy	4
418	Satana	4
419	Sikkim	4
420	Tikamgarh	4
421	Vijayawada	4
422	Wayanad	4
423	Zuarinagar	4
424	Annigeri	3
425	Ariyalur	3
426	Arundhati Nagar	3
427	Balaspore	3
428	Belvatagi	3
429	Bharatpur	3
430	Bhaushaebnagar	3
431	Chidambaram	3
432	Dharani Nagar	3
433	Fatehpur	3
434	Fdhamandalan	3
435	Gobichettipalayam	3
436	Gonikopal	3
437	Gudivada	3
438	Hoshangabad	3
439	Hubli	3
440	Jachh	3
441	Jagdishpur	3
442	Karaikudi	3
443	Katihar	3
444	Kattankolathur	3
445	Khammam	3

Sl No.	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
446	Khananpara	3
447	Kolar	3
448	Kotebazar	3
449	Kovilangulam	3
450	Krishnanagar	3
451	Lakhimpur	3
452	Lamphelpat	3
453	Mahbubnagar	3
454	Malda	3
455	Mangrol	3
456	Mirza	3
457	Murshidabad	3
458	Muvattupuzha	3
459	North Lakhmipur	3
460	North Parur	3
461	Pali	3
462	Palode	3
463	Parite	3
464	Phulbani	3
465	Poondi	3
466	Rae Bareli	3
467	Rahara	3
468	Saklespur	3
469	Sangli	3
470	Shikohabad	3
471	Simour	3
472	Sindewahi	3
473	Sirsi	3
474	Surathkal	3
475	Thane	3
476	Thirupathisram	3
477	Tinsukia	3
478	Valvada	3
479	Vedasandur	3
480	Vuyyuru	3
481	Wakawali	3
482	Aizawl	2
483	Ambala	2
484	Anantharajpet	2
485	Andaman and Nicobar Islands	2
486	Amej	2
487	Badnapur	2
488	Balipara Lokra	2
489	Bambolim	2
490	Bardoli	2

SI No.	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
491	Beawar	2
492	Bethuadahri	2
493	Bhawanipatna	2
494	Bhilai	2
495	Biswanath	2
496	Bongaon	2
497	Cauvery	2
498	Chandemagore	2
499	Cheyar	2
500	Chickballapur	2
501	Dholpur	2
502	Diggi	2
503	Ela	2
504	Ghaghraghat	2
505	Godavari	2
506	Gola Gokarannath	2
507	Golaghat	2
508	Gopalnagar	2
509	Gurazala	2
510	Haldia	2
511	Hamirpur	2
512	Hathras	2
513	Iqbalpur	2
514	Jiagunj	2
515	Kakdwip	2
516	Kalahandi	2
517	Kamareddy	2
518	Kanchipuram	2
519	Kandla	2
520	Kandwa	2
521	Karagpur	2
522	Katol	2
523	Kendraparha	2
524	Kheda	2
525	Khudwani	2
526	Koduvalli	2
527	Kolasib	2
528	Kollam	2
529	Kozhencherry	2
530	Kufri	2
531	Kumulur	2
532	Kunchanapalli	2
533	Kunjban	2
534	Kurukali	2
535	Madhira	2

Sl No.	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
536	Mandasur	2
537	Mandla	2
538	Margherita	2
539	Mawana	2
540	Melvisharam	2
541	Mizoram	2
542	Motihari	2
543	Nagamangala	2
544	Nagrakata	2
545	Nagratala	2
546	Nagrota-bagwan	2
547	Naihati	2
548	Najibabad	2
549	Nalgonda	2
550	Nangal	2
551	Narasaraopet	2
552	Neyveli	2
553	North Lakhmipur	2
554	Nowshera	2
555	Paithan	2
556	Palacode	2
557	Palghar	2
558	Palghat	2
559	Pampadumpura	2
560	Pantharapur	2
561	Pasighat	2
562	Periyar	2
563	Peshawar	2
564	Pilibhit	2
565	Pottaneri	2
566	Powerkheda	2
567	Prasanthi Nilayam	2
568	Raigarh	2
569	Rajpipla	2
570	Rampura	2
571	Ranipet	2
572	Rapar	2
573	Sangla	2
574	Sevagram	2
575	Shahabad	2
576	Shirval	2
577	Shivnagar	2
578	Sidhi	2
579	Sipighat	2
580	Sivakasi	2

SI No.	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
581	Sonepat	2
582	Srikakulam	2
583	Sultanpur	2
584	Sumerpur	2
585	Sundargarh	2
586	Tabo	2
587	Tadepalligudem	2
588	Talipramba	2
589	Tanuku	2
590	Tehri Garhwal	2
591	Thiruvalla	2
592	Tirutani	2
593	Tiruvalangadu	2
594	Tiruvarur	2
595	Turbhe	2
596	Udupi	2
597	Ullal	2
598	Vadapudupet	2
599	Velhagao	2
600	Veppankulam	2
601	Washim	2
602	Wellington	2
603	Yamuna Nagar	2
604	Achalpur	1
605	Alleppey	1
606	Amargadh	1
607	Ambajogai	1
608	Ambernath	1
609	Amlai	1
610	Araria	1
611	Arudchutinagar	1
612	Arunapuram	1
613	Atara	1
614	Athmallik	1
615	Bagwan	1
616	Ballawal Saunkhri	1
617	Bangaon	1
618	Baraut	1
619	Beloniya	1
620	Bhad	1
621	Bhadravati	1
622	Bhandra	1
623	Bheemarayangudi	1
624	Bhind	1
625	Bichapuri	1

Sl No.	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
626	Bir	1
627	Bodinayakanur	1
628	Budaun	1
629	C.r. Nagar	1
630	Chaibasa	1
631	Chalthan	1
632	Chamba	1
633	Chamoli	1
634	Chandrapur	1
635	Chintapalli	1
636	Chirimiri	1
637	Churachandpur	1
638	Dadahu	1
639	Damanjodi	1
640	Dapchari	1
641	Daurala	1
642	Davangere	1
643	Dhenkanal	1
644	Dhuri	1
645	Dumka	1
646	Dungarpur	1
647	Duttapur Wardima	1
648	Eriyad	1
649	Etah	1
650	Fertilizernagar	1
651	Gabalphur	1
652	Ganganagar	1
653	Ganjam	1
654	Gardoli	1
655	Garsa	1
656	Ghatanji	1
657	Gondia	1
658	Gopalganj	1
659	Guan	1
660	Gudiyatham	1
661	Hapur	1
662	Harinagar	1
663	Haringhata	1
664	Haripad	1
665	Hekra	1
666	Hessarghatta	1
667	Hetampur	1
668	Hilli	1
669	Hiwara	1
670	Hutbay	1

Sl No.	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
671	Jahanabad	1
672	Jalna	1
673	Jamnagar	1
674	Jatanbari	1
675	Jeelugumilli	1
676	Jeolikote	1
677	Jeypore	1
678	Jhang	1
679	Jhour	1
680	Jinol	1
681	Joara	1
682	Kadiri	1
683	Kalamati	1
684	Kalimpong	1
685	Kalpa	1
686	Kalpakkam	1
687	Kandia	1
688	Kannara	1
689	Kanyakumari	1
690	Karakwasla	1
691	Karamana	1
692	Karjat	1
693	Kasgonj	1
694	Kashipur	1
695	Kathalagere	1
696	Kaveripattinam	1
697	Khargone	1
698	Khariar	1
699	Kishanganj	1
700	Kokrajar	1
701	Kolenchery	1
702	Kotagiri	1
703	Krishnapuram	1
704	Krishnarajasagara	1
705	Kumarganj	1
706	Kumbakonam	1
707	Kuttamperoor	1
708	Lalandi	1
709	Lalgola	1
710	Latehar	1
711	Madhepur	1
712	Madhopur	1
713	Madhubani	1
714	Magod	1
715	Mahad	1

Sl No.	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
716	Mahuva	1
717	Malegaon	1
718	Manahari	1
719	Manasbal	1
720	Mandi Dabwali	1
721	Mangrulpir	1
722	Medak	1
723	Meghalaya	1
724	Melvisharam	1
725	Mennonpara	1
726	Minicoy	1
727	Mohol	1
728	Mokokchung	1
729	Mugad	1
730	Muktsar	1
731	Multan	1
732	Munirabad	1
733	Munnar	1
734	Muthorai	1
735	Nagicherra	1
736	Nagla	1
737	Nalanda	1
738	Narendrapur	1
739	Narsinghpur	1
740	Nauni	1
741	Nayanangal	1
742	Nekarikallu	1
743	Nelamangala	1
744	Nizamabad	1
745	Nopa	1
746	North Kanara	1
747	Odakkali	1
748	Palaparru	1
749	Pali-marwar	1
750	Pallapuram	1
751	Paonta Sahib	1
752	Parkal	1
753	Parur	1
754	Patan	1
755	Pauri Garhwal	1
756	Peddapalli	1
757	Pollibetta	1
758	Ponneri	1
759	Pottangi	1
760	Pramakudi	1

Sl No.	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
761	Pravaranagar	1
762	Pulla	1
763	Punganoor	1
764	Purulia	1
765	Quilon	1
766	Raghavendra Nagar	1
767	Raigadh	1
768	Ramagundam	1
769	Ramgarh	1
770	Rath	1
771	Razole	1
772	Rewari	1
773	Ropar	1
774	Rupnagar	1
775	Sahibganj	1
776	Sakoli	1
777	Samayanallur	1
778	Samba	1
779	Sameerwadi	1
780	Sangamner	1
781	Sangli	1
782	Sardar Shahar	1
783	Sarkand	1
784	Sattur	1
785	Saveriyarpuram	1
786	Shahdol	1
787	Shankargarh	1
788	Sharbu Kinnaur	1
789	Sherghati	1
790	Shertallai	1
791	Shirgaon	1
792	Shirol	1
793	Shringonda	1
794	Sikar	1
795	Sringeri	1
796	Srinivasanagar	1
797	Sullurpet	1
798	Sundernagar	1
799	Supaul	1
800	Surendrabag Kardej	1
801	Suri	1
802	Takkolam	1
803	Taloda	1
804	Tandojam	1
805	Tavanur	1

SI No.	City/town	Number of Indian Papers
806	Tekari	1
807	Thadiyankudisai	1
808	Thal	1
809	Thana	1
810	Thandigudi	1
811	Tirupur	1
812	Tirurkuppam	1
813	Tiruvazhamkunru	1
814	Titligarh	1
815	Travancore	1
816	Trivaudrasu	1
817	Tumkur	1
818	Tura	1
819	Ugarkhurd	1
820	Vandiperiyar	1
821	Vengurla	1
822	Venkatramannagudem	1
823	Vemgurla	1
824	Vijapur	1
825	Virbhadra	1
826	Vizianagaram	1
827	Vrindanan	1
828	W Champam	1
829	Wadura	1
830	Warananagar	1
831	Wavora	1
832	Yavatmal	1
833	Zirukpur	1
834	Unknown	19
Total		51761